

Research Unit FOR240

Image Sequence Analysis to Investigate Dynamic Processes

Progress Report Phase II (3/1998–2/2001)

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Preface

This report presents the results of the second phase (3/1998 - 2/2001) of the research unit (Forschergruppe) “Image Sequence Processing to Study Dynamic Processes”. The research unit was founded in December 1995. In the second funding period two more application areas (projects E and F) were added to the research unit.

Scope and General Research Strategy

The central theme of the research unit is the study of transport, exchange, and growth processes by

- developing and using visualization techniques that take image sequences and extract the biological or physical parameters of interest and make them visible, and by
- using image sequence processing techniques to tackle key scientific questions in various research areas that cannot be studied adequately without these techniques.

A close and interdisciplinary cooperation between applications and fundamental research in image analysis is the most distinct feature of the research unit. In the first phase of the research unit it has become evident that the interaction between basic research in image sequence processing and the different application areas was a key element for the achieved progress. The Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing (Interdisziplinäres Zentrum für Wissenschaftliches Rechnen, IWR) at Heidelberg University with its rich history of groundbreaking interdisciplinary cooperation proved to be a stimulating environment for the research unit. The IWR was founded several years ago as a central institute of Heidelberg University with just such interdisciplinary activities in mind.

Usage of a Common Software Platform

All members of the research group use a common, portable, modular, and open software environment. This software package runs both on UNIX platforms and on PCs under Windows95/NT and incorporates data structures for image sequences, volumetric data and multigrid image processing. It also supports real-time image sequence acquisition with a number of frame grabbers.

The software is used for the development of the algorithms *and* for all application projects of the research unit for the acquisition, interactive evaluation, and analysis of image sequences. With the aid of a powerful scripting language that allocates image objects and defines operators on the basis of the built-in algorithms, the software can quickly be adapted to new experimental setups and be used for automatic batch processing of large quantities of image data. Newly developed algorithms are exchanged either via DLLs or shared libraries or workspaces using the scripting language.

Usage of Standard Hardware

Our research focuses on the development of effective algorithms running on standard hardware platforms. This approach is validated by the following facts. First, the algorithms for image processing become more and more complex, making it increasingly difficult to port algorithms to dedicated image processing hardware. Second, instruction sets for pixel processing, e. g., VIS and MMX, are incorporated into general purpose hardware boosting the time-consuming low-level image processing. Third, the scientific community at large should profit from the progress gained by the work of this research unit.

Sharing of Equipment

The members of the research unit share a central pool of equipment for image sequence acquisition and image sequence analysis. This includes a cluster of computers suited for real-time sampling of image sequences,

various cameras in the visible and infrared range, geometric and radiometric calibration setups, and other equipment used in several projects jointly to take image sequences. This approach ensures the effective usage of expensive equipment by different research groups.

Intensive Communication between Development and Applications

A weekly workshop seminar fosters the interdisciplinary cooperation and provides a forum that the members of the research group meet each other on a regular base. The seminar is also used to discuss the development of the image sequence processing algorithms between the core project and the different application areas or any other topics that arise. The progress of the individual projects and the development of further cooperation was also reviewed in several internal workshops that took place on November 16, 1996, March 8, 1997 (both Carl-Benz-House, Ladenburg), January 22/23 (Heidelberg), December 8, 1999, and May 24, 2000 (both in Oberflockenbach).

International Collaboration

Actual topics in the research areas of the research unit were discussed in the weekly colloquium of the research unit. A complete list of all talks of guests given in the colloquium from the winter semester 1995/1996 through the summer semester 2000 is given in appendix IV. This section also lists all research stays of guests with the research unit and research stays of members of the research unit abroad. The members of the research unit also gave a number of invited talks and have been invited for external research stays (appendix III). All groups of the research unit have close contacts and cooperation to leading international research centers.

The progress made in the research unit was presented to and discussed with the international research community at the first workshop “Image Sequence Processing to Study Dynamical Processes” that took place from June 4–6, 1997 in Heidelberg and the second workshop from September 19–22, 2000.

Acknowledgments

Financial support for this research unit by the German Science Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) is gratefully acknowledged. The principal investigators are also grateful for the constructive and detailed comments of the review committee. By reading this progress report and the renewal proposal the reviewers will find that their comments have been taken seriously and have considerably improved the cooperation and scientific outcome of the research unit.

We also would like to thank the administration of Heidelberg University for providing some matching funds in difficult times and the vice rectors for scientific research, Prof. Jörg Hüfner and later Prof. Heinz Horner, for their support of and interest in this research unit. Likewise, we are grateful for the advice and support of Prof. Willi Jäger and Prof. Jürgen Warnatz, directors of the IWR.

Finally the principal investigators would like to cordially thank all diploma and doctoral students that participated in this research unit. Their work was substantial for the achieved progress. With a lot of enthusiasm they picked up the ideas of this truly interdisciplinary research and took the extra effort to fill it with life by contributing much to the open-minded interdisciplinary cooperation. A complete list of all diploma theses and dissertations that were undertaken in the research unit is given in appendix II.

Heidelberg, August 2000

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A Image Sequence Analysis

1 Introduction and Summary

This project is the core project of the research unit. Its task is to provide the image sequence processing algorithms required for the application projects B through F.

In phase II of the research unit, emphasis was on further enhancement of low-level and model-based image sequence processing including

- a toolbox for image sequence processing that models motion fields and interesting parameters of dynamic processes directly in a flexible way (Section 2),
- studies on performance characteristics of image sequence algorithms (Section 3),
- filter optimization (Section 4),
- scale-space analysis for image sequences (Section 5),
- 3-D reconstruction with a single moving camera (Section 6), and
- extension of all these techniques to multichannel image sequences (Section 7).

The development of visualization techniques was a further goal of the research unit. Based on the advice of the reviewers, we did not develop visualization tools within the core project but rather used available tools. Specific visualization techniques for particle tracking have been developed in project F.

2 Modeling Motion and Dynamic Processes in Image Sequences

This topic is of central importance for the research unit as the estimation of motion is not sufficient to completely analyze dynamic processes. When the research unit was initiated five years ago we had the following approach to this problem in mind: We would first determine a motion field and derive the underlying parameters, for example the growth rate by computing the divergence of the flow field, in a second step. However, this approach requires dense motion fields. Whenever such dense motion fields can not be determined, it is not possible to derive any further parameters.

It constitutes one of the most significant progresses of the research unit to develop a general concept with which the motion field *and* parameters of dynamic processes can be estimated directly in a *single step*. The concept is very general in the sense that the parameters of any dynamic process that can be modeled by a linear partial differential equation can be quantified. Since most physical, chemical, and biological processes can be described by equations of this type, it covers many applications of the research unit. Moreover, in certain cases it is possible to estimate parameters of dynamic processes although the motion field can only be determined partially. In this section, we briefly describe the approach. For details, especially the mathematical background we refer to our publications.

2.1 Approach by Error Minimization

The technique is based on an extended estimation approach that we have previously applied to estimate the optical flow locally. The estimated optical flow is given as the solution to the following minimization problem [4]:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') (\nabla g^T \mathbf{f} + g_t)^2 d\mathbf{x}' dt' \rightarrow \min \quad (\text{A.1})$$

with a weighting function $w(\mathbf{x})$ selecting the size of the spatiotemporal neighborhood in which the optical flow should be estimated.

Equation (A.1) assumes all gray value changes to be caused by movement of an object alone. This is however exactly what happens when the object undergoes any dynamical process. Thus the optical flow is no longer conserved and additional terms have to be considered. With respect to the applications in the research unit, the following processes are of interest:

Source terms. Source terms cause first-order temporal changes in the image sequence proportional to the source strength q . Source terms occur e. g., in infrared images if an object is heated or cooled.

Relaxation processes. A relaxation process also causes a first-order temporal change. This time the change is proportional to the relaxation constant λ and the gray value g . Examples for relaxation processes include first-order chemical reactions (projects C and E) and decay processes of fluorescence intensity changes.

Diffusion processes. If a transport process is captured by image sequences, chemical species are not only advected but also undergo diffusion. According to Fick's second law, this is a second-order process (projects B, C, D and E). The diffusion coefficient D describes the tendency of an object to spread out by this process.

If we take all these processes together, we end up with a more complex optimization problem given by

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') (\nabla g^T \mathbf{f} + g_t + q - \lambda g + D\Delta g)^2 d\mathbf{x}' dt' \rightarrow \min . \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Now not only the optical flow vector \mathbf{f} but also the source term q , the relaxation constant λ , and the diffusion coefficient D are estimated and varied to obtain a solution to (A.2) in a least squares sense. Thus the number of unknowns has increased from two in (A.1) to five.

It is also easy to incorporate first-order temporal or spatial changes of the optical flow \mathbf{f} into this approach. Again, this is significant for the research unit, since first-order changes of the optical flow field give other significant parameters of dynamic processes. A first-order temporal change is equal to an acceleration and can be used to estimate forces acting upon an object, provided its mass is known. Likewise the spatial divergence means the relative change in size and can thus directly be used to determine growth rates in project D.

In the first order case, an affine spatiotemporal flow field is assumed

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{t} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{a}t \quad (\text{A.3})$$

adding six more unknowns to the optimization problem:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') (\nabla g^T (\mathbf{t} + \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}' + \mathbf{a}t') + g_t + q + \lambda g - D\Delta g)^2 d\mathbf{x}' dt' \rightarrow \min . \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Obviously not all eleven unknowns are estimated for a given problem. The approach is flexible enough. Only the required parameters are used. For a growth study with isotropic growth, for example, just a single additional parameter, the scalar growth rate a , is required:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') (\nabla g^T (\mathbf{t} + \mathbf{a}\mathbf{x}'))^2 d\mathbf{x}' dt' \rightarrow \min . \quad (\text{A.5})$$

2.2 Total Least Squares Solution

Since all unknown parameters in the optimization integrals are linear, the solution of (A.2)–(A.4) is not more complex than the simple optical flow problem (A.1). Formally, the extensions can be understood in a very elegant mathematical way by Li group transformations [2, 3, 4]. To arrive at a solution, however, it is sufficient to rewrite the terms in (A.2)–(A.4) as the scalar product of an unknown parameter vector \mathbf{p} and a data vector \mathbf{d} with estimates that can be obtained directly from the image sequence. For (A.2) these vectors are given by:

$$\mathbf{p} = [f_1, f_2, 1, q, \lambda, D]^T \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{d} = \left[\frac{\partial g}{\partial x}, \frac{\partial g}{\partial y}, \frac{\partial g}{\partial t}, 1, g, -\frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} - \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial y^2} \right]^T . \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Using these two vectors (A.2) reduces to

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') \left(\mathbf{d}^T \mathbf{p} \right)^2 d\mathbf{x}' dt' \rightarrow \min , \quad (\text{A.7})$$

It has the same form as the simple optical flow problem. Then an *extended structure tensor* \mathbf{J} with the components

$$\mathbf{J}_{pq} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') d_p d_q d\mathbf{x}' dt' \quad (\text{A.8})$$

can be constructed using the data vector \mathbf{d} and (A.7) reduces to

$$\mathbf{p}^T \mathbf{J} \mathbf{p} \rightarrow \min . \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Thus the optimal parameter vector \mathbf{p} is given as the *eigenvector* to the minimal *eigenvalue* of the extended structure tensor \mathbf{J} . This solution to the minimization problem is also known as a *total least squares solution*. In contrast to a standard least-squares solution it has the advantage that not only the temporal derivatives but also the spatial derivatives and all other parameters estimated from the data in the image sequence are regarded as quantities with errors.

2.3 Examples and Results

Examples of the application of this extended structure tensor method for modeling the motion and dynamic processes can be found in the reports to all other projects of the research unit. It has been used and will be used even more (see proposals) to estimate various parameters of growth, exchange, and transport processes including direct estimation of second-order terms:

- Source terms (TP B, C and E)
- Relaxation processes(TP B, C and E)
- Diffusion processes (TP B, C, D and E)
- Growth rate (TP D)
- Divergence and convergence of flow (TP B and D)
- Vorticity of flow (TP B)
- Volumetric flow (TP F)

Therefore here only two example are given in order to illustrate that motion fields can be determined with the extended technique under circumstances where it was not possible before. The first example uses computer generated image sequences of a blob that translates and possibly decays or diffuses [3]. Each of the three models (no diffusion and decay, decay, diffusion) is applied to each case. Figure A.1 shows that the optical flow is only estimated correctly when the correct model is used.

The second example shows a decaying heated spot at the water surface (Fig. A.2, [1, 3]). Again it is obvious that the motion field is only computed adequately if the decay of the spot is taken into account. However, there are still a couple of problems that cannot be solved. These open problems include the direct estimation of

- motion superimposition and
- dispersion (non-Fourier motion).

These two problems will not further be studied in the research unit but pursued in a new spin-off project since they are only relevant for the study of wind waves in project B. However, without the work in the research unit, it would not have been possible at all to tackle these problems now.

Dynamic model used for motion and brightness change estimation			
	constant	exponential	diffusion
constant			
	$E_f = (6.5 \pm 7.9) \cdot 10^{-4}$ no BC parameter	$E_f = (1.4 \pm 1.7) \cdot 10^{-2}$ $E_k = (6.7 \pm 8.2) \cdot 10^{-4}$	$E_f = (1.1 \pm 1.1) \cdot 10^{-3}$ $E_D = (4.8 \pm 5.9) \cdot 10^{-3}$
exponential			
	$E_f = (4.7 \pm 2.6) \cdot 10^1$ no BC parameter	$E_f = (3.7 \pm 3.3) \cdot 10^{-2}$ $E_k = (2.1 \pm 1.1) \cdot 10^{-1}$	$E_f = (1.9 \pm 1.0) \cdot 10^1$ $E_D = (5.3 \pm 0.9) \cdot 10^4$
diffusion			
	$E_f = (0.5 \pm 1.2) \cdot 10^3$ no BC parameter	$E_f = (5.8 \pm 1.5) \cdot 10^2$ $E_k = (1.0 \pm 0.0) \cdot 10^2$	$E_f = (1.2 \pm 0.5) \cdot 10^{-1}$ $E_D = (6.7 \pm 3.5) \cdot 10^{-2}$

Figure A.1: Results of different parameterized brightness constraint models (columns) used to estimate motion and brightness change parameters of artificial test sequences (rows) with constant brightness, exponentially decay, and diffusion, respectively. Every test sequence is evaluated with all three models. Errors are given for the estimated optical flow (E_f), the exponential decay constant (E_k), and diffusion coefficient (E_D). All errors are given as relative errors in percent (from [3]).

2.4 Relevance for Computer Vision

Our general approach yields significant progress for low-level motion analysis. It has been known for a long time that the brightness constraint equation is not valid in most real-world cases. However, most approaches to motion estimation still used the simple brightness constraint equation underlying (A.1).

The generalized structure tensor method includes a model with a first-order brightness change model and thus delivers robust motion estimates even when the classical brightness constraint equation is severely violated. Haußecker and Fleet [2] applied models with first-order and second-order brightness changes to real-world scenes and demonstrated that it is possible to estimate unbiased optical flow in cases with illumination changes, where no reliable estimation of the optical flow was possible with a constant brightness model (Fig. A.2).

3 Analytical Studies on the Performance Characteristics of Image Sequence Algorithms

With increasing mathematical foundation of computer vision, an exact study of the performance characteristics of computer vision algorithms receives more and more attention. This topic is of special interest

Figure A.2: Exponentially decaying heat spot at a water surface. **a** first and **b** last image of the sequence; **c** optical flow estimated with constant brightness; **d** optical flow estimated with an exponential decay model. The decay rate κ is averaged over the area thresholded by the confidence measure (from [3], see also [1]).

for scientific applications and thus for the research unit since it is important to know to which extent the application of a certain algorithm introduces systematical or statistical errors into the results.

We started the investigation of this subject long before the foundation of the research unit [5]. Within the research unit, the techniques could be further generalized and also applied to 3-D spatiotemporal images. Additionally they have been verified by experiments with computer generated and with real world image sequences.

The basic requirement for an analytical study of low-level motion estimation is a unified approach that formulates the motion estimators as nonlinear differential operators in continuous spatiotemporal images. It has been shown that all known differential methods contain terms of the form [5]:

$$J_{pq}(\mathbf{x}) = \int w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') \partial_p g(\mathbf{x}', t') \partial_q g(\mathbf{x}', t') d^2 x' dt' . \quad (\text{A.10})$$

This operation can be performed as a cascade of a linear convolution and a nonlinear point operation:

$$\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{D}_p \cdot \mathcal{D}_q), \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where \mathcal{B} and \mathcal{D}_p are a smoothing filter and a derivative filter into direction p .

With this continuous formulation two significant advantages are gained over previous approaches. First, it is not required to make any specific assumptions about the types of gray value structures. Second, it is possible to distinguish principal flaws in an approach from errors in the implementation due to an inadequate discretization method.

Most of the analytical studies have already been performed in phase I of the research unit (see the extensive report of the phase I, section A2). In phase II, we completed these studies and extended them to more complex cases. We were invited to report our results at the Dagstuhl workshop on “Performance Characterization in Computer Vision” [6].

We also initiated a first study of error propagation for tensor-based, i.e. total least squares, estimation of optical flow. The first results are encouraging [2]. Thus we have established the theoretical basis that the many routine measurements to be performed in the third phase of the research unit can adequately be analyzed.

Figure A.3: Absolute value of the angular error in degrees for direction of maximum error (22.5° against x) **a** standard central derivative, **b** Sobel, **c** optimized Sobel operator of (A.12) and **d** optimized 5×5 -operator. Please note different scaling of axes!

4 Optimization of Filters for Low-Level Image Sequence Processing

Most algorithms used in the Research Unit, e.g. the structure tensor method and its extensions (see Section 2) are based on linear shift-invariant filters. In order to get minimal computational errors, optimal filters are needed. Therefore a universal filter optimization tool has been developed with the following features (see [9])

- freely choosable ansatz and reference functions, usually transfer functions of filters with fixed support and ideal filters,
- simultaneous optimization of filter sets,
- flexible consideration of additional constraints,
- weighted error norms (L_2 and L_∞) with user defined weighting functions,
- nonlinear optimization strategies for floating point and rational coefficients, the latter are used for SIMD instruction sets such as MMX or VIS [7].

In addition a theoretical framework for quality measurement of n -th order, m -dimensional derivative filters has been developed (see [9], chap. 3).

4.1 Examples

As filters can be optimized with many different settings (size of support, reference function, error norm and weighting function, type of coefficients) only some results can be presented here.

4.1.1 Derivative Filters for Gradient Direction

The most important result for the research unit is the development of small and highly accurate derivative filters for the computation of the gradient direction. When using these filters the accuracy of motion estimation with the structure tensor improved about two orders of magnitude. Stability with respect to noise improved over one order of magnitude (compare [9], chap. 8).

The key idea for the optimization of these filters is to introduce a smoothing of the filters in cross direction. Recall that the transfer function of an ideal first-order 1D derivative is given by $i\pi\tilde{k}$, where \tilde{k} denotes normalized wave numbers. The transfer function (denoted by a $\hat{\cdot}$) of the commonly used central derivative operator $D_x = [\frac{1}{2}, 0, -\frac{1}{2}]$, however, is $\hat{D}_x = i\pi\tilde{k} \text{sinc}(\pi\tilde{k})$.

In order to maintain rotation invariance, one should apply a similar smoothing operator $S(a) = [a, 1 - 2a, a]$ perpendicular to the direction of the derivative. We then obtain a derivative filter with a transfer function of the form

$$\hat{D}_x = i\pi\tilde{k}\hat{B}(\tilde{k}),$$

where B is an approximation of an isotropic smoothing filter. The well known "Derivative of Gaussian" filter is of this form. To get the best smoothing filter, we may optimize for precise computation of the gradient direction, which is the most common feature of interest in the research unit. This results in the following minimization [9]:

$$E(a) = \left[\int w(\tilde{k}) \arctan\left(\frac{\tilde{k}_y}{\tilde{k}_x}\right) - w(\tilde{k}) \arctan\left(\frac{\hat{D}_y \hat{S}_x(a)}{\hat{D}_x \hat{S}_y(a)}\right) \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \rightarrow \min,$$

Figure A.4: Optimized steerable filters for anisotropic smoothing: **a**, **b** and **c** show transfer functions of F_1 , F_2 and F_3 (eq. 4.1.2) for 5×5 discretizations optimized for rotation invariance. **d**, **e** and **f** show contour plots of transfer functions of resulting filters for $\lambda_1 = 1$, $\lambda_2 = 0$ and three angles α 0° , 22.5° and 45° .

where the integration area is the whole Fourier domain. Using a rational coefficient a and a weighting function $w(\tilde{k}) = \cos^4(\pi\tilde{k}_x/2) \cos^4(\pi\tilde{k}_y/2)$ (i.e. a 5×5 Gaussian) we get $a = 3/16$ or $S(3/16) = [3, 10, 3]/16$. Thus we obtain a convolution kernel with the filter notation:

$$\partial_x \doteq \frac{1}{32} \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 0 & -3 \\ 10 & 0 & -10 \\ 3 & 0 & -3 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \partial_y \doteq \frac{1}{32} \begin{bmatrix} -3 & -10 & -3 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 3 & 10 & 3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

This optimized Sobel operator has significantly decreased angular errors in gradient computation with respect to other popular 3-tab kernels such as Sobel or central differences. If we increase the support of the kernels to 5×5 angular error decreases over 3 orders of magnitude (Fig. A.3). For more details see [9].

4.1.2 Steerable smoothing filters

In Fig. A.4 transfer functions of steerable 2 dimensional smoothing filters F optimized for best directional behaviour are shown. In polar coordinates r and ϕ they approximate the filter

$$\begin{aligned} F(r, \phi, \alpha) &= F_r(r) (\lambda_1 \cos^2(\phi - \alpha) + \lambda_2 \sin^2(\phi - \alpha)) \\ &= F_r(r) \left(\frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{2} (\cos 2\phi \cos 2\alpha + \sin 2\phi \sin 2\alpha) + \frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}{2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where α is the parameter to steer. The positive constants λ_1 and λ_2 are usually $\in [0, 1]$. They correspond closely to diffusivities in tensor valued anisotropic diffusion (compare Scharr and Weickert [11]). As filter set and interpolations we use:

Filter	Interpolation
$F_1(r, \phi) = F_r(r)$	$k_1(\alpha) = \frac{\lambda_1 + \lambda_2}{2}$
$F_2(r, \phi) = F_r(r) \cos(2\phi)$	$k_2(\alpha) = \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{2} \cos(2\alpha)$
$F_3(r, \phi) = F_r(r) \sin(2\phi)$	$k_3(\alpha) = \frac{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2}{2} \sin(2\alpha)$

For these filters nonnegativity of the coefficients of the resulting filter can be guaranteed, which is an important feature for algorithms like normalized convolution. For related filters such as finite difference discretizations of anisotropic diffusion (see Section 5) it has been shown, that no consistent stencil with this property can be designed for arbitrary diffusivities, if stencil size is less or equal 5×5 [11]. How these filters can be used for effective scale space analysis by anisotropic diffusion is shown in Section 5.

4.1.3 Other filters

Further optimizations have been done, e. g. for

- 1 dimensional Hilbert filters (reference function: ideal transfer function),
- 1 dimensional interpolation filters (reference function: zero padding interpolation) for arbitrary positions,
- 1 dimensional first order derivative filters (reference function: ideal transfer function),
- 2 and 3 dimensional Laplacian filter (reference function: isotropy),
- steerable 2 dimensional second order directional derivative filters (reference function: direction),
- 3×3 filter discretizations of anisotropic diffusion (reference function: ideal transfer function for arbitrary but fixed direction).

For the latter optimization the well known nonnegativity discretization (see [15]) turned out to be optimal. Therefore the novel filter discretization of anisotropic diffusion (Section 5) is compared to this stencil.

5 Scale-Space Analysis for Image Sequences

In many applications of the research unit technical requirements strongly limit the possibilities of data acquisition. Therefore imaging techniques such as thermography by an infrared camera (project B and D) and fluorescence microscopy ("*in vitro* motility assay" of project E, GFP methods of project F suffer from low signal to noise ratios. Consequently one of the key methods of project F is a noise reducing technique (Section 8.1). This is a well known scale space technique which uses nonlinear diffusion with a scalar valued diffusivity applied to each image of a sequence separately. In the literature this method is called "anisotropic" diffusion which is misleading as real anisotropic diffusion (as it will be used next) is driven by a tensor valued diffusivity (compare e.g. [15]).

For image sequences fulfilling the Nyquist theorem spatio-temporal information is available. Moving objects can be described by trajectories in space-time, i.e. line-like structures in image sequences with orientations according to the velocity of the objects. An essentially one dimensional smoothing of an image sequence along these trajectories is thus expected to have excellent denoising properties.

Coherence-enhancing anisotropic diffusion filtering is a scale-space and image restoration technique that has been introduced for the enhancement of line-like structures [16]. Because the direction of trajectories is the feature of interest in image sequences it is crucial to use numerical schemes with highly accurate directional behaviour. To this end, we introduced a novel algorithm for coherence-enhancing anisotropic diffusion (see [9, 11]). This method applies differentiation filters with optimal rotation invariance (see [10] and Section 4), and boils down to a steerable explicit scheme on a 5×5 stencil. By comparing it with several common algorithms we demonstrated its superior behaviour regarding rotation invariance, avoidance of blurring artifacts (dissipativity) and accuracy. The latter one is compared to an analytical solution for coherence-enhancing diffusion filtering of images with circular symmetry that we were able to derive. We also showed that the new scheme is more than three times more efficient than common explicit schemes on

Figure A.5: Dissipativity illustrated by means of a 206×160 image of a peacock. The filter parameters are $c_1 = 0.001$, $c_2 = 1$, $\sigma = 0.6$, $\rho = 2$, $\tau = 0.2$, and 100 iterations.

3×3 stencils. It does not require to solve linear systems of equations, and it can be easily implemented in any dimension.

With this new method we developed a structure preserving denoising algorithm using spatio-temporal, real anisotropic diffusion. The application to image sequences of the motility assay (see figure E.9) in a preliminary study showed that this new development leads to a so far not achievable improvement on the signal to noise ratio. Additionally an optical flow based displacement estimation with the structure tensor showed to improve clearly by coupling it to this denoising strategy [14]. The accuracy of results and the big variety of possible applications is encouraging. Still one problem has to be solved to make this algorithm usable for non-experts. The choice of parameters at the moment is strongly data dependent and needs expert knowledge. Investigations on automatic parameter choice as well as slightly modified underlying differential equations are therefore of major interest.

In the following sections, we briefly describe the new algorithm in two dimensions and present some results.

5.1 General filter structure

Anisotropic diffusion filtering with a diffusion tensor evolves the initial image under an evolution equation of type

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = \nabla \cdot (D \nabla u), \quad D = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ b & c \end{pmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where $u(x, t)$ is the evolving image, t denotes the diffusion time. D is the diffusion tensor, a positive definite symmetric matrix that is adapted to the local image structure. The choice of D and details on coherence-enhancing anisotropic diffusion can be found in Weickert [16].

Equation (A.13) can be solved numerically using finite differences. Spatial derivatives are usually replaced by central differences, while the easiest way to discretize $\frac{\partial u}{\partial t}$ consists in using a forward difference approximation. The resulting so-called explicit scheme has the basic structure

$$\frac{u_{i,j}^{k+1} - u_{i,j}^k}{\tau} = A_{i,j}^k * u_{i,j}^k \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad u_{i,j}^{k+1} = (I + \tau A_{i,j}^k) * u_{i,j}^k \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where τ is the time step size and $u_{i,j}^k$ denotes the approximation of $u(x, t)$ in the pixel (i, j) at time $k\tau$. The expression $A_{i,j}^k * u_{i,j}^k$ is a discretization of $\nabla \cdot (D \nabla u)$. It comes down to the convolution of the image with a spatially and temporally varying mask $A_{i,j}^k$. See [15, 17] for common choices of A .

For our approach we need to rewrite the differential operator in (A.13) as

$$\nabla \cdot (D \nabla u) = \partial_x (a \partial_x u + b \partial_y u) + \partial_y (b \partial_x u + c \partial_y u). \quad (\text{A.15})$$

The key point in our new discretization is to compute $\nabla \cdot (D \nabla u)$ as given in (A.15) by the usage of first order derivative operators as given in (A.12). These filters have optimal behaviour with respect to rotation invariance (Section 4.1.1).

As a demonstration of the superior behaviour of our new scheme, a picture of a peacock (Fig. A.5) has been diffused by our method and two common schemes. Goal of this kind of diffusion is to enhance line-like

Figure A.6: *Experimental set-up: The camera (1) is attached to a rotating arm (2) and moves in a circular path above the observed plant (3). At the other end of the arm a counter weight (4) balances the camera. At the axis of rotation (5) the inclination angle is automatically measured for each image frame. As the radius of rotation is known this enables us to calculate the camera's position.*

structures without blurring them. Our scheme shows least blurring artifacts and most isotropic behaviour. Please note that the nonnegativity scheme is the optimal scheme concerning accuracy and isotropy if we restrict A to a 3×3 support (see [9], chap. 7).

6 3-D Reconstruction using Moving Cameras

In the investigation of plant leaf growth (Project D) precise measurement of motion divergence (relative error $< 0.1\%$) is of outmost importance. Due to egomotion of a plant leaf during growth process and the effects, if this motion is restricted, 3-D information of the leaf surface with the same relative error is needed. To this end we investigated 3-D reconstruction using moving cameras. The main idea is that using information not only from multiple views but from a complete image sequence increases accuracy and simplifies establishment of stereo correspondences at every pixel. The last point is one of the major difficulties in stereo applications.

Instead of the classic two-camera system we employ only one camera which is continuously moved from one stereo position to the other. The correspondence problem is now solved by tracking each pixel over the acquired image sequence. In a first implementation of this idea we focus on this novel low level depth from integrated motion algorithm.

Our method starts by attempting to fit a locally constant displacement to the space-time intensity pattern in a total least squares sense (Section 2.2). From the residual of this fit we can identify problematic regions. High residual values can be either attributed to aliasing, a motion discontinuity or non-coherent motion. While we can not deal with aliasing we are able to detect the other two. In a further processing step we apply an iterative regularization scheme to obtain dense full flow in order to compute dense depth maps. Towards this end we impose a smoothly varying flow field and take the above information into account. The full flow field can be used to track certain features (here each individual pixel) over a long image sequence. Knowing the correspondence from our algorithm and camera position from a special experimental set-up (see Fig. A.6), we compute the depth at every point using standard stereo triangulation. For a more detailed description of the algorithm, especially details on the regularization see Spies et al. [13].

Figure A.7: a first image, b last image, c accumulated displacement between the two frames, d computed depth map and e texture mapped rendered structure.

Correspondence is established by simply summing up the displacements between consecutive frames employing bilinear interpolation. This means we do not need to employ any form of tracking stabilization, such as a Kalman filter [e.g. 8, 18].

As we use standard stereo triangulation and no sophisticated stabilization is applied we hereby show that the accuracy of motion estimation by the structure tensor with optimized derivative filters (compare Section 4) is sufficient for our demanding task.

Figure A.7 shows the resulting structure estimation for two real image sequences taken with our special experimental set-up.

7 Multichannel Image Sequence Processing

The combination of different data channels into a combined estimation framework is of major interest to various applications throughout the research unit. Up to now we investigated one special case in detail, namely the combined use of intensity and depth data for the analysis of the motion of deformable surfaces (range flow). This method is used in subproject D to study the 3D movement of growing leaves. Here we could show that a combination of these independent data sources provides for more accurate estimations [12]. Additionally it is sometimes possible to overcome the aperture problems that are encountered in the separate channels alone. It is our goal to generalize this approach in such a way that it can be used for arbitrary numbers and types of data channels in the final phase of the research unit, see the proposal for details.

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B Wind Waves, Turbulence, and Exchange Processes at the Ocean Surface

1 Introduction and Summary

Despite intensive research in recent years, knowledge about small-scale air-sea interaction processes such as the mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer and the dynamics of short wind waves and their influence on the exchange processes is still poor and many basic questions are open [15, 17]. On the one hand, the poor knowledge can be attributed to the complex turbulent processes at a free surface undulated by waves that are also influenced by the physicochemical properties of the surface layer. On the other hand, inadequate experimental techniques are a major obstacle for further progress. Conventional techniques proved to be inadequate and it is only for the advent of sophisticated imaging techniques that gradually an experimental insight into these processes is gained, which will certainly also spur further theoretical progress. This is why small-scale interaction processes have become one of the subjects in this research unit.

In phase II of the research unit, we could make significant progress especially with the development of experimental techniques and the analysis of image sequence data gained by these techniques. This includes

Short wind waves: First measurements of wave-number resolved wave slope amplitude distributions (Section 2)

New facility, the Aeolotron: This facility was designed and constructed during phase II and is now ready for measurements. It is by far the most advanced facility for using imaging techniques for small-scale air-sea interaction studies (Section 4).

Thermography: The most significant progress was obtained with passive thermographic techniques in conjunction with the techniques to estimate motion and parameters of dynamic processes in a single step from image sequences (Section 2 in part A). It is now possible to measure the net heat flux across the water surface. Thus transfer measurements by passive thermography do not require micrometeorological total heat flux measurements (Section 7).

Optical Techniques for Gas Transfer Measurements: Using the differential optical absorption spectroscopy from project C, an imaging IR spectrometer has been constructed to be used in the Aeolotron for fast measurements of profiles of several gases in the air space (Section 6).

LIF Mass boundary layer imaging: It could be demonstrated that a depth-resolving LIF imaging of the aqueous mass boundary layer is feasible (Section 8).

Further analysis of field data from Coastal Ocean Process (CoOP) experiments shows that the controlled flux technique using heat as a proxy tracer for gas exchange measurements give not only reliable results but also direct insight into the mechanisms (Section 3). Using the new technique to measure directly heat fluxes across the interface, the technique even becomes independent of micrometeorological net heat flux measurements that did not provide enough accuracy and time resolution.

Finally, we could also gain progress in modeling air/sea gas transfer across the ocean surface. All current models establish just an empiric or semi-empiric correlation between wind speed and gas exchange rate. For the first time, a detailed model could be developed that includes the influence of wind waves on the transfer process and correctly explains the change in the Schmidt number exponent and the absolute transfer rates (Section 5).

2 Short Wind Waves

During phase II of the research unit no new wave measurements were taken because the old annular facility was torn down late in 1998 and the new facility in the new building of the Institut für Umweltphysik was

Figure B.1: Slope amplitude distribution as a function of the wave number from along-wind traveling wind waves measured in the old Heidelberg annular wind/wave facility at conditions as indicated (from [3]).

under construction ready for measurements in Summer 2000. Thus we worked, as outlined in the proposal for phase II, mainly on new methods to analyze wind/wave image sequences that overcome the limits of standard Fourier transform techniques.

A new technique for the determination of local wave numbers and the direction of the waves from wave slope images was developed. It is based on a scale space decomposition of the wave images, including a decomposition into six directional components using steerable filters that have been developed in the core project A (Section 4). With a nonlinear regression technique, up to three superimposed wave components can be detected simultaneously. Thus the local amplitude, wave number and direction of these individual components can be determined in each point of the image. From this data various statistical distributions can be computed, for instance the slope amplitude distribution for each wave number while the Fourier transform yields only a mean value.

Fig. B.1 shows such distributions for along-wind traveling waves as measured in the old Heidelberg annular wind/wave facility. Surprisingly, also at low wind speeds the slope of the capillary waves is steep, even somewhat higher than for short gravity waves. The capillary waves only occur less frequently than the short gravity waves. With a Fourier spectrum it cannot be distinguished from the mean slope amplitude whether there are infrequent steep waves or frequent waves with only a low steepness.

Figure B.2: Measured gas transfer velocity from the passive flux technique, as a function of time for a period with variable rain. Individual points are infrared estimates of gas transfer velocity (normalized to Schmidt number 600). In the period of time after UTC 11:20 (Year Day 192 of Year 1997), the intensity of rain increased, along with a corresponding increase of gas transfer rate.

3 Field Measurements of Air-Water Gas Transfer

As was demonstrated in the first Coastal Ocean Process (CoOP) field experiment in 1995, the active controlled flux technique suffered from the inability to track a laser-heated ocean-surface spot for a long enough period of time so as to compute its rate of heat decay in an unambiguous manner. This experiment took place in the Pacific Ocean between the Channel Islands near Santa Catalina and Monterey Bay. In this region the predominant long wave swell has a mean period of approximately 20 seconds. This gives rise to very high orbital wave velocities that advect the laser-heated surface-spot very quickly out of the field of view of the infrared camera used to image the spot's temperature decay. The resulting image sequences only track the spot's temperature during a brief period of an exponential decay of temperature in time. Fitting this decay to estimate the rate of heat transfer across the air-sea interface yielded poor results. While the technique of active transfer is still useful in situations where the gross motion of the surface under study is slow enough to record sustained image sequences, we began the development of the passive controlled flux technique.

In this technique the spatial distribution of temperature obtained from the ocean surface can be used to model the surface renewal occurring at the air-water interface. A successful model was constructed ([11];[9]) that used a model of surface renewal to explain the heat transfer across the interface. After investigating a number of different temporal renewal schemes, including periodic renewal, uniformly random time period renewal, and log-normal time period renewal; the log-normal statistical surface renewal was found to provide an excellent correlation with observed heat transfer rates. By using Schmidt/Prandtl number scaling arguments, the use of this technique for scaling heat flux measurements to mass flux measurements was used in the second CoOP field experiment in 1997. By this technique it was possible to obtain very short time estimates of heat flux (order 10 seconds) so as to correlate heat flux (and scaled mass flux) to other observable phenomena obtained during the 1997 experiment, including the frequency-wavenumber spectra of short capillary and capillary-gravity waves [1] and the enhanced surface concentration of organic matter [7].

Figure B.2 shows a short time series obtained during one day during the 1997 field experiment. At the period of time between 11:20 and 11:30 (Universal Time) a rain shower began. The short time estimates of gas transfer (normalized to a Schmidt number of 600 relevant to CO₂) demonstrate the rapid response of the Passive Flux Technique in responding to what is interpreted as an enhanced surface renewal resulting from rain droplets increasing the near surface turbulence as reported in the literature (e.g. [12]).

A major drawback of this technique lay in its need for an independent measurement of heat transfer. This drawback resulted from the fact that the model of surface renewal was underconstrained with the use of spatial statistics alone. The model required the use of a long time average of estimates obtained from the Passive Flux Technique to be fixed against another estimate of heat flux. In the case of the 1997 experiment, we had access to an independent measure of heat flux, and could choose to use either traditional meteorological measurements of bulk aerodynamic properties [6], estimates achieved from inertial-dissipation methods [4], or the current state-of-the-science measurements making use of the direct covariance technique

Figure B.3: Transfer velocity normalized for Schmidt number 600 (CO_2) as a function of the wavenumber-binned mean square slope: \diamond - 4 m wind-wave canal without surfactant, \circ with surfactant, \square - CoOP field data from 1997 analyzed with inertial dissipation heat transfer estimates of heat flux, $+$ CoOP field data analyzed with direct covariance estimates of heat flux. Solid line represents best linear fit through all data points.

[5]. Using the best estimates from each of these atmospheric techniques for long term heat flux measurement, we were only able to estimate mass transfer using the Passive Flux Technique to an accuracy of $\pm 30\%$.

In Fig. B.3 a compiled set of data obtained from various work performed under laboratory and field conditions is plotted. The gas transfer rate (again Schmidt number normalized for CO_2) is plotted against the wavenumber-binned mean square slope (the integrated means square slope for all waves with wavenumber greater than 200 rad/m). Here both laboratory work and field data are presented. The $+$ symbol outlying the general cluster of data represents the rainy period at the end of the time series in the previous figure. Although the direct covariance technique estimates a large enhancement in the heat transfer (obtained from the independent meteorological measurements), it is not possible to explain such a large enhancement of heat transfer by direct cold rain effects. At present we can not say if this is a real turbulence-induced effect or an uncertainty in the bulk heat flux estimate.

After the 1997 field experiment we began work on an improved model described below in Section 7.2 that made use of a combination of spatial and temporal image sequences to include an additional constraint and obviate the need for an independent measure of long time heat flux. Experiments carried out in the Heidelberg Aeolotron using this improved image acquisition and analysis have resulted in a significantly improved methodology for estimating heat flux across the air-water interface [8] and are currently the topic of many of the proposed research goals explained below.

4 The Heidelberg Aeolotron

The study of small-scale air sea interaction still lacks suitable facilities. This is less a question of the size of the facility but more a question of what kind of measurements are feasible. The trouble is that most existing facilities (for a list see Table B.1) are not suitable for modern imaging techniques as they have been developed by the research group in Heidelberg in the recent years.

Moreover, annular facilities are much more suitable for small-scale air-sea interaction studies. This is especially true for gas exchange measurements. In linear facilities only rather short wind waves can be generated. Moreover, the wind wave field is inhomogeneous. It starts with small ripples at the entrance of the facility and the wavelength is gradually increasing along the facility towards the beach at the end.

In contrast an annular channel has no beginning and no end. The wind amplifies the waves until they reach an equilibrium. Much larger wind waves can be generated than in a linear facility of the same size and the waves are the same everywhere in the facility so that experiments are much easier. The first annular air-sea interaction facility was built in 1950 in the Soviet Union by Vasilii Shuleykin. The huge 40 m diameter facility is located in Katsively on the Crimea at the Marine Hydrophysical Institute. It was used to study the evolution of waves by wind until 1974.

Without knowing the earlier Russian work — the founding director of the Institut für Umwelphysik at the University of Heidelberg, Prof. Karl Otto Münnich, — constructed about 25 year ago a small circular facility. Various small circular facilities for air-sea gas exchange studies have been used since the late seventies

Figure B.4: Snapshots from the construction and operation of the new Heidelberg air-sea interaction facility, the Aeolotron.

at Heidelberg University and later at Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution for air-sea gas exchange studies (Table B.1).

In 1999 the Institut für Umwelphysik at the University of Heidelberg moved into a new building. This building gave the opportunity to build a new air-sea interaction facility with unique experimental possibilities. An annular wind/wave facility with 10 m in diameter was built that was specifically designed for the usage of imaging techniques. The facility was named “Aeolotron” after the Greek god of the winds — Aeolus. The Aeolotron is a unique facility in many respects. It is a large facility, yet very versatile in its usage and the wide range of experiments that can be performed. The main features of the Aeolotron include:

Geometry: Annular channel; 0.63 m wide; 2.41 m high; mean circumference 29.2 m; maximum water depth 1.20 m

Water storage: Separate 28 m³ storage tanks for sea water and deionized water

Table B.1: Comparison of the geometry of some major facilities for small-scale air-sea interaction studies (operational facilities are typeset in boldface):

KA: Institute for Hydrology, University of Karlsruhe, HH: Bundesanstalt für Wasserbau, Hamburg, M: IMST, Univ. Marseille, France, D: Delft Hydraulics, Delft, The Netherlands (no longer operational), SIO: Hydraulic Facility, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, La Jolla, USA, UF: University of Florida, Miami, SU: Storm basin, Marine Hydrophysical Institute, Sevastopol, Ukraine (no longer operational), HD1: Small annular wind/wave flume, Univ. Heidelberg (no longer operational), HD2: Large annular wind/wave flume, Univ. Heidelberg (dismantled), WH: Small annular wind/wave flume Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution (now in Heidelberg), HD3: Aeolotron, Univ. Heidelberg (HD3, in operation since June 2000).

	KA	HH	M	D	SIO	UF	SU	HD1	HD2	WH	HD3
Length (mean perimeter) [m]	15	24	40	100	40	?	119	1.57	11.6	?	29.2
Width of water channel [m]	1.8	1.0	2.6	8.0	2.4	?	2.0	0.10	0.20	0.3	0.63
Outer diameter [m]	-	-	-	-	-	-	40	0.60	4.0	1.0	9.93
Inner diameter [m]	-	-	-	-	-	-	36	0.40	3.4	0.6	8.67
Max. water depth [m]	0.3	0.5	0.8	0.8	1.5	?	3.0	0.08	0.25	0.20	1.20
Water surface area [m ²]	27	24	104	800	96	?	239	0.16	3.5	?	18.4
Water volume [m ³]	8	12	83	768	144	?	716	0.01	0.87	?	22.1

Water quality: Chemically clean environment; circulation system with filters and UV oxidation system for continuous cleaning of water; suitable for both deionized water and sea water

Water temperature: Temperature ranges between 5 and 35 C (maximum heat flux in/out the facility of about 100 W/K because of the well insulated air- and water space)

Air flow: Paddle wheel driven by 64 100 W DC motors to generate wind speeds up to 15 m/s; time constant about 2 s

Waves: Homogeneous wave pattern and the largest possible fetch through its annular shape, deep enough to get high wave ages at low and medium wind speeds; the maximum phase speed of waves is 3.45 m/s; the maximum wavelength for a deep water wave is 3 m

Water flow: Separate water flow system with speeds up to 0.7 m/s against the wind direction

Control of air temperature and humidity: Air conditioning system with independent control of humidity and air temperature; 64 kW cooling; 15 kW heating power; high positive and negative heat fluxes at the water interface of more than 1 kW/m²

Gastight air space: Closed air space with controllable flush rate up to 1000 m³/h. Fast gas exchange measurements are possible by measuring the rate of concentration increase in the gastight air space:

$$\frac{\Delta c_a}{c_w} = \frac{V_w}{V_a} \frac{\Delta t}{\tau}$$

Because the volumes of the air and water space, V_w and V_a are approximately equal, and concentration changes of trace gases in the air, c_a of about 2% of the concentration in the water, c_w , can be measured, a measurement takes only about 1/50 of τ , e. g., 2–60 min. (τ ranges from about 2 hours at 15 m/s to 60 hours at 2.5 m/s wind speed.)

IR imaging: Especially designed for IR imaging of the water surface with walls reflecting IR radiation and with low thermal mass

The standard instrumentation of the Aeolotron includes sensors to measure air and water flow (propeller anemometers) air and water temperature measurements (high precision Pt100 sensors); humidity, wave height, and gas concentrations in (CO₂, N₂O, CH₄, R12 using an infrared gas analyzer). The most important experimental capabilities of the Aeolotron, however, are imaging techniques since they give a direct insight into the processes. A central optical experimental stand was constructed so that at the same footprint at the water surface multiple parameters can be made visible simultaneously. The slope of the waves can be coded in color by a color-graduated light source through the large optical window at the bottom of the facility. A camera mounted above the facility takes image sequences that show all waves from tiny capillary waves to large gravity waves.

Figure B.5: Schmidt number exponent n as a function of the total mean square slope: **a** data from Huber [13] and Börsinger [2] **b** composite model for a Schmidt number of 600, $\beta_s = 12.2$, $\beta_w = 6$, $\delta = 0.04$, and $\gamma = 1, 2, 3$;

Thermal images are taken through an oblique window from the side of the facility. These image sequences show the fine-scale temperature fluctuations at the water surface that reveal the structure of the turbulence at the water surface and how it is influenced by waves. The patterns are completely different at low wind speeds without waves and at high wind speeds with waves.

5 Modeling of Air-Water Gas Transfer

Standard empirical models relate the transfer velocity k just to the wind speed. Although the experimental data suggest an excellent correlation between k and the mean square slope of waves, k cannot simply be expressed as a function of this parameter. Then the transfer velocity would be zero if no waves are present and relating a quantity with the dimension of a velocity to the dimensionless quantity wave slope is theoretically inadequate.

As a consequence of the intermittent nature of the transfer process, we rather need to sum up the total gas flux over smooth and wavy patches. Since the transfer velocity k is linearly related to the flux density j by $k = j/\Delta c$, we can simply add up the transfer velocities weighted with fractional areas:

$$\frac{k}{u_{*w}} = (1 - \alpha(\sigma_s^2)) \frac{1}{\beta_s} Sc^{-2/3} + \alpha(\sigma_s^2) \frac{1}{\beta_w} Sc^{-1/2}. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

The fractional area α gives the relative area where wave-induced surface renewal occurs. It is set to be a function of the mean square slope of the waves. Again, the simplest assumption is that the fractional area covered by wave-induced surface renewal is directly related to the mean square slope of the waves by a polynomial law

$$\alpha(\sigma_s^2) = \frac{\sigma_s^{2\gamma}}{\delta^\gamma + \sigma_s^{2\gamma}}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Then the resulting Schmidt number exponent can be expressed as:

$$n = \frac{\frac{2}{3}(1 - \alpha(\sigma_s^2)) \frac{1}{\beta_s} Sc^{-2/3} + \frac{1}{2} \alpha(\sigma_s^2) \frac{1}{\beta_w} Sc^{-1/2}}{(1 - \alpha(\sigma_s^2)) \frac{1}{\beta_s} Sc^{-2/3} + \alpha(\sigma_s^2) \frac{1}{\beta_w} Sc^{-1/2}} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

As (B.3) indicates, the transition from $2/3$ to $1/2$ depends slightly on the Schmidt number itself. The same is true for the enhancement of the transfer over the lower limit of the transfer given by (B.1) with $\alpha = 0$:

$$\frac{k}{k_s} = 1 + \alpha(\sigma_s^2) \left(\frac{\beta_s}{\beta_w} Sc^{1/6} - 1 \right). \quad (\text{B.4})$$

From this equation and (Fig. B.6b) also the weak influence of the Schmidt number on the point of transition can be seen. The composite model has three free parameter: β_w , δ as the threshold mean square slope, and γ , the exponent in the relation between the fractional area influenced by wave-induced surface renewal and the mean square slope of waves.

Figure B.6: **a** Transfer velocity of CO₂ as a function of the transfer velocity for water vapor. Measurements from the small circular wind/wave flume of Heidelberg University; from Jähne [14]; **b** Enhancement of the gas transfer velocity according to (B.4) as a function of the total mean square slope for Schmidt numbers of 60, 600, and 6000 with $\beta_s = 12.2$, $\beta_w = 6$, $\gamma = 2$, and $\delta = 0.04$.

The general form of the transition both of the experimental data of the enhancement (Fig. B.5) and the decrease of the Schmidt number exponent n (Fig. B.6) is in very good agreement with the model. Although the data points show considerable scatter, the transition appears to be quite steep. Therefore the exponent γ must be at least 2. For verification of the model (or any other model if the proposed model will turn out to be incorrect), new laboratory experiments are required with much more accurate measurements of the Schmidt number exponent n . Moreover, the measurements must include wave slope measurements and cover a wide range of conditions including measurements with surface films.

6 Optical Techniques for Gas Transfer Measurements

From the work in project C we learnt that differential absorption spectroscopy (DOAS) is a powerful technique to measure the concentration of several gases simultaneously. This technique has already been used in a simple imaging IR spectrometer which was set up using the Radiancel IR camera with a CaF₂ prism as a dispersive element. However, the narrow spectral range of the Radiancel camera and the bad spectral resolution limited the system considerably. It was not possible to measure water vapor using the 2.8 μm band and alkanes and alkenes (e. g., methane) at the 3.3 μm band.

In the second phase of the research unit, a new IR camera was available that was specifically optimized for spectroscopic measurements. The spectral range was extended to 1.5–5.0 μm and a rather low aperture of $f/4$ through $f/8$. This made it possible to construct the optics ourselves by using off-the-shelf optical components.

A sketch of the whole spectroscopic system, as it has been mounted at the Aeolotron for gas concentration measurements in the air space is shown in Fig. B.7b, a photograph in Fig. B.7a. As a radiation source a heated wire in a Xe-filled chamber is used at one side of the facility. At the other side of the facility, the spectrometer is placed. It consists of a CaF₂ prism as a dispersive element. An imaging lens with $f = 150$ mm of KCl has been chosen so that the whole spectrum from 2–5 μm covered 128 pixel horizontally with a spectral resolution of about 0.03 μm (Fig. B.7b). The whole optical path from the front lens of the

Figure B.7: a Imaging IR spectrometer mounted at the Aeolotron; b Sketch of the instrument; c N₂O calibration measurements.

spectrometer to the window of the focal plane array in the camera is filled with dry nitrogen in order to avoid absorption along these internal paths and thus systematic errors in the determination of gas concentrations.

The construction of the system has just been finished and we were able to make a first calibration measurement. Since the air space of the Aeolotron is gastight, we simply injected known quantities of N₂O into the air space and measured the concentration both with a Hartmann&Braun nondispersive IR absorption detector (URAS14) and our spectroscopic system. The DOAS spectra were evaluated only from a single line of the camera in order to get an idea from the noise level of the instrument. Figure B.7c shows the results. In the concentration range between 0 and 100 ppm, the standard deviation between the two measurements was only 0.4% and no deviation from a linear response could be observed.

These initial results are very encouraging. The spectroscopic IR measurements of gas concentrations will be the main instrument for gas exchange measurements in the Aeolotron. Since we can sample 400 images/sec, also the fluctuations of the concentrations may give interesting further insight into the mechanisms of air-sea gas exchange (for further discussion, see proposal).

Figure B.8: Variation of **a** the water surface temperature and **b** the variance of the water surface temperature in the course of an experiment in the old annular wind/wave flume. The ventilation of the air space has been shut off and on in order to switch between periods with no net heat transfer and negative heat transfer due to evaporation; **c** shows the ratio of the variance of the surface temperature fluctuations to the temperature difference across the aqueous heat boundary layer at conditions as indicated. Solid lines mark different theoretical models about the surface renewal process.

7 Studies of Small-scale Air-Sea Interaction using Thermography

7.1 Spatial Structure of Microturbulence

The statistical techniques for measuring gas transfer velocities using passive thermography rely on a constant ratio between the variance of measured surface temperature fluctuations, σ_T , to the temperature difference across the aqueous heat boundary layer, ΔT [19]. Surface renewal models yield values for $\sigma_T/\Delta T$ from 0.36 for periodic renewal up to 0.66 for exponential renewal. The measured temperature distributions best agree with log-normal renewal, which gives $\sigma_T/\Delta T = 0.5$. However, it has not yet been verified experimentally, whether this essential ratio is really correct.

Therefore we carried out measurements in the old annular wind/wave facility. The temperature difference across the aqueous heat boundary layer can be measured by switching on and off the heat flux across the water surface. This can be achieved by shutting on and off the ventilation of the air space. When the air space is closed, no heat transfer takes place and the surface temperature is equal to the bulk temperature. With open ventilation, evaporation takes place and the surface temperature is cooling down. The difference between these two temperatures directly gives ΔT (Fig. B.8a).

Figure B.8c shows the measured ratios. For high wind speeds and clean surface conditions the measured values agree well with the theoretical ratios so that reliable transfer measurements can be taken. At low wind speeds and water surfaces covered with surface films, the ratios is significantly lower. This is not surprising since under these circumstances no surface renewal takes place any more. Using a constant $\sigma_T/\Delta T$ -ratio

Figure B.9: *a* Decomposition of the spatial fluctuations into a Laplacian pyramid; the first four levels are shown; *b* variance in different levels of the Laplacian pyramid at wind speeds as indicated.

would significantly overestimate the transfer velocities. Therefore, it is important to perform further, more detailed measurements, as they are now possible in the Aeolotron. It would be best, if the degree of surface renewal could be estimated directly from infrared image sequences.

One way could be an analysis of the spatial structure of the micro turbulence at the ocean surface to find out which scales contribute most to air-sea gas transfer. Therefore we carried out a scale space study of the spatial structures of the microturbulence at the water surface [18, 19, 20]. The original infrared images are decomposed into a Laplacian pyramid. Since every level of the Laplacian pyramid spans an octave of scales, the variance within a level is a direct measure for the dominance of a certain scale. The investigated scales are in the range between centimeters and decimeters and thus much smaller than the wavelengths of the dominant gravity waves.

At low wind speeds, large scales (level 3 and 4) dominate the temperature distribution whereas the variance at medium speeds and small scales (level 0 and 1) are three times smaller (Fig. B.9). At moderate wind speeds all scales contribute about equally to the temperature distribution. Finally, at higher wind speeds the smallest scales (level 0) dominate the temperature distribution.

This first study shows that it is possible to measure $\sigma_T/\Delta T$ and to perform a scale analysis of the horizontal structures of the micro turbulence at the water surface. However, more detailed measurements are required. The reported measurements were handicapped by rather low heat fluxes. In the Aeolotron we will be able to achieve much higher heat flux densities. Therefore much better results can be expected.

7.2 Direct flux measurements

Although being a very important parameter in linking atmospheric and oceanographic models, experimental data of sea surface heat fluxes is scarce and imprecise. The energy budget at the sea surface may be written as

$$j_h = j_s + j_l + j_r, \quad (\text{B.5})$$

where j_h is the net heat flux in the ocean, j_s the sensible heat flux in the atmosphere, j_l the latent heat flux and j_r the radiative heat flux [16]. Current measurement techniques are combining different sensors and heuristic assumptions on water vapor transfer to calculate the individual fluxes that make up the net heat flux j . Quite often the individual sensors are separated by a few meters which makes for a low spatial resolution and big systematic errors. In order to produce any useful results integration times have to be in the order of a few minutes. Even with these strong limitations on spatial and temporal resolutions, measurements typically produce errors of about 30%. This turned out to be one major drawback in evaluating data from the 1997 field experiment as outlined in Section 3. Therefore an alternative more accurate method was devised.

Figure B.10: A typical infrared image at 4.2 m/s wind speed with the two dimensional flow field calculated and the total derivative of the temperature with respect to time $d/dt\Delta T(t)$.

Through the use of passive thermography with only one infrared camera, accurate laboratory and field measurements on a time scale of seconds are feasible. Our approach of measuring the heat flux assumes that surface renewal events are replacing surface water by bulk water. These fluid parcels are exposed to surface heat fluxes and are subject to a temperature change that is governed by molecular diffusion according to Fick's law, that is

$$j = -D\rho c_p \vec{\nabla} T. \quad (\text{B.6})$$

D is the coefficient of thermal diffusivity. In most conditions the net heat flux is negative which means that the sea surface temperature is colder than the bulk water, an effect often called the cool skin of the ocean. The temperature difference ΔT between surface temperature T_s and the temperature of the bulk T_b is given by

$$\Delta T(t) = \alpha j \sqrt{t - t_0}, \quad t \geq t_0, \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi D c_p \rho}} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where ρ is the density of the sea water, c_p the specific heat and t_0 the time at which the fluid parcel from the bulk was carried to the sea surface. This equation can be solved for the net heat flux j . The resulting equation poses the difficulty that the quantity $t - t_0$ cannot easily be measured. This problem can be solved by taking the total derivative of ΔT with respect to time in the reference frame of the fluid parcel, which is given by

$$\frac{d}{dt} \Delta T(t) = \frac{1}{2} \alpha j \frac{1}{\sqrt{t - t_0}}, \quad t \geq t_0 \quad (\text{B.8})$$

With these two equations j can be derived as

$$|j| = \sqrt{\frac{\pi D}{2}} c_p \rho \sqrt{\Delta T(t) \frac{d}{dt} \Delta T(t)}. \quad (\text{B.9})$$

The natural constants for sea water are quite well known and $\Delta T(t)$ can be derived from the infrared images. Thus, if $d/dt\Delta T(t)$ can be calculated, the net heat flux j is known.

In conjunction with project A (see Section 2) a digital image-processing algorithm was developed that allows for the extraction of the material derivative of the temperature with respect to time $d/dt\Delta T(t)$ from a sequence of infrared images, compensating the surface motion [10]. Exemplary results of this computation can be seen in Fig. B.11. From this derivative, the probability density function of the underlying surface renewal model, as well as the sea surface heat flux can be estimated [8].

A second way of calculating the net heat flux j was developed that relies on the material derivative of the temperature with respect to time $d/dt\Delta T(t)$, too. This method is of statistical nature for it makes some assumptions on the probability density function of surface renewal events. The average temperature difference across the cool skin of the ocean is given by [21] as follows:

$$\Delta \bar{T} = \int_0^\infty p(t) t^{-1} \left(\int_0^t \Delta T(t') dt' \right) dt \quad (\text{B.10})$$

The underlying transport model implicates that $p(t)$ is a log normal distribution, strong evidence of which has been presented in [8]. Given a log-normal distribution for $p(t)$ equation (B.10) can be integrated, leading to

$$j = \frac{3}{4} \sqrt{\pi D} c_p \rho \Delta \bar{T} \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma^2}{16} + \frac{m}{2} \right) \right]. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Figure B.11: **a** Results of calculations for the heat flux in three different wind regimes, following equation (B.9). The fluctuations of the heat flux are not errors but modulations of the flux by waves. The solid lines represent the net heat flux as calculated from temperature measurements of the water.

b Measured data of the times in between consecutive surface renewal events ($t - t_0$). The experimental data seems to agree with the theoretical log-normal distribution quite nicely.

Wind speed	j_{true} [W/m²]	j_{pdf} [W/m²]	j_{sqrt} [W/m²]
2.0 m/s	-111 ± 3	-100 ± 11	-137 ± 13
4.2 m/s	-161 ± 2	-149 ± 31	-188 ± 12
8.0 m/s	-304 ± 3	-273 ± 43	-280 ± 49

Table B.2: Comparison of results for calculations of j . j_{true} is the value calculated from the temperature decline in the Aeolotron as measured by precision thermometers, j_{sqrt} is the value calculated with equation (B.9) and j_{pdf} is given from the fit parameters as shown in equation (B.11). The results from the different methods seem to agree reasonably well.

The parameters σ and m are the parameters of the log normal distribution $p(t)$ which can be fitted to a histogram of times ($t - t_0$) between surface renewals. These times ($t - t_0$) can be calculated from infrared image sequences by solving equation (B.7) and (B.8):

$$(t - t_0) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\Delta T(t)}{d/dt \Delta T(t)} \quad (\text{B.12})$$

A plot of experimental data with the fitted log-normal distribution can be seen in Fig. B.11b.

Measurements at the Aeolotron were conducted and the results of the new techniques successfully compared to results gained independently. Results of these comparisons for three different wind regimes with heat flux calculations from equation (B.9) are shown in Fig. B.11. Comparison of heat flux measurements with both techniques (the one following equation (B.9) and that of equation (B.11)) are shown in table B.2. The simplicity of the experimental set-up makes field measurements feasible.

8 Studies of Air-Water Gas Transfer using Laser-Induced Fluorescence Techniques

A study was performed to investigate the feasibility of a spectroscopic measurement which enables us to perform both area- and depth-resolved measurements of the mass boundary layer (Diploma theses Ulrike Lode and Jutta Reinmuth). The new technique is a blend of ideas originating from the differential absorption technique of subproject C and multi-labeling techniques, as they will be used in subproject E and F.

The idea is as follows. The fluorescence spectrum of fluorescein excited at 488 nm peaks at 510 nm and extends beyond 600 nm. A second dye is used to attenuate the emitted fluorescent light in this wavelength range. With this double-dye technique, the shape of the observed fluorescence spectrum depends on the path length the light travels through the water before it is measured. Since the fluorescence is excited from the air space, the path length directly corresponds to the distance from the water surface and the spectrum of the observed fluorescence is given by

$$I(z) = \exp(-\alpha(\lambda)z) c_f(z) f(\lambda), \quad (\text{B.13})$$

where $\alpha(\lambda)$ is the wavelength-dependent absorption coefficient of the absorbing dye solution, c_f the concentration of the fluorescent dye and $f(\lambda)$ its fluorescence spectrum. For a given wavelength, the fluorescent light received is then integrated over a characteristic depth $\hat{z} = \alpha^{-1}(\lambda)$. The totally observed fluorescent intensity is given by integration over the depth:

$$I(z) = \int_0^{z_{\max}} \exp(-\alpha(\lambda)z) c_f(z) f(\lambda) dz. \quad (\text{B.14})$$

If both $\alpha(\lambda)$ and $f(\lambda)$ are known, (B.14) constitutes a linear inverse problem to determine the depth-dependent concentration, $c_f(z)$, of the fluorescent dye. It is of the same nature as retrieving the ozone profile or the tropospheric ozone concentration from the GOME absorption spectra (see subproject C) and optimizing the labeling of chromosomes with multiple fluorescent dyes (subproject F).

The solution of the inverse problem depends on the variation of α with lambda. It is obvious that only that depth range can be resolved over which \hat{z} is varying. We found a number of dyes that show strongly varying absorption coefficient in the interesting wavelength range from 500–600nm. We could also verify that the inverse problem is well posed for the spectra of these dyes. Depending on the number of spectral samples up to 40 height intervals could be resolved within the mass boundary layer. All these results indicate that a depth-resolving LIF-based mass boundary layer visualization technique is feasible.

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C Analysis of global gas emissions for multispectral image sequences

1 Introduction

Within the last 100 years the chemical composition of the atmosphere has changed significantly due to anthropogenic influences. Among the emitted trace gases, oxides of nitrogen (notably NO and NO₂) play a central role. Their natural concentration in most parts of the troposphere is believed to be below 10-20 ppt (part per thousand), whereas concentrations up to 200 ppb (part per billion) can now be found in cities. While NO₂ is itself toxic, its particular importance lies in the influence on atmospheric ozone chemistry. NO₂ may be also of interest with regard to radiative heating of the atmosphere.

The main sources for tropospheric NO_x (= NO + NO₂) are produced by industry and traffic, forest and bush fires (biomass burning), microbiological emissions by soil, exchange with the stratosphere, lightning and air traffic. It is estimated that more than 2/3 of the total NO_x emissions are thought to be anthropogenic, dominated by the burning of fossil fuels for transportation and industrial activities.

Current production estimates for anthropogenic sources are very uncertain, and this uncertainty is mainly due to shortcomings in measurement techniques used. The available ground-, balloon- and aircraft-borne instruments make only local measurements, from which it is very difficult to estimate the global distribution of the trace gases of interest. This deficiency can best be resolved by the use of space-borne monitoring devices.

In Phase II of the Research Unit a new method for the quantification of the global NO_x budget from image sequences of the GOME spectrometer on board the ERS-2 satellite was developed. In contrast to measurements using ground-based, balloon- or aircraft-borne sensors this instrument provides, for the first time, the possibility of observing global maps of NO₂ column densities. As part of this work, algorithms were developed to analyze GOME spectra numerically and to extract physically relevant parameters from the resulting maps using image processing techniques.

2 The Satellite Instrument

Since 1995 a novel instrument – the *Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment* (GOME) on board of the ERS-2 satellite – has become available. It is capable of monitoring the global distribution of various trace gases in the atmosphere with spectroscopic methods over a long period of time by measuring earthshine absorption spectra in the visible and near UV spectral range. The basis of the spectral analysis is the Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy. This technique compares the narrow structure of absorption bands in the spectrum with reference absorption spectra. As these spectra are characteristic for each trace gas the methods allows to derive the concentrations of various trace gases simultaneously.

Column densities of NO_x were determined using *Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy* (DOAS) [7]. By the combined use of an efficient B-spline interpolation and an inversion algorithm based on Householder transformations, the numerical algorithms accelerate the retrievals by a factor of 26 with respect to previous methods. Moreover, techniques were developed for separating tropospheric and stratospheric NO₂-columns and estimating the lifetime of NO₂ in the troposphere. This allows determination of regional NO_x source strengths.

3 Retrieval of trace gas concentration maps

The applied method consists of several analysis steps which will be presented sequentially in the following sections (Fig. C.1).

Figure C.1: Flowchart of the applied analysis procedures.

3.1 The Raw Data

The starting point of the analysis are raw spectral data of the GOME instrument which are scaled into *calibrated radiances* (Level 1 data, see Fig. C.1/1a) by the *Deutsche Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt* (DLR). Also the PMD data are used for further calculations (Fig. C.1/1b). To deal with the huge data rate (approximately 6 GB per month) an analysis algorithm has been developed which is able to perform the analysis on standard PC hardware at about 26 times real time acquisition.

3.2 The DOAS Technique

On the basis of these data, apparent NO_2 Slant Column Densities, SCDs, (Fig. C.1/2a) can be calculated from the NO_2 spectral signature using the DOAS method [7, 8, 9]. The spectral retrieval is the basis for generating time sequences of global NO_2 maps (see also [3, 4, 5]).

4 Cloud Detection

The PMD data yields an integral of the light intensity over the three wavelength intervals 295-397nm (UV), 397-580nm (blue) and 580-745nm (red). This data can be used to deduce information about clouds and the surface albedo (Fig. C.1/2b,c). Therefore a cloud detection algorithm has been developed using image sequences of PMD data. The cloud detecting algorithm focuses on two characteristics of clouds, their degree of whiteness and that clouds form a moving layer in front of a static background.

In fact the *whiteness* of the clouds seems to provide a good classification feature. This leads to a color model in which the color white plays a decisive part. An appropriate color model to measure whiteness is the HSV color model. In this model, the RGB color space is transformed to a cylindrical coordinate system in which H is the hue and is measured by the angle around the vertical axis, S is the saturation of the color relative to the color gamut and V specifies the brightness value. In this color space cloudy and clear-sky pixels separate quite well. We can now define a subset of the HSV space that characterizes the clouds. Since there is only a small overlap between the region classifying the background and the region of clouds, an efficient separation can be achieved by applying a threshold in the S-V space.

Figure C.2: A flow chart of the cloud detection method to determine a PMD background image. (A color version of this image can be seen in the CD version of this document.)

Although the results are very promising, the method only allows us to determine whether or not a cloud is detected but it does not allow us to infer the degree of cloud cover. Moreover, the limiting values for the cloud subspace are to a certain degree arbitrary and disregard local conditions like the ground albedo. Our method can serve as a pre-classification for the second, iterative cloud detection method described in the following section.

The results of the HSV method can be improved by considering that clouds are moving, forming and dissolving. Therefore those SV values nearly constant with time are likely to belong to the background whereas those which change should belong to cloudy pixels. That approach is successful, if the majority of days are cloud-free. Apparently, that condition is fulfilled through the HSV-pre-classification. The implementation of this idea is realized in the employed iterative algorithm.

- First we use the HSV-pre-classification to generate a PMD image sequence with less cloud cover.
- Then we calculate the mean RGB values over this series of pictures. This average picture serves as a first estimate for the background picture \mathbf{B}^0 .
- In the third step the background image \mathbf{B}^n allows us to measure the deviation of each pixel from the PMD images \mathbf{A}_k . For this purpose a weighting function $W(\|\mathbf{A}_k(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{B}^n(\mathbf{x})\|) \in [0, 1]$ is required, which is set to 0 if the actual pixel $\mathbf{A}(\mathbf{x})$ has nearly the same SV values as the one from the background image $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{x})$, and is set to 1 otherwise.
- The calculated weighted mean over the picture series (using the weighting function W) allows us to reiterate \mathbf{B}^n . By yielding a better estimate for the background picture, we go back to the third step.
- The algorithm terminates when the background image converges.

If $\mathbf{B}^n(\mathbf{x})$ is the background picture of the n^{th} iteration and \mathbf{A}_k the k^{th} picture of the time series, the cloud free background image is given by the fix-point of the following function:

$$f(\mathbf{B}^n(\mathbf{x})) = \mathbf{B}^{n+1}(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\sum_k^K \mathbf{A}_k(\mathbf{x}) W(\|\mathbf{A}_k(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{B}^n(\mathbf{x})\|)}{\sum_k^K W(\|\mathbf{A}_k(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{B}^n(\mathbf{x})\|)} \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Finally the background image $\mathbf{B}^\infty(\mathbf{x})$ can be used to calculate a degree of cloud cover. For a more detailed description of the algorithm see [10, 11].

Figure C.3: Visualization of the discrimination algorithm. (A color version of this image can be seen in the CD version of this document.)

5 Air Mass Factors

It has to be accounted for that a satellite-borne instrument measures trace gas concentrations integrated along a light path through the whole atmosphere, i.e. through both the troposphere and the stratosphere. Since these paths are in general not standing vertically on the ground and also do not represent a single physical path (they include scattering), they should be called 'apparent slant column densities'. In order to obtain column density data independent of the viewing geometry, the apparent slant column densities are transformed into 'vertical column densities' (Fig. C.1/3a) using a conversion factor. The figures Fig. C.3 and Fig. C.4 show an analysis flowchart and an example composite image. The conversion factor, called *Air Mass Factor*, is particularly dependent on the solar zenith angle (SZA) i.e. the location of the satellite, the scan angle of the instrument, the surface albedo, the viewing geometry and the cloud cover, Fig. C.1/3b).

$$\text{AMF} = \frac{\text{SCD}}{\text{VCD}} \quad (\text{C.2})$$

6 Separation of Stratosphere and Troposphere

However, for the analysis of anthropogenic influences only the tropospheric fraction is of interest. In Phase II of the Research Unit an algorithm was developed that discriminates between these two fractions by applying an image processing approach (Fig. C.1/4a,b).

Moreover, the calculation of the NO_x budget requires further processing: in general the earth is partially covered with clouds that hide tropospheric portions of the NO_2 column from the view of the satellite instrument. This is especially true for the tropospheric column which is of particular interest for the analysis of anthropogenic emissions. In Leue et al. [2], Leue [6] a technique is demonstrated how to correct the NO_2 columns in the temporal mean using the cloud detecting algorithm also developed in the research unit (see

Figure C.4: Illustration of the correction process for the tropospheric residual NO₂-column with the tropospheric Air Mass Factor. (A color version of this image can be seen in the CD version of this document.)

above). Furthermore certain assumptions can be made, e.g. the total column varies on a much larger spatial scale than the tropospheric fraction, due to the longer lifetime of nitric oxides in the stratosphere and the fast horizontal mixing there. The tropospheric emissions usually take place on a scale of only several hundreds of kilometers as they are mainly caused by rather localised emissions from industrial sources, or biomass burning events. These sources are only over land masses.

6.1 Estimation of the stratospheric background

The observation described above can be exploited to estimate the stratospheric background following an image processing approach. First land regions are masked out to avoid errors in the stratospheric signal due to tropospheric contributions. To avoid influences of emissions near coastlines a region of approximately 200 km off shore are disregarded as well. Using a threshold we segment pixels with a cloud fraction of at least 50% and mask out the cloud free pixels. On the remaining pixels the stratospheric proportion of the total column will dominate. The cloud fraction of the GOME pixels is detected using the cloud detection algorithm introduced by Wenig [10] which uses the data of the three PMD channels to deduce the fractional cloud cover for each GOME pixel. This procedure yields an image of NO₂ column densities with pixels that very likely represent the stratospheric NO₂ column but contain large gaps due to the masking process.

These gaps have to be interpolated in order to estimate the total stratosphere. To provide boundary conditions we have to account for the different structure of the stratospheric distributions in latitudinal and longitudinal directions. An interpolation algorithm has to be chosen which does not simply calculate the interpolated value for every pixel but also slightly takes into account the average over the neighbouring region, for the values do not exactly represent the stratosphere but contain noise and also remnants of the tropospheric NO₂ column.

Figure C.5: Example for the decay curve along a latitudinal section through a NO_2 plume at the eastern shore of the US. The $1/e$ width of the curve can be calculated by a nonlinear regression with an exponential function. (A color version of this image can be seen in the CD version of this document.)

We use for this purpose the concept of *Normalized Convolution* by Knutsson and Westin [1]. If \mathbf{g} denotes the original image, where $\mathbf{g}(x,y)$ is the NO_2 concentration, \mathbf{m} the mask for each pixel in the interval $[0, 1]$, which is given by $1/\sigma_g^2$ and is 0 for the gaps, then the interpolated image \mathbf{g}' is given by:

$$\mathbf{g}' = \frac{\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{g} \cdot \mathbf{m})}{\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{m})} \quad (\text{C.3})$$

with the lowpass filter operator \mathbf{B} which can be of different size in any coordinate direction.

The advantage of this filter type lies in its efficiency and the fact that it combines interpolation and averaging. The resulting numerical errors are dependent of the size of the gaps and are typically between 3.0 % and 20.0 %, the resulting stratospheric NO_2 -VCDs range from $1 \cdot 10^{15}$ to $4 \cdot 10^{15}$ molecules cm^{-2} (see Fig. C.4).

6.2 The Tropospheric Column

The result of the interpolation is now operationally defined as the stratospheric background of the total NO_2 column. An example can be seen in Fig. C.3 which also illustrates the intermediate steps in the discrimination algorithm. The image shows that the background could be estimated very well and is smoothly interpolated over the land regions which had been masked out for the calculation of the latitudinal sections.

The tropospheric contribution can now be estimated by forming the difference between the original image and the estimated stratosphere. In the resulting image Fig. C.3-c we see that localized emission sources appear pronounced, whereas the global stratospheric trend is almost completely suppressed. Moreover it emerges that the NO_2 column over land is systematically higher than that over the oceans which confirms our assumptions that the main sources are over land.

7 Emission Rates

These long time sequences of global tropospheric NO_2 concentration maps can be used for further analysis. From this time series of the mean NO_2 pollution for different areas of the world can be generated. As an example time series of monthly mean NO_2 concentrations are shown in Fig. C.6. The analysis of long time sequences seems to be very useful, because some problems can only be seen in the global view. We found out that there is a shift in stratospheric NO_2 which is nearly the same for every year. This is caused by an error in the measured solar spectrum which is dependent of the viewing geometry during the calibration phase.

For the determination of the mean NO_2 source strength from the tropospheric maps, knowledge of the NO_2 lifetime is necessary. This constant was estimated from the decay curve of NO_2 on the off wind side of coasts with strong tropospheric emissions (see Fig. C.5). For this calculation wind information from a meteorological database (NILU's database: <ftp://zardoz.nilu.no>, Norway) has been used.

Finally we derive estimates for the global emissions and emission rates of nitric oxides. With this method we introduce a new procedure which is completely independent of standard approaches to calculate the NO_x

Time series of monthly mean NO₂ Concentrations

Figure C.6: Time series extracted from the image sequence of the global tropospheric NO₂ maps.

Figure C.7: Estimate of the global mean NO_x emission for 1997 in units of nitrogen. The upper value denotes the mean mass in the atmosphere, the lower value the mean source strength.

budget (generally based on statistical data of fuel use and emission factors). It can thus be used to improve the current uncertainty in current estimates.

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D Time and Space-Resolved Measurements of Growth in Plants

1 Summary

The central topic of this project is the analysis of dynamics of growth processes of plants in space and time by image sequence analysis. During the report period (1) the 2D-expansion analysis developed during the first funding period was transferred to routine botanical analysis after adaptation of the set up and the algorithms. (2) For expansion analysis of freely moving leaves the moving camera system proved to be the most flexible and adequate approach. Reconstruction of the leaf position by depth-from-motion algorithms were implemented and applied. Extraction of the vein system in 3D was started. (3) Root expansion analysis was established in a structure-tensor based approach. A root tracking device was constructed and programmed to follow the growing root tip over several days. First steps to extract the co-ordinate system of the root automatically were done. (4) Reporter gene analysis of transgenic plants expressing green fluorescent protein in nuclei permanently and only during cell division was started. (5) The optical properties of leaves were evaluated by analysis of their interaction with polarised light and by construction of a CCD-spectrometer in the visible, near and far infrared wavelength. (6) Thermographic analysis was enhanced by a specially designed cuvette. Heat capacity, water content and whole leaf transpiration rate could be analysed.

2 Introduction

Spatio-temporal analysis of growing plant tissues is of central importance to understand how the generation of the plants internal patterns is determined by the genetic background, and adapted to dynamically varying environments. Despite its general importance, knowledge on spatio-temporal organisation of growth and differentiation in plant organs and tissues is very limited. This is mainly due to technical problems that make it difficult to analyse spatio-temporal dynamics at mechanistically meaningful resolution. On the other hand image sequence acquisition provides both spatial and temporal resolution and due to fast advances of available hard- and software has started to become a central tool in life sciences. In combination with physical and physiological expertise, quantitative information from living organisms can be revealed.

The aims of this project in the report period were (1) to establish the previously developed 2D- image sequence analysis in routine botanical application, (2) to develop modules allowing such analysis in freely moving leaves, (3) to commence analysis of spectroscopic and optical properties of leaves, and (4) development of techniques on spatio-temporal dynamics of root growth. (5) Thermographic analysis of leaves had to be optimised with respect to the set-up and the remote analysis of water content in intact leaves. (6) Dynamic imaging of reporter gene image analysis has been started with a number of different approaches, closely connected to growth analysis. During this funding period we assigned high priority to techniques that (7) extract the physiologically meaningful co-ordinate systems of the respective plant tissue from the image sequences.

3 Leaf Growth Analysis

3.1 Botanical Objectives

Leaf growth is central to a plants performance. The general pattern originates in the genetics of the leaf, but can be significantly altered by environmental constraints. Especially investigation of leaf growth of broad-leaved species (dicots) that show areal growth was significantly hampered by the absence of suitable methods. Expansion growth needs to be analysed in the temporal and spatial scales of hours and millimetres to link up to underlying processes of gene expression, cell elongation and dynamics of environmental impact.

Figure D.1: Diurnal course of the relative growth rate of *Ricinus* leaves as determined by the thread and the digital images sequence processing (DISP) methods. This analysis has been repeated many times during the report period with the same discrepancy in the diurnal course at the beginning of the night.

3.2 Starting Point

Mapping of 2D-spatio-temporal expansion rates in dicot leaves was established during the first funding period and published in Schmundt et al. [3]. This work reported, for the first time, on the diurnal patterns of expansion gradients in dicot leaves. The imaged leaf was fixed in a plane in front of the camera and image sequences were taken in the near infrared to minimise the disturbance of plants by light. To allow routine application, this technique needed to be further evaluated and extended.

Image sequences of growing castor bean plants showed considerable 3D-distorsion in a regular manner that were correlated to the diurnal course of leaf growth. For the 2D-expansion analysis these movements, were minimised by holding the leaf midrib in a horizontal plane. However, as this might interfere with growth processes, a technique had to be initiated, which would allow the analysis of non-fixed leaves.

3.3 Accomplishments in Leaf Growth Analysis

3.3.1 Evaluation of the 2D-Expansion Technique.

Comparison of the diurnal course of expansion rate in fixed and non-fixed leaves. During its development the results of the 2D-technique were evaluated versus classical expansion rate methods. These devices measure continuously the velocity of the leaf tip held under tension by an electronic recording device. As both methods put tension on the growing leaf, we compared the results with a method (thread method) newly developed by us, which allows to determine diurnal courses of overall expansion of freely moving leaves in 2 hour intervals [6].

This comparison revealed that 2D-expansion analysis and thread method gave matching results during most of the day, but showed a discrepancy at the beginning of the night. During this period expansion rate in the 2D-set up was significantly reduced in comparison to freely growing leaves (Fig. D.1). After some hours the expansion rate in the 2D-set up increased sharply to the values present in the control leaves. The amplitude and timing of the expansion rate during the rest of the diurnal course were in agreement between both techniques. In agreement with the shortening of the duration of expansion each day, the end size of the fixed leaves was significantly reduced compared to control leaves. Intriguingly, the leaf blade was undulated in the fixed leaves and smooth in the control leaves.

The 2D-set up interfered with leaf expansion during a period when unfixed leaves exhibited strong bending and downward movement. Reestablishment of control expansion rates occurred at the time of night when the growing leaf blade moved upwards again in unfixed leaves. Thus we hypothesised that hindrance of the leaf movement was responsible for the inhibition of growth in the earlier part of the night in fixed leaves and that biomechanical interaction could be responsible. Intensive analysis and experiments revealed that

pulling at the leaf tips with a force of 200 mN in the 2D-set up fully restored the end size of the leaf and the diurnal course to control values - without overshooting at other times of the day. Leaf undulation was no longer observed. This result is (a) of high botanical interest [7] as it indicates a significant role of the movement and implies a role of biomechanical signals in normal plant growth. It is of practical importance because (b) the convenient 2D-expansion analysis can further be used to study the basic organisation of expansion in botanical analysis.

Transfer of the 2D-expansion analysis to tobacco. Tobacco is one of the model species of modern plant molecular biology. Transfer of the 2D-expansion method required an adaptation of the leaf fixation technique and of the general set up to the stunted habitus of tobacco (Movie 1). Diurnal maps of leaf expansion were determined [6]. Further analysis concentrated on tobacco and *Ricinus* as model species.

Movie 1: Raw data sequence from a growing tobacco leaf hold in place by a suitable fixing set up.

Experiments for botanical characterisation of 2D-expansion revealed that (a) diurnal leaf expansion is linked to day-night cycles, as the diurnal variation ceases in continuous light. (b) The impact of environmental parameters (light intensity, drought, temperature, nutrients, light period) and development was studied. These experiments showed that the method can be applied in routine botanical experiments and gave new insights into the organisation of leaf growth during stress [4, 6].

Refinement of the 2D-expansion technique. The set up was enhanced significantly by

(a) improvement of the fixation. Additionally to the introduction of defined pulling forces, the direction and number of fixation threads was optimised. This allowed for a full 2D- analysis of the peltate leaf of *Ricinus* (Movie 2).

Movie 2: Rhythmic expansion growth of a *Ricinus* leaf during a diurnal course as mapped by the enhanced 2D-expansion analysis.

(b) A new IR panel was designed, which guarantees more intense and homogenous illumination and even allowed imaging in growth chambers with a high percentage of IR-radiation from the artificial light source.

The most significant improvement in the 2D-software were (a) enhanced interpolation algorithms, (b) adaptation of the display workspace to the requirements of botanical analysis (area of interests, export of data, adaptation of LUTs) and (c) a tracking function for analysis of growth rates of individual areas on the leaf. The latter was necessary, as the previous version of the software only allowed velocity and growth trajectories to be extracted for chosen pixels. However, as the leaf moves through the imaged frame a picked pixel represents different regions on the leaf. This made extensive manual effort necessary to extract the data needed to plot of expansion rates over time along the leaf structures. The developed tracker moves an interactively defined area along the velocity field determined in the 2D-analysis. This highlights the necessity to transfer the velocity and divergence fields to physiologically meaningful co-ordinate systems.

3.3.2 Extraction of the Vein System as the Physiologically Meaningful Co-ordinate System of Leaf Growth.

The co-ordinate system of leaf growth and development is the vein system [6]. It is the main pathway for the delivery of substances and the most prominent biomechanical feature of the dicot leaf.

Extraction of the vein system from the images taken in the near infrared was based on a sequence of imaging operations. Briefly, the origin of the main veins was interactively marked. A search algorithm identified preferred orientations. Orientation analysis on filtered images was used to find nodes and segments. These were combined and represented in chain code (Fig. D.2). The later allows to classify the vein system depending on the relative position in the vein tree (1st, 2nd, 3rd-order veins). The outline of the leaf was represented at subpixel accuracy by splines as developed. This approach was also used to analyse the 3D-position of the leaf (see below).

This work must be continued to accelerate the analysis and to make it more robust and thus suitable for routine analysis in botanical applications. Interactive adjustments should be minimised and the entire algorithm needs to be transferred to image sequences.

3.3.3 Analysis of Motion and Growth in Leaves Moving in Three Dimensions.

Fixation of the leaf had significant impact on the diurnal course of leaf expansion and 3D-movements of leaves were significantly correlated to expansion activity in the leaf (see above). Even though these could be overcome by application of a 200 mN pulling force, it was very desirable to refine the methods to allow analysis of expansion in a non-fixed leaf. This required 3D-analysis. The strategy for the development of an expansion analysis in dicot leaves without fixation combines low level image analysis for maximal density of motion, depth and growth maps with vein-oriented analysis. The latter represents the physiological co-ordinate system, but will additionally allow to reduce computing time significantly, as the first estimation of

*Figure D.2: Automatically extracted leaf vein system of *Ricinus communis*. The colors indicate different categories of the vein system.*

the 3D-position of the veins gives good approximate information about the position of the whole leaf. Several modules in this strategy were been started during this funding period in close cooperation with TP-A.

Imaging acquisition techniques for 3D-images

Three main approaches were used and evaluated to determine the 3D-structure of the leaf. **Laser scanner analysis** of *Ricinus* leaves was implemented during a visit of Hagen Spies in the laboratory of John Barron (Canada). The scanning laser beam gives a reflectance image and a depth map. The accuracy of the technique was found to be applicable to analyse slow movement of leaves in 3D (Movie 3). Problems for the technique are rapid movements of the leaf (e.g. induced by wind in a growth chamber), the wavelength of the laser beam (visible light - interaction with the physiology of the plant) and the high costs of the laser scanner (available in Canada on courtesy of Agriculture Canada).

Movie 3: Movement of *Ricinus* as imaged by the laser scanning range sensor. Left: reflection image, right: depth map: grey values indicate the depth of the leaf regions.

A structured light approach was established on the basis of a stripe projector (Fig. D.3 a). The algorithms to compute a depth map were implemented in Heurisko and first experiments were undertaken on growing leaves (Fig. D.3 b). Movement could nicely be analysed during the light period. However it proved to be difficult to use IR-illumination with the stripe projector. Therefore analysis during the night time, when the strongest movements occur, is problematic. Thus this technique - though highly accurate - is not easily adaptable to analyse leaf growth. However it can be used as a reference technique.

Image sequences of leaves taken by a **moving camera system** mounted on a swinging arm (Movie 4) were analysed using a depth from motion algorithm developed by TP-A [5]. This pendulum approach gave the 3D-position of the leaf surface can be calculated (Fig. D.4), and image sequences can be taken in the near IR-range. The technique is thus suitable to analyse leaves in light/dark cycles.

Movie 4: Image sequence from a swinging arm trajectory Movie 5: 3D-reconstruction of the leaf veins and the leaf outline by splines.

Vein system in image sequences for 3D-analysis.

In images from the moving camera sequences the techniques to extract the vein system were applied. Major veins and the circumference of the leaf were fitted with subpixel accuracy by splines. The 3D-position of these structures was estimated by a depth-from-motion algorithm (Movie 5, [2]). In the future we will concentrate on the moving camera approach, as it allows IR-imaging, multi-camera approaches, might have a high enough accuracy and can be used to analyse optical properties of leaves (see proposal).

a

Figure D.3: *a* Structured light approach on a Ricinus leaf. Patterns projected onto the leaf surface can be seen. *b* 3D-representation as calculated from the structured light approach on a Ricinus leaf.

4 Root Expansion Analysis

Root growth zones exhibit a linear arrangement of cell division (at the very root tip), cell expansion (region between 2 and 12 mm in maize) and differentiation. They have been intensively analysed under steady state conditions, but very little is known about the dynamic changes of spatio-temporal expansion patterns.

Root expansion mapping was first introduced into this project during the running funding period. Initially we aimed for a particle tracking approach (see previous proposal), as classical techniques for mapping root expansion use artificial landmarks and track their movement on the root surface. However, an evaluation of the image sequences revealed that the analogous approach to the leaf expansion method based on the structure tensor could be used and gave high density maps of expansion without the need for artificial landmarks.

Figure D.4: Reconstruction of the 3D-surface from the moving camera approach.

4.1 Development of the Experimental Set up

4.1.1 Development of the Root Tracker.

The growth zone of a root is only a few millimetres long with strong differences in expansion rates. In order to obtain maximal spatial and temporal resolution the expansion zone should cover most of the image frame. Therefore the expansion mapping could only be done for a period of several minutes before the root tip left the imaged region.

A root tracking device (root tracker) was conceived to follow the growing root tip and to hold the zone of interest within the frame. The root tracker was designed from "Mikrobank" components in conjunction with two moving stages to adjust the x- and y-direction. It was realised for imaging of (a) Arabidopsis roots growing on agar plates (a classical technique to grow plants e.g. for molecular biological applications) and of (b) tobacco and maize roots growing in the flowing solution culture (described in the previous report). For imaging roots growing on the agar, the plates were moved relative to the camera, in the nutrient solution set up the camera followed the growing roots (Fig. D.5 a and b). The root was segmented with an adjustable threshold and the binary image was scanned for the position of the root tip. Whenever the root tip left a predefined region during the image sequence, the moving stages were activated and positioned the growth zone again inside the image frame in x- and y-direction.

Illumination of the scene did benefit from the development of the new IR-LED panels. Manipulation of the root to place particles was not required any more, as structure tensor analysis works well on roots without artificial landmarks.

4.2 Root Expansion Analysis from Image Sequences

X-direction velocity and expansion rates were determined by structure tensor-based analysis adapted to root growth sequences (Movie 6). Velocity and growth profiles determined over periods of 30 minutes gave good results. Errors were mainly traced back to y-axis movements of the root tip due to lateral oscillations. The analysis will be further optimised due to the spatial and temporal resolution and by accounting for the y-direction movement of the root by oscillations. These oscillations are also of botanical interest and should be analysed quantitatively.

Figure D.5: *a* Root tracker for roots growing on Agar plates. *b* Root tracker for roots growing in nutrient solution.

Movie 6: Structure-tensor analysis of a growing root in nutrient solution.

4.3 Extraction of the Physiological Coordinate System

The physiological co-ordinate system of the root originates at the root tip and extends along the axis of the root. Up to now, growth and velocities fields were determined in image coordinates, which limits the accuracy of the analysis, as explained above. Additionally the curved and oscillating coordinate system has to be taken into account.

The present implementation of the root tracker determines the position of the root tip. Although, the absolute result is sensitive to the set threshold, if illumination is held constant, it is rather robust. The root tip velocity was analysed during experiments over a period of up to 11 days in *Arabidopsis* root grown on Agar plates (Fig. D.6). Extraction of the middle axis of the root can be obtained crudely from scanning of the binary image.

Subpixel accuracy of the position of the root tip, of the middle axis and the outline of the root is presently being worked on. Initial approaches include the application of splines as developed in TP-A to fit the outline of the root and to find the true axis of the root also in bending roots. Problems originate from the fact that especially in the image sequences of growing *Arabidopsis* roots, the root does not stay in focus throughout the experiment (due to the small field of depth of the microscopic objectives).

5 Reporter Gene Analysis

Reporter gene approaches couple the expression of the gene-of-interest with the occurrence of optical effects (luminescence, fluorescence, etc.) by expressing genes coding for optically detectable proteins. Some of these methods require the application of substrates by infiltration or spraying (Glucuronidase (GUS); Luziferase - Luziferin). An attractive alternative provides Green Fluorescent Protein (GFP), a protein from jellyfish ("Quallen"), which has inherent fluorescent properties.

5.1 Evaluation of the set up (slow scan camera)

A highly sensitive camera is available in the research unit (slow scan - Astrocam). This camera system was installed, an interface for the access from Heurisko was implemented and the usability for fluorescence and reporter gene imaging was evaluated. The sensitivity of the camera system is high enough to image even very low light processes. However, if speed is critical: the camera is too slow. Binning of pixels on the chip increases the frame rate, but reduces spatial resolution.

5.2 Experimental Advance in Dynamic Reporter Gene Imaging

Calcium imaging by Aequorin bioluminescence was not followed further after the first imaging results proved that cooled and touched leaves and roots of transgenic tobacco plants show transient luminescence (Fig. D.7, Fig. D.8). The slow scan camera had a high enough sensitivity to image the bioluminescence, but the slow frame rate allowed only 3-5 images per emission peak (see above).

Figure D.6: Root growth rate of a single *Arabidopsis* root as imaged over a period of 11 days by the root tracker. Variations of root growth rate are due to temperature variations. When - in other experiments - temperature in the root medium was held constant, no variations of root expansion rate was observed during day-night cycles, while the leaf expansion rate varied significantly.

Figure D.7: Ca-release visualised by luminescence of transgenic tobacco leaves expressing *Aequorin* in the response to cooling.

Luminescence of Luciferase expressed under the control of the promotor (on/off-switch of a gene) of Adenosin-5'-diphosphoglucose-Pyrophosphorylase (AGPase) was imaged. This approach was used to analyse the relative expression of AGPase, a key enzyme of starch metabolism, in relation to the availability of glucose and nitrate (Fig. D.8, DA H. Ehrler). The result proves that dynamic reporter gene analysis can be used for screening purposes.

Green fluorescent protein was imaged in a number of different transgenic lines with the slow scan camera system. A most interesting line has been analysed in a cooperation with Prof. D. Inze's laboratory (Gent, Belgium). These plants express a fusion protein between GFP and a nuclear location sequence (GFP-NLS), a signal peptide, which guides the protein (GFP) into the nuclei [1]. This causes permanent

Figure D.8: Expression of AGPase imaged by luminescence of Luziferase.

fluorescence of the GFP in the nuclei (Movie 7) and thus opens a possibility to quantitatively analyse cell number, local cell density and cell division dynamically by a kinematic approach (see proposal). This approach will be followed intensively during the following funding period.

Movie 7: Stack of confocal images through the root tip of transgenic Arabidopsis expressing GFP-NLS. The nuclei fluoresce due to transport of GFP into the nuclei (Transgenics provided by D. Inze and G. Beemster)

Development of **labile reporter gene products** opens another way to analyse cell division activity: A major drawback of these techniques for imaging dynamic processes has been that the reporter gene products were long living substances. As expected (see previous proposal) recently labile reporter genes have become available. Dr. P. Dörner (Edinburgh) provided us with transgenic Arabidopsis plants, which express labile GFP during cell division only (for details see proposal). First experiments show short term fluorescence events (minutes) when cells divide (Movie 8). We can now approach the rapidly expanding and promising field of labile reporter gene products, as we have already experience in analysing dynamic processes in living plants.

Movie 8: Integrated confocal image stack from roots of transgenic Arabidopsis expressing GFP transiently during cell division (Transgenics provided by P. Dörner). Two nuclei - in different depth in the tissue - flash up, while they divide, during this 1.5 hour sequences.

6 Infrared Imaging and Thermography

Leaf differentiation parallels leaf growth and thus occurs also in a spatially and temporally distinct manner. Exchange of water and carbon dioxide is a most prominent function of leaves. However, classical analysis of water relations allows only punctual analysis of set areas or integrated analysis of whole leaves.

Thermography has been used successfully in TP B to analyse gas exchange at the air-sea interface. During the first phase of this research, the theory to estimate transpiration rate from thermographic analysis was developed. The predicted linear relationship between transpiration rate and the temperature difference (between the transpiring leaf and a non-transpiring reference) was demonstrated experimentally (passive thermography). Maps of heat capacity were identified as crucial requirement to obtain local rates of transpiration, as significant differences in heat capacity between areas on the leaf are present.

6.1 Improvement of the Set-up

A **new cuvette system** was specifically designed to combine passive and active thermography. The system consists of a Plexiglas cuvette within a circulating gas volume (Fig. D.9). Temperature of the gas is controlled by a Peltier-based device and humidity is adjusted to a set point by a cold trap (max. throughflow 20 l/min). Gas composition (e.g. CO₂-concentration) can be changed by mixing CO₂-free air with pure CO₂. The cuvette itself has been constructed with a removable base and lid to allow adjustment of modules for different purposes. A base module was constructed that holds a Peltier-temperated plate for active thermography (DA B. Kümmerlen).

Figure D.9: Experimental set-up of the newly designed IR-imaging system consisting of the minicuvette gas exchange system (bottom), the cuvette system with control of temperature, humidity, light conditions and gas composition. The IR-camera is positioned on the top of the system between two high efficiency lamps. The IR-radiation of these lamps is shielded from the cuvette by means of two glass plates.

Active thermography was further optimised by implementing a feedback-controlled IR radiation module for the Peltier-controlled heat flux from beneath the leaf. The control parameters were optimised for Ricinus and tobacco leaves. Oscillating heat fluxes can now be used without drifts of the leaf temperature (DA Harald Ehrlér and Marcus Prokop).

6.2 Spatio-temporal Analysis of Transpiration, Heat Capacity and Water Content

Measurements in the new cuvette system validated the linear relationship between transpiration rate integrated over the entire leaf and the temperature difference between the leaf and a non-transpiring reference. Hysteresis in this relation was due to the temporal delay of the measurement of the temperature difference (instantaneous) and the IR-gas analyser (delayed by the time needed for mass flux from the cuvette to the device). From the data sets corrected for the delay in gas flux the heat transfer coefficient (HTC) could be quantified for the whole leaf. Dependency of HTC from wind speed was found to fit a square model.

Heat capacity (HC) was measured using the active thermography module in the base of the cuvette. We found that HC of the vein system was double the HC of the interveinal areas. The thickness of a water film equivalent to the measured HC was found to be close to the local thickness of the analysed leaves.

A comparison of the heat capacity and the water content showed the theoretically expected linear relationship. However, a detailed analysis of the variation of this relationship showed systematic overestimation of the water content at the edge of the leaf and the leaf tip Fig. D.10a. Additionally the relations between integrated transpiration rate and temperature differences between the reference and local temperatures ex-

Figure D.10: *a* Distribution of deviations of relative water content as estimated by thermography from the measurement by direct biomass analysis; *b* Variation of transpiration rate vs. ΔT at different sites of the leaf.

hibited significant deviations between central and edge areas of the leaf Fig. D.10b. Thus we conclude that the heat transfer coefficient varies significantly across the leaf and a further technique to analyse these spatial variation is required for full analysis of local transpiration, heat capacity and water content. Additionally this measure would provide a means to analyse the role of the boundary layer conditions at the leaf-air interface. This is a long lasting debate in botanical research, also linked to growing leaves, as e.g. leaf hair density varies with leaf age.

7 Optical Properties of the Leaf - Systematic Analysis to Support Quantitative Imaging

Several investigations were taken during the funding period on specific optical properties of the leaf. The aim of these analyses was to find suitable imaging conditions that ease image sequence analysis. It is not the purpose of this research to fully analyse this highly complex optical system. The topics were chosen on the basis of the direct applicability to actual approaches.

7.1 Analysing Leaf Structure with Polarised Light

Polarised light is a promising approach to (a) identify the vein system and (b) to gain more information about the interaction of leaf structure with light in general (see proposal). Image sequences of leaves illuminated with polarised light were taken and the effect of different polarisation angles between analysator and polarisator were tested. In direct transmission mode the vein system provided the highest contrast to the interveinal areas when the angle of the plane of polarisation was parallel to the longitudinal direction of the local vein structure. Therefore, veins in different orientations are highlighted depending on the angle of the plane of polarisation. This effect was obtained with polarised light in the visible and the infrared wavelength range (Movie 9a). The opposite contrast between veins and interveinal areas was obtained when the polarised light source and the camera with analysator were not positioned on one axis (Movie 9b). This difference can be used to further increase the contrast between veins and interveinal areas. Additional effort is required to analyse the impact of the inclination of the leaf surface as a 3D-object for adequate application of polarised light. This will yield additional information on the leaf structure.

Movie 9: (a) direct transmission of polarised light (near IR) through a Ricinus leaf. During the sequence the analysator was turned in 10 degree steps. (b) Interaction of polarised light and Ricinus leaf at a angle of 150 degrees between camera and polarised light source.

Infiltration of water into the intercellular spaces significantly altered the interaction of polarised light with the leaf structure. This result promises that analysis of the leaf with polarised light has a potential for determining the third important process of growth, namely the formation of intercellular gas spaces. These are of high structural and functional importance especially in leaves and have yet been neglected in growth analysis in general - again for technical reasons.

Figure D.11: Schematic setup of the CCD-based spectrometer.

7.2 Spectroscopic Analysis of Leaves in the Visible, Near and Far Infrared Wavelength

A CCD-based spectrometer was set up, which allows to capture simultaneously spectra along a line of a leaf (Fig. D.11). A "Geradsichtprisma" was used as the dispersive element, as it allowed a linear set up of the device.

The spectra were recorded along one axis of the CCD chip as previously initiated in TP B. This device has been set up to identify spectroscopic fingerprints of specific structures and substances along spatial (and temporal) gradients (DOAS approach). Based on these fingerprints, filter sets shall be identified, which allow the registration of these structures and substances in two dimensions.

The sensitivity and range of wavelength of the system was evaluated and it was calibrated by the monochromator available to the research unit (co-operation with TP E). Spectra and intensity of Xenon and halogen radiation sources as well as diode lasers were analysed to demonstrate their applicability for leaf spectroscopy. First spectra of tobacco and Ricinus leaves have been taken (Fig. D.12).

The interaction of polarised light of different wavelength was analysed at a set of polarisation planes. The first results imply that polarised light of different wavelengths is interacting with the leaf in different ways. This can probably be used to study the fate of light of different wavelength inside the tissue (see proposal). Chlorophyll fluorescence spectra along a transect across the leaf could be measured.

First experiences with spatially resolved IR-spectroscopy analysed the absorption of IR radiation in Ricinus leaves at a number of wavelength at which water absorbs (selected by IR-filters). Evaluation proved that water films of the typical thickness of the leaf could be analysed (co-operation with TP A, B and C) and that leaves showed significant contrast between veins and interveinal areas. This approach will be further evaluated on the chance to build an additional method to analyse water content and thus heat capacity. This information would then allow active thermography to be used to analyse local gradients of the heat transfer coefficient (HTC, see above).

Figure D.12: Spectrum of a transect across a *Ricinus* leaf as taken by the CCD-spectrometer. In this set up a heat filter strongly reduced radiation of wavelength above 900 nm. This filter will be removed in future experiments to exploit the full spectral sensitivity of the CCD-camera. The y-axis in the plots depict a line across a *Ricinus* leaf. For each pixel along this line the x-axis gives the spectral information. Please bear in mind that the dispersion is not linear with the wavelength.

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E Spatial and temporal analysis of Ca^{2+} -regulation and of motor protein motility

1 Introduction and Summary

The aim of this project is to use image sequence analysis for the investigation of calcium regulated dynamic processes in cellular and subcellular muscle fiber preparations. This includes the direct analysis of motor protein interaction in the *in vitro* motility assay as well as studying the regulation of this interaction by the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR), the intracellular Ca^{2+} -ion store.

Our general approach is to combine experimental work with digital image analysis and mathematical modeling. This allows us to study the molecular basis of cellular and subcellular processes. Especially for clinical medical applications this approach is very useful, as it helps to reveal the relation between molecular mechanisms and physiological and pathophysiological phenomena on the cellular level. This obviously is of great importance for our understanding of diseases, where modulations and alterations of molecular interactions are involved, as well as for identifying the molecular targets for drug delivery.

During the last three years we have made enormous progress in both fields of Ca^{2+} -regulation and motor protein interaction. We could internationally establish our general approach of a model based analysis of Ca^{2+} -transients recorded in "skinned" muscle fiber preparations, where the outer cell membrane is permeabilised [18]. Additionally we could significantly improve our experimental equipment for fluorescence imaging experiments and now have the possibility to use epi-fluorescence, confocal and multiphoton fluorescence microscopy. Therefore with our model based approach we can now address not only macroscopic Ca^{2+} -releases but also study subcellularly localized elementary events of Ca^{2+} -release (Ca^{2+} -sparks).

In the field of motor protein interaction we succeeded to adopt the structure tensor method for the analysis of noisy fluorescence images [19]. We now have an automated method with high precision which we can use for the analysis of large image data sets. This will allow us to systematically address interesting and important physiological questions. Additionally we have implemented a mathematical model of the acto-myosin interaction, which allows us to study the molecular basis of actin filament sliding in the *in vitro* motility assay.

2 Dynamics of Ca^{2+} -regulation in skinned skeletal muscle fibers

In general, the fast activation of skeletal muscle fibers within a few milliseconds is initiated by an action potential generated by a nerve impulse, which is transmitted to the interior of the muscle fiber via the transverse tubular system leading to the voltage-dependent release of Ca^{2+} -ions through ion channels (ryanodine receptors) in the membrane of the sarcoplasmic reticulum (SR). Diffusion of these ions leads to a transient global cellular increase in the free myoplasmic Ca^{2+} -concentration by one to two orders of magnitude. Via activation of the Ca^{2+} -binding troponin/tropomyosin complex this finally results in the contraction of the muscle fiber.

The later stages of Ca^{2+} -reuptake by the SR, which is essential for the contraction-relaxation process are still not very well known. Apart from binding to intracellular buffers (e.g. parvalbumins, troponin-C), Ca^{2+} -ions are actively removed from the myoplasm by the powerful Ca^{2+} -ATPase, which actively pumps Ca^{2+} -ions back into the SR and thus lowers the intracellular Ca^{2+} -concentration to achieve relaxation.

The function of the SR and its constituents, for example, the Ca^{2+} -ATPase, can be extensively studied in "skinned fiber" preparations, where the outer sarcolemma has been removed either by mechanical microdissection, by UV-laser microdissection or by chemical detergent treatment [21], thus allowing direct diffusional access to the myoplasm. Effects of various drugs on the contractile proteins and on components of the SR can directly be investigated by recording caffeine-induced force and fluorescence transients, which are well-established indicators to monitor the Ca^{2+} -handling in these preparations.

2.1 Experimental techniques

We record the caffeine induced Ca^{2+} -transients with the ratiometric Ca^{2+} -sensitive dye Fura-2 [3]. Fura-2 allows dual excitation measurements and thereby offers the advantage that the fluorescence signal is independent of critical quantities, for example, the dye concentration and the specimen geometry. Therefore the changes in the fluorescence ratio signal can be directly correlated with a change in the Ca^{2+} -ion concentration bound to the fluorescent indicator.

Figure E.1: Macroscopic caffeine induced Ca^{2+} -transient in a skinned fiber recorded with $10 \mu\text{M}$ Fura-2. From [18]

Figure E.1 is a typical example of a caffeine-induced Ca^{2+} -transient in skinned muscle fiber preparations. After the addition of caffeine at time $t = 0\text{s}$ the release of Ca^{2+} -ions inside the muscle fiber for times $t < 2.4\text{s}$ can be seen and for times $t > 2.4\text{s}$ the contribution of Ca^{2+} -diffusion out of the fiber through the permeabilized sarcolemma is clearly visible. Due to the diffusional loss of Ca^{2+} -ions the radial concentration profile is of very special interest in these experiments. Therefore intensity cuts perpendicular to the muscle fiber axis were acquired from each ratio image of the time series. The alignment of the radial profiles in time leads to the top left panel in figure E.2, which consequently reflects the spatiotemporal Ca^{2+} -ion distribution. The solution surrounding the muscle fibers in these experiments contains large amounts of extrinsic buffers, which comprises 0.5mM EGTA and the fluorescence indicator Fura-2 itself. Therefore the accurate description of the total Ca^{2+} -turnover can only be achieved by using a more sophisticated analysis of the fluorescent images.

2.2 Mathematical modeling

For modeling the Ca^{2+} -turnover in "skinned" skeletal muscle fibers one can use cylindrical symmetry for a first approximation. The following model calculations were performed assuming homogeneity along the fiber axis and radial symmetry. As the main process of Ca^{2+} -translocation is diffusion, modeling the Ca^{2+} -transient leads to the solution of the diffusion equation with various sink and source terms. The diffusion equation in cylindrical coordinates where diffusion occurs purely in radial direction can be written as

$$\frac{\partial c(r, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r D \frac{\partial c(r, t)}{\partial r} \right) + h(r, t) \quad (\text{E.1})$$

with

$$h(r, t) = \sum_l h_l(r, t)$$

where c is the concentration, D is the diffusion coefficient of the diffusing substance, r is the radial coordinate, t is the time coordinate, and $h(r, t)$ is the sum of all source and sink terms $h_l(r, t)$ of the various processes involved.

Let $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ denote the free Ca^{2+} -concentration in the following equations.

The release of Ca^{2+} -ions from the sarcoplasmic reticulum is assumed to be proportional to the concentration gradient across the SR membrane

$$\frac{d[\text{Ca}^{2+}]}{dt} = k_1 ([\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{SR} - [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{myoplasm}}) \quad (\text{E.2})$$

where k_1 is the proportional constant, which can be used to adjust the extent of SR Ca^{2+} -ion release per unit time.

The active removal of Ca^{2+} -ions from the cytosol by the SR Ca^{2+} -pump is modeled with a Hill-type relation, assuming a Ca^{2+} -dependent second-order saturable pump. The uptake of Ca^{2+} -ions into the SR can then be written as

$$\frac{d[\text{Ca}^{2+}]}{dt} = p \frac{v_{\text{max}}[\text{Ca}^{2+}]^n}{[\text{Ca}^{2+}]^n + K_m^n} \quad (\text{E.3})$$

where v_{max} is the maximum uptake velocity, K_m is the half-maximal uptake rate, $n = 2$ is the Hill-coefficient, and p is the proportional factor.

Calcium is assumed to bind to all buffers in a 1:1 stoichiometry and without cooperativity, so that the following equation holds:

$$\frac{d[\text{Ca}^{2+}]}{dt} = k_{\text{on}}^l [\text{Ca}^{2+}]_{\text{free}} \cdot [\text{buffer}^l]_{\text{free}} - k_{\text{off}}^l \cdot [\text{Ca}^{2+} - \text{buffer}^l] \quad (\text{E.4})$$

where $l = 3, 4, 5$ is the index for the various buffers, k_{on}^l is the kinetic on-rate constant, k_{off}^l is the kinetic off-rate constant of the $\text{buffer}^l - \text{Ca}^{2+}$ binding.

The finite difference approximation of the diffusion equation without sink and source terms neglecting the error term is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} c_{i,j+1} &= \frac{D}{2i} \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta r)^2} [(2i+1)c_{i+1,j} - 4ic_{i,j} + (2i-1)c_{i-1,j}] + c_{i,j} \\ c_{0,j+1} &= 4D \frac{\Delta t}{(\Delta r)^2} (c_{1,j} - c_{0,j}) + c_{0,j} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.5})$$

The upper equation is for $i \neq 0$ only. The indices i and j denote the radial grid position and the discrete time index, respectively. Similar finite difference formulae can be found for the other differential equations.

The boundaries of the system have to be treated with reasonable boundary conditions. In the present case Neumann boundary conditions naturally apply, as there can be no flux perpendicular to the glass surface of the experimental chamber. Also, the interface between two different media, in this case between cytosol and surrounding bath solution, has in general to be treated separately. The rate equation for the change in free myoplasmic calcium concentration at grid points inside the fiber volume is given by

$$c_{i,j+1} = \text{diff} + h_{1i,j} - h_{2i,j} - h_{3i,j} - h_{4i,j} - h_{5i,j} \quad (\text{E.6})$$

where diff stands for the finite difference formula described by equation 5 for diffusion, $h_{1i,j}$ is the Ca^{2+} -release term, $h_{2i,j}$ the Ca^{2+} -pump term, $h_{3i,j}$ is the buffering of troponin-C, $h_{4i,j}$ the buffering of EGTA and $h_{5i,j}$ the buffering of Fura-2. Similar rate equations can be obtained for the concentration of each substance and for the grid points outside the fiber volume. Finally, the rate equation for the free Ca^{2+} -concentration inside the sarcoplasmic reticulum can be written as

$$c_{i,j+1}^{SR} = v_{SR} (h_{2i,j} - h_{1i,j}) - h_{6i,j} + c_{i,j}^{SR} \quad (\text{E.7})$$

where $h_{6i,j}$ denotes calsequestrin buffering and $v_{SR} = 10$ is the volume factor compensating the fact that the SR occupies only 10% of the fiber volume.

The diffusion coefficients of calcium and all mobile buffers are significantly different in free solution and in the cytosol. The diffusion coefficients are only roughly half the value in the cytosol (for free Ca^{2+} -ions: $D_{\text{cytosol}} \approx 225\text{-}300 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, $D_{\text{free}} \approx 700 \mu\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$), thus, all models have to include the distinction between the different media. The kinetic on- and off-rate constants of many Ca^{2+} -buffers have been measured *in vivo* and *in vitro*, but uncertainties still originate from the fact that these quantities are highly sensitive on experimental conditions, for example, ionic strength and pH. Therefore, corrections regarding the experimental conditions are very often required.

Figure E.2: *a* Experimentally determined spatio-temporal distribution of Ca^{2+} -ions, *b* – *d* the simulated spatio-temporal ion-distributions (Ca^{2+} bound to the fluorescent indicator, free Ca^{2+} and total Ca^{2+}) as obtained by the model calculations.

The various parameters for the simulation and their original measurement are summarized in [18].

The radial Ca^{2+} -ion distribution as calculated from the model is shown in figure E.2. For the details, especially the calibration, see [18]. It is evident that the radial Ca^{2+} -Fura-2 distribution roughly corresponds to the measured radial Fura-2 fluorescence signal. The other concentrations of interest, for example, the free Ca^{2+} -ion distribution, are significantly different from the measured fluorescence signal. This can not solely be explained by the nonlinear calibration curve of the fluorescent dye.

The differences mainly arise from the kinetic properties of the fluorescence dye and the high extraneous buffer capacities. In general, the error due to the kinetic limitations of the fluorescence indicator is larger, the faster the processes occur.

We now have the possibility not only to study the spatio-temporal time course of the free Ca^{2+} -concentration, but also the time course of other quantities normally difficult to access with experimental techniques. Changes in the total Ca^{2+} -concentration, without a significant change in the free Ca^{2+} -concentration, for example are thought to play an important role in the pathophysiological development of

Figure E.3: Quantities derived from the model calculations: **a** time course of the release rate of Ca^{2+} -ions from the sarcoplasmic reticulum; **b** time course of the free Ca^{2+} -ion concentration inside the sarcoplasmic reticulum; **c** flux of Ca^{2+} -ions across the permeabilized sarcolemma from the fiber preparation into the surrounding bath solution; **d** time course of the rate of change in free Ca^{2+} -ion concentration inside the fiber preparation.

Duchenne muscular dystrophy. We now have the possibility to address these questions very directly with this model based approach. Also the various components and fluxes (see for example figure E.3) during the Ca^{2+} -turnover can now be directly addressed.

We have also extended our mathematical model by one spatial dimension, in order to account for the more complex structure of the sarcoplasmic reticulum. The first approach included two-dimensional diffusion with radial symmetry and binding to several buffers (EGTA, Fura-2, Troponin-C, Calsequestrin). Confocal microscopic images can also be simulated by convolution with a typical point spread function (PSF) of a microscope (a 3D-Gaussian kernel with different geometric parameters (e.g.FWHM) for the r and z axes). We are now able to compare the results with our experimental data after determining the specific PSF of the fluorescence microscopic setup. Different experimental conditions can be easily modeled by adapting the various parameters to the specific experimental conditions.

Figure E.4 is an example for a simulation of a Ca^{2+} -release obtained with the extended 2-dimensional model. Release occurs from $t=0$ ms to $t=5$ ms from a source with 80 nm in diameter centered around the origin. Again the fluorescence signal which is considered to be proportional to the amount of calcium bound to the fluorescent indicator can not be simply correlated with the free Ca^{2+} -concentration via the dissociation constant. With the help of this model we are currently evaluating the influence of different release sizes and different release source distributions in the membrane of the sarcoplasmic reticulum [14].

2.3 Deconvolution

The experimental data obtained with the fluorescence microscopic methods, especially epi-fluorescence images, contain large amount of out of focus information. We have addressed this problem experimentally and theoretically as described in the following. Experimentally we have optimized our flow chambers such that the least amount of background fluorescence occurs while simultaneously still having a homogeneous solution flow. For eliminating the remaining out of focus information we have tested various deconvolution methods. The various methods tested and implemented were:

- van Cittert algorithm

Figure E.4: Spatio-temporal Ca^{2+} -ion distribution bound to the fluorescent indicator as obtained with the extended 2D-model. Release occurs from $t=0$ ms to $t=5$ ms from a source of 80 nm in diameter centered around the origin.

- Richardson-Lucy algorithm
- Maximum a posteriori algorithm
- Blind deconvolution algorithm

The main criteria for the quality of these algorithms except for their ability to remove out of focus information are their convergence with high amount of noise and the computing time. All algorithms have been testes on computer generated test sequences and on real fluorescence image data sets (for details see the Diplomarbeit [4]).

In summary we obtained the best results with the blind deconvolution algorithms, which was surprising in the first stage, as these algorithms do not use the measured point spread function (PSF) of the microscopic system as for the other algorithms, but iteratively approximate the PSF. The reason for this is due to the fact that measured PSFs itself contain noise and therefore the deconvolution is biased by this noisy PSF. Although the blind deconvolution does not use any information of the actual optical system it yields better results, since the PSF is approximated and not influenced by noise . For the details see [4].

3 Motor protein interaction studied in the *in vitro* motility assay

In the *in vitro* motility assay originally devised by [8] fluorescently labeled actin filaments move over a surface of immobilised myosin or heavy meromyosin. Many parameters of this motion have been shown to be of significant importance for our understanding of the acto-myosin interaction, as e.g. the filament velocity is thought to be directly correlated to the unloaded shortening velocity of muscle fibers and therefore a direct reflection of the cross-bridge turnover rate ([2]). Also this assay is ideally suited to screen the functional domains of myosin, such as the nucleotide binding site, the actin binding site, the converter region and the lever arm ([15], [9], [13], [20], [7]). Furthermore myosin isoforms ([17], [6]) and actin mutants as e.g. described in [1] can be selectively studied in this assay.

Therefore an accurate and standardized determination of the various parameters of actin filament motion is of vital importance for exploiting the full power of this assay. Current techniques for automated determination of motion in series of images are mostly based on particle tracking algorithms with a preceding segmentation ([11], [22]). Segmentation in low light level images with a low S/N ratio is still a process, which is subject to arbitrary and selective assumptions. Furthermore particle tracking algorithms inherently suffer from major problems. For determining the actin filament motion in the *in vitro* motility assay these algorithms mostly use the centroid of the filaments to calculate their displacement and hence their velocity. As pointed out by several groups (e.g. [5]) this generally leads to an underestimation of actin filament speed

Figure E.5: Top: Confocal fluorescence image of a skeletal muscle fiber. Lower panel: Blind deconvolution of the above image with 50 iterations. The small insets show the restored PSF as obtained with the blind deconvolution algorithm. See [4] for details.

when longer filaments are considered, which generally follow curved trajectories. The error depends on filament length and the curvature of the trajectory. Using only pointlike filaments is an arbitrary selection of filaments with the uncertainty of thereby selecting certain filament properties. Another problem of most automated algorithms is that non motile filaments are also assigned a non zero velocity due to Brownian motion or jitter introduced by the acquisition hardware ([5]). This can lead to significant alterations in the histogram of filament velocities, i.e. introducing new apparent filament velocities, whose amplitudes are solely dependent on the fraction of non motile filaments and whose absolute values are strongly dependent on the frame rate of image acquisition ([5]). Also many of these algorithms have not been tested on artificial data sets, which allow to quantify the accuracy of each method. Therefore there is a large uncertainty if differences in filament velocities can be entirely ascribed to variations in the various parameters of the acto-myosin interaction, or to the different experimental conditions rather than to the different algorithms used for the analysis of the actin filament motion.

Therefore we have implemented an automated method using the structure tensor method for the determination of actin filament velocity in the in vitro motility assay with subpixel accuracy. To characterize the performance of the algorithm we have tested the method on both artificial data sets and experimental data from rabbit fast skeletal myosin .

3.1 Tests on computer generated test sequences

Our implementation of the structure tensor method was first tested on computer generated sequences in order to characterize its performance under known conditions. The displacement vectors and subsequently the velocity vectors determined by the structure tensor method are computed for every image of the image sequence. This can be done for the entire frame size or for smaller areas of interest (aoi) within the frame. From the velocity vectors all other quantities, such as e.g. the absolute value of the velocity and hence the

velocity distribution, can be derived. The objects are rodlike filaments with different lengths, which move in x- and y-direction, in a 45° degree angle and in an approximate circle, respectively. These motions represent a basis of possible displacements, from which all other movements can be derived. The displacement of objects in all sequences was 1 pixel/frame for the motion in x-y direction and for the approximate circular motion. The objects in the diagonal direction move with a displacement of $\sqrt{2}$ pixel/frame. The tests were performed with different levels of Gaussian noise superimposed on the image sequences (for details see [19]).

The tests showed that our algorithm based on structure tensor method allows the exact quantification of the velocities with subpixel accuracy even with high amount of noise superimposed. The noise does not bias the peak velocities, but only results in a broadening of the velocity distribution ([19]).

3.2 Analysis of motility assay image sequences

Figure E.6: Top: Example of an analysis of 100 frames of motility assay data with our structure tensor method. For the analysis areas of interests (aoi) can be selected. Scale bar 10 μm . Bottom: Histograms for the velocity distributions in the aois and in the entire frame. Additionally the velocity histogram obtained with a conventional particle tracking algorithm is shown in the right lower panel. From [19]

As an example for the application of the method to noisy fluorescence images the analysis of the velocity distribution of actin filament movement in an in vitro motility experiment is shown in figure E.6. The upper panel in figure E.6 shows the 4 areas of interest (aoi) selected for the analysis of the velocity distributions in the time series. Additionally the velocity distribution for the entire frame is calculated. In the lower panel of

figure E.6 the resulting velocity histograms are plotted. One can distinguish different filament populations, a slow moving population as analyzed in *aoi1* with a filament speed of approximately $0.6 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ and a fast moving population as analyzed in the other areas of interest with a mean speed of approximately $3 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ and a small fraction of filaments with velocities above $4 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ as detected in *aoi3* and *aoi4*. The velocity distribution calculated for the entire frame has its peak velocity at $3.01 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$ with a broadness of $0.67 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$. The calculation is performed on the first level of a Gaussian pyramid and the time to calculate the velocity histogram for the entire frames of the image sequence (768×576 pixel, 8 bit, 100 images) is less than one minute on a standard PC. Figure E.6 additionally shows the velocity distribution as obtained with the a standard particle tracking algorithm. All motile filaments in the frame were tracked, once a filament stopped it was discarded for the stop period. Again the peak velocities as calculated by the structure tensor method ($v_{\text{max}}=3.01 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$) and the particle tracking algorithm ($v_{\text{max}}=3.04 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$) are very similar. The distribution obtained with the tracking algorithm is significantly broader ($2\sigma=2.4 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$) than the respective distribution obtained with the structure tensor method ($2\sigma=1.34 \mu\text{m}/\text{s}$). This is in accordance with the results obtained with the test data described above, where the analysis of curved trajectories generally leads to a broader velocity distribution with the particle tracking algorithm [19]. In most cases curved trajectories are by far the most dominant movements of actin filaments in the *in vitro* motility assay.

3.3 Mathematical modeling of the acto-myosin interaction

For the detailed analysis of the actin filament motion in the *in vitro* motility assay experiments we have developed a mathematical model, where the underlying molecular interactions are simulated.

We have implemented a model of the cross bridge cycle, where the interaction of myosin (S1 or HMM) with actin is described by the differential equations obtained with a spring type model [12]. These mechanical states are also correlated with the known biochemical states of ATP-hydrolysis. The basic architecture of HMM can be viewed as a rigid shaft, a spring and a chemical active head which is capable of hydrolyzing ATP and which has a high affinity for the discrete binding sites of actin (see figure E.7). The actin filament is assumed to consist of a few actin monomers. Each of these monomers represents a discrete binding site, so that several myosins can attach to one actin filament. A pair of monomers is linked with a spring but we assume that this spring shall be rigid in the first approximation.

The implemented model of the ATP- cycle is shown in the lower panel of figure E.7. At the rigor state HMM is attached to the actin filament. Binding of ATP leads to the detachment from the actin filament and in the next step the hydrolyses of ATP to ADP+Pi occurs. Subsequently HMM rebinds to the filament and triggered by the Pi-release a conformational change in the myosin head region occurs. After the release of ADP the system returns to its initial state. The chemical reaction speed of the several stages are expressed by the use of respective rate constants.

In the first step of our model the following assumptions were made. As mentioned above, the spring between two actin monomers is assumed to be rigid. HMM can only bind to one actin monomer. The cycle has only one stage, the conformational change, where the rate constant is $1/(\text{cycle time})$. In the next step several myosins are allowed to attach to one filament.

From these interactions the forces on single actin filaments are calculated and hence the equations of motion are derived and solved. The model output is transformed either to velocity histograms or to image sequences in order to directly compare the model output with experimental images sequences (for details see [10]).

4 Other activities within the research unit and future prospects

During the previous funding period a variety of collaborations with other projects of the research unit have been successfully established. Additionally to the close collaboration with the central project (A), which already resulted in a variety of common publications (e.g. [19]), there has also been a very close research contact to projects D and F.

Especially the possibility of using confocal and multiphoton microscopic techniques in our lab allows new and exciting questions to be addressed in collaborative projects with the other groups in the research unit. Vice versa we also could successfully apply methods, which were developed in other projects of the research unit. Additionally we have shown the potential of the very new methods recently developed by the other groups in the research unit for our applications.

In the next sections we will give an overview and discuss the large potential that the results obtained so far promise for the future cooperative work in the next funding period.

Figure E.7: Mathematical model developed for the description of actin filament movement in the *in vitro* motility assay. Top row: Model of the actin filament and of the myosin molecule. Lower panel: Model of the cross bridge cycle and the respective biochemical states of ATP-hydrolysis.

4.1 Parameter estimation in spark images

In a first approach we used the extended structure tensor method developed in the central project (A) for estimating parameters of motion in confocal line scan images of Ca^{2+} -sparks.

From figure E.8 one can clearly see that the easiest description of a Ca^{2+} -sparks in terms of a source with subsequent diffusion alone is not adequate. The confidence measure and the estimated diffusion coefficient do not show a useful result (upper panels). On the other hand if assuming an additional exponential decay of the fluorescence signal, as e.g. buffers as Ca^{2+} -sinks, the resulting decay constants can be reliably estimated with this method.

As outlined in our renewal proposal, based on these preliminary results we want to further develop this method for the estimation of the parameters of motion in Ca^{2+} -spark images.

4.2 The use of anisotropic diffusion filtering for the analysis of motility assay data

The use of the 3D-anisotropic diffusion filtering in spatial and temporal direction (compare project A, Section 5) promises a significant enhancement in signal to noise ratio of noisy fluorescence images. By this newly developed technique objects are smoothed along their spatio-temporal trajectories which essentially is motion corrected temporal integration of the signal. As shown in figure E.9 this method allows the reduction of noise without changing the morphological parameters of the actin filaments. Improvements achieved hereby can be used twofold:

- Firstly quality of signals can be improved for easier and more accurate evaluation and so far unusable data can be evaluated.
- Secondly, if accuracy of results is high enough without this method, initial signal to noise ratio can be lowered. This offers less bleaching and/or higher temporal density of image acquisition.

Figure E.8: Parameter estimation in confocal line scan images of Ca^{2+} -sparks. In the upper panels grey value changes are restricted to diffusion and in the lower panels an exponential decay is assumed. Left panels are the original line scan images, the middle panels are the estimates for the diffusion constant in the upper row and for the exponential decay constant in the lower panel. The right panels show the corresponding confidence measures for the estimated parameters.

The simplified evaluation and novel experimental possibilities arising by this approach give confidence in the productivity of future investigations.

Figure E.9: Example of motility assay data set improved with the method of 3D-anisotropic diffusion filtering.

4.3 Analysis of particle trajectories in the *in vitro* motility assay

In preliminary work we could show that the approach developed in the group of Dr. R. Eils (project F) for analyzing particle movement in image sequences [16] can also be applied to the analysis of *in vitro* motility assay data. Especially the possibility to extract information on single particle trajectories in detail is of fundamental interest for the interpretation of actin filament movement. Individual motion parameters of actin filaments help to address the question of identifying different velocity populations in these experiments.

Also it is important to analyze the movement of individual filaments. This helps to detect velocity changes of single filaments and enables a direct analysis of individual filament paths. In our approaches with the structure tensor the velocity information is extracted with a pixel based algorithm and yet no information on single particles is available. Therefore this supplementary information is of great importance to fully understand and describe the interaction of actin and myosin in this assay.

Figure E.10: Left panel: Histogram of the velocity distribution in the *in vitro* motility assay obtained with a particle tracking approach. Right Panel: Trajectories of single actin filaments in the *in vitro* motility assay. Both results were obtained with the algorithms developed in the group of Dr. R. Eils (project F) [16].

From these very encouraging preliminary results it is evident that we want to intensify the work on these topics as detailed in our renewal proposal.

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F Dynamic processes in human cell nuclei

Research Group Cremer

1 Introduction and Summary

There is a variety of arguments and observations in favor of a highly ordered and functional 3D-architecture of the cell nucleus. But despite the development of advanced light microscopes and fluorescence labeling techniques, until now little is known about the organization of the chromatin in the nucleus and its role in the formation of chromosome aberrations which are closely correlated with various human diseases. In order to understand the mechanisms leading to such malignant diseases, it is highly desirable to study and understand not only the spatial but also the temporal organization of the chromatin structure.

Recently, it has become possible to directly study the dynamics of the chromatin structure inside the cell nucleus in living cells. An approach that provided many signals of sub-chromosomal size at once, and thus enabled a more detailed study of the types of chromatin motion that occur, was given by the fluorescence-labeling of newly replicated DNA in human cell nuclei with subsequent segregation of the labeled chromosomes into daughter nuclei. However, the quantitative analysis of such data has to be done by automated image analysis tools.

The nature of living cell microscopy data makes this a challenging task: the intensity of the excitation laser light has to be reduced to a minimum to avoid photo-bleaching and photo-toxic effects on the living cells under observation. Therefore, the data is severely degraded by photon noise. For the same reasons the temporal and spatial Nyquist theorems cannot exactly be fulfilled during the acquisition procedure. A large number of objects with strongly varying sizes (ranging from sub-resolution objects to object of several micrometer diameter) have to be tracked in 3D over time. The cell nuclei perform rotations, 3D translations and even deformations during the observation period. A possible bias by the user has to be excluded (e.g. the segmentation has to be done under same criteria).

The past funding period contained the following major items:

1. Adaptation of the 2π -tilting device to a conventional microscope and a confocal laser-scanning microscope
2. Acquisition of micro axial tomographic image sequences.
3. Algorithm development for the precise alignment of micro axial tomographic image sequences.
4. 3D-reconstruction of images with high and isotropic resolution.

Although the PhD graduate student position was immediately advertised, for one year it was not possible to find in this area any interested student. Then for 6 months the position was held by Dr. Arif Esa from Israel who had worked on image analysis of nuclear structure. Dr. Esa, however, soon accepted a position at the National Cancer Institute (NIH). Only then we succeeded to employ an Italian physicist, Dott. Antonio Cavallo (graduate from Rome University). Although his thesis in Physics had been in a completely different field, he started his work here with great enthusiasm and has realized a good basis for future work in the Forschergruppe. His goal is to obtain a Ph.D. in Physics from Heidelberg university as a further qualification. In the difficult situation described above, it was tried to support the scientific goals of this project as much as possible in the frame work of other Ph.D. work of the group of Prof. C. Cremer.

2 Reconstruction of micro axial tomographic image sequences

A major limitation of present optical light microscopy is the lack of resolution along the optical axis. E.g. the resolution of a confocal microscope is 2.5 times worse in axial direction than in lateral direction. In order to overcome this limitation, a 2π -tilting device was developed. It allows the rotation of the specimen under

the microscope and thus the acquisition of multiple microscopic (3D) images of the same biological object from different observation angles. From such a series of micro axial tomographic images a three-dimensional (3D-)image with high and isotropic resolution can be computed.

Alignment A major prerequisite for the computation an isotropic high resolution 3D-data set is the precise alignment of the individual 3D-images from the different angles of view including 3D-translations and rotations round all three axis. For this an iterative and automatic alignment method which does not require any special sample preparation techniques was developed. Such an approach is described in [38] by making use of a high frequency enhancing cross-correlation approach iterating over the angles of rotation. This technique was modified and used for the alignment of many experimental data-sets. The rotations were performed by a succession of shearing ([23] chapter 9.4.3) which can be performed in each plane by a Fourier-based shifting. Due to possible refractive index mismatch between embedding media and objective lens/immersion oil, the z-axis in light-optical microscopy is often not correctly scaled. Therefore, also the axial (z-)scaling was varied to optimize the cross-correlation coefficient, i.e the result of the matching.

Tomographic ML-reconstruction For the computation of an isotropic high resolution data set from measured axial tomographic views the maximum likelihood (ML) algorithm was modified to simultaneously maximize the likelihood of the reconstructed image for all measured images. The derivation of the ML-iteration formula is described in [19]. This approach offers the possibility to combine a sophisticated deconvolution method with a solution to the problem of tomographic data reconstruction. The rotational steps in the developed reconstruction algorithm were excluded from the iterative part of the procedure algorithm. The idea is based on a rotation and alignment of the measured data coordinate systems to a standard coordinate system defined by the reconstructed data set. This way, no rotation and shifting steps are necessary during the iterative reconstruction process, which considerably increases the computation speed and minimizes artefacts by the interpolation procedures.

Results To test the usefulness of the reconstruction method for the imaging of nuclear structures, simulations of a chromosomal structure model were performed. This procedure allowed a tight control of the performance of the algorithm. Virtual confocal images of such a simulation based on the “Spherical 1-Mbp Chromatin Domain” (1Mbp SCD-)model [25] were computed. The size of the simulated nucleus was ten micrometers in diameter. In the simulation the whole territory of chromosome 7 or chromosome X were labeled, respectively (simulations performed by Dipl. Phys. G. Kreth) and the process of confocal imaging was computed (see Fig. F.1). This was achieved by a convolution of the simulated original structure with an experimentally measured PSF. Then these data-sets were subjected to simulated photon noise. The maximum assumed photon count was equal to 200 photons per voxel in every view. For the single-view reconstruction the simulated photon counts was greater by a factor of three. For reconstruction, the data-sets were corrected, re-sampled and rotated to the position by the automated alignment procedure. Then the iterative ML-based reconstruction process was applied to the data (either to one or multiple views simultaneously). During iteration over-relaxation factors were used until the total number of 15 iterations was reached. The isotropic resolution in the reconstructed micro axial tomographic image is clearly visible in the maximum intensity projections given in Fig. F.2. Also no artefacts had been introduced by the reconstruction algorithm. From Fig. F.2 and from quantitative measurements micro-axial tomographic reconstruction also was found to be superior to single view ML-reconstruction. For more examples also for experimental data refer to [19].

3 Image analysis of dynamic processes in living cells

So far, the following image analysis procedures have been successfully applied to 4D (3D+time) image sequences of living cells.

Model-based-segmentation of sub-chromosomal foci On a sub-chromosomal level, the image stacks contained multiple signals of sub-chromosomal foci with a size comparable to the microscopic observation volume (the observation volume is defined as the volume of the PSF at half maximum [28]. They were segmented using a model-based algorithm which detected local maxima and used an iterative region-growing process for the segmentation of individual foci. An improved implementation which also models the intensity distribution of individual foci and uses this information to subtract signal from neighboring objects, is described in [4]. In simulations and experiments, this approach yielded a significant improvement in localization accuracy [4]. This improved algorithm was used to analyze the present data.

Figure F.1: ML-reconstruction of micro axial tomographic image sequences of a simulated X-chromosome. First row: Original image in three different observation angles. Second Row: Virtual microscopic images of structures of first row. Third row: For comparison standard ML-deconvolution using only one individual input image. Last row: Isotropic, high resolution image using all micro axial tomographic images in the deconvolution procedure.

Matching of cell nuclei Since the recorded cell nuclei are moving and rotating during the observation period, the data has to be corrected for the motion of the cell nuclei. This is done by a correlation function analysis (CFA). A more detailed discussion on the CFA is given in section alignment.

Tracking of sub-chromosomal foci over time Since DNA foci represent objects with a size comparable to the microscopic observation volume, it was difficult to assign stable shape parameters. Therefore, in a first approach a template-based tracking algorithm was developed, which used two templates: The 3D-displacement from the object to be tracked to a candidate object, and the difference between the integrated fluorescence intensities (IFIs) of the two objects. The IFI was obtained by multiplying the brightness and the volume found by the segmentation algorithm described in [6]. This value was a more stable estimate than just the volume or just the brightness. To track an object from one image stack to the next, the maximum allowed displacement of an object, which defined the search volume, was given by the user. The basic principle is illustrated in Fig. F.3.

Statistical analysis of foci movement From the trajectories of individual foci determined by SPT quantitative parameters such as diffusion coefficients were determined. Furthermore, a statistical test was specially adapted for the detection of possible directed motions of individual foci. For details see [5], [10].

Short summary of the result of the motion analysis Application of the analysis tools to experimental data showed that mutual diffusion-like movements between foci located on different chromosomes were more pronounced than inside the territories. The statistical test for directed motion of foci inside chromosome territories revealed that foci occasionally switched from random to directional movements. Furthermore,

Figure F.2: XZ-Projections of the zero degree observation angle images of a micro axial tomographic image sequence of a simulated X-chromosome. First row: Original image (left) and virtual microscopic image of the same structures (right). Second Row: Standard ML-deconvolution using only the zero degree image (left) and isotropic, high resolution image using all three micro axial tomographic images.

for the first time it was possible to quantitatively show that sub-chromosomal foci persist as stable entities during a long observation period in vivo ($> 4\text{h}$). The results are presented in detail in [5], [10].

4 Cells in living-, fixed- and after labeling-state

Fluorescence in situ hybridization on three-dimensionally preserved nuclei (3D FISH) is the main tool to study (1) positions of chromosomes in the interphase nucleus, (2) morphology of interphase chromosomes, and (3) positions of genes within chromosome territories. The number of publication using 3D FISH is constantly growing. An alternative way to study interphase chromatin is to use replication labeling ([46], next section). Advantages of the later method are obvious: it allows in vivo observations. On the other hand, the replication labeling has strong limitations: it remains impossible to identify certain chromosomes or genes in vivo. Though FISH allows to study individual chromosomes and individual genes and though the majority of biomedical research is done using FISH, it requires some harsh treatments necessary for chromatin denaturation which are possibly destructive for the nuclear morphology. This fact raises the question about the degree to which the spatial relations observed using FISH may be extrapolated back to living cells. Therefore, an image analysis procedure was developed to compare 3D-distances between the same sub-chromosomal foci in three different stages of the same cell: in the living-state (after replication-labeling), after fixation and after "mock-FISH" labeling (principally the same treatment as used in Fluorescence In Situ Hybridization). The data was used as four-dimensional (4D-) data with 3 spatial dimensions and as the 4th dimension the different stages of the cells. A program for visualization of the 4D-dataset, with a graphical user interface (GUI) was developed (see Fig. F.4). The first version of this program allowed a threshold based segmentation with automated object identification, using six neighboring voxels to define the connectivity. After segmentation, pairs of spots can be selected by mouse click, and the corresponding 3D-distances can be computed with high precision.

The first results using this program showed that inside the cell nuclei there were differences in the 3D-distances between individual foci in different stages of cell preparation. Changes of large 3D-distances ($>10\ \mu\text{m}$) due to the different cell treatment (fixation, and mock-FISH labeling) were on average $0.315\ \mu\text{m}$, which was a relative change of 2.5%. Looking on smaller distances we were able to shown, also, that there were changes in the positions of very closely neighbored spots: this means that for very small structures inside a cell nucleus there were sensible modifications after fixation and hybridization. An example nuclei is shown in Fig. F.5, the result of the quantitative evaluation of this example nucleus is given in Table 1. These quantitative data are of utmost importance for the correct interpretation of structural FISH data.

Figure F.3: Schematic principle of the automated tracking of objects in time-lapse series of three-dimensional image stacks. (a) In a two-dimensional projection, the search volume for the central object comprises three candidates at the next sampling time $t=t_1$ (open circles). The search volume is given by a sphere with a radius of 900 nm. (b) For all objects, the integrated fluorescence at $t=t_1$ is compared to the integrated fluorescence intensity (IFI) of the central object at t_0 as a second feature. (c) A diagram that shows both features. (d) Displacements and the differences in IFI are normalized to the maximum difference (IFI) and to the maximum expected displacement which corresponds to the radius of the search volume. The object which is closest to the object at the origin is recognized as the matching partner in the next image stack.

Table F.1: L: Living cell nucleus F: Same nucleus after fixation M: nucleus after mock-FISH

	A-B	C-D	E-F	G-H
	3D distances (μm)			
L	14.077	6.377	13.536	8.412
F	14.234	6.942	13.491	8.456
M	14.037	6.361	13.162	8.263
	Differences (μm)			
L-F	0.157 (1.1%)	0.565 (8.9%)	0.045 (0.3%)	0.044 (0.5%)
F-M	0.197 (1.4%)	0.581 (8.4%)	0.329 (2.4%)	0.193 (2.3%)
L-M	0.040 (0.3%)	0.016 (0.3%)	0.374 (2.8%)	0.149 (1.8%)

The visualization tool developed here (Fig. F.4) is proposed to be extended to control the outcome of the 4D-particle tracking procedures and should then allow a user intervention in case of erroneously tracked sub-chromosomal foci or other objects .

In the current implementation the graphical user interface widget is no more than an helper: it displays the data in a suitable way and shows superimposed, the tracked spots (all of this operations are in real 3D). The core of this widget is written in C++ with support of the QT graphic library. Thus, the program can easily be implemented on another platform such as Unix, Windows Nt or LINUX (current implementation). The widget imports 4D data to display in three different channels (red, green and blue for three individual "time" steps) and then import from an external program the detected spots (common principle for plug-ins of graphic programs). In an overlay all the data is displayed and by user interaction, the program can

Figure F.4: Graphical user interface for segmentation and computation of variation of 3D-distances over time. With minor changes this tool will be used to control results of 4D-particle tracking and will allow a user intervention in case of erroneously tracked particles.

track interactively chosen spots, while discarding none-interesting spots. This approach has three different advantages:

- the program can display data and supplementary informations from an external programs (like a spot tracker) simultaneously, without the need for modifying the main core program.
- the program can be ported to any platform.
- it allows experts e.g. biologists, to choose what they like to trace

Recently, the widget was used in combination with a segmentation program developed in a previous project, without any modification of the programs.

5 3D optical flow determination

After completing of the image sequence analysis of living-, fixed- and mock-FISH-labelled cell nuclei, the work was started using the tensor methods developed by Project A. These algorithms for the determination of the optical flow using the structure tensor method in 4D have recently been implemented. Presently this algorithms are being tested for programming errors using simple test data. After this the necessary adaptation of the algorithms for the needs of the evaluation of synthetic and/or experimental 4D-data can be started.

6 Dynamic Chromatin Modeling and Virtual Microscopy

The present experimental findings about large scale chromatin structure suggest a organization of chromosomes in exclusive, 1-Mbp sized domains (experimentally observed structures were termed: sub-chromosomal foci) with a diameter range between 400-800nm ([46], [5]). A computer model for the quantitative modeling of chromatin structure is the relaxed "Spherical 1-Mbp Chromatin Domain (SCD)" model ([25]). Taking into account the limited knowledge concerning the actual folding of the chromatin fibre at the ultrastructural

Figure F.5: Example nucleus during the quantitative evaluation. The respective computed 3D-distances are given in Table 1.

Figure F.6: First implementation of the tensor method without any correction or processing (only one horizontal plane is shown): the data are chromatin model simulations from G. Kreth, see text for details (200 time steps of 128-128-40 voxels size).

level, this model makes no assumptions on the ultrastructural chromatin topology inside the 1-Mbp chromatin domains. This simplification allows for a drastic reduction (several orders of magnitude) in computer time and permits the computing of the entire set of chromosome territories in a model nucleus on a single personal computer within one day. This model has recently been dynamized, allowing the computation of 4D (3D+time) image sequences of chromatin structure. For details of the simulation see [25]. In combination with the above described "Virtual Microscopy" methods, it is now possible to analyze quantitatively the performance of 4D-image analysis methods with a realistic model of chromatin structure. In the accompanying proposal it will be explained how this model could be used in the remaining funding period for several important tasks of the analysis of dynamic processes of living-cells.

Research Group Eils

7 Introduction and Summary

With the completion of the sequencing of the human genome the three-dimensional and - considering the apparent dynamics of genome organization during the cell cycle and differentiation - four-dimensional genome analysis has become indispensable to understand the structural and functional compartmentalization of the cell nucleus. In phase II of the research unit (which has been the first phase for project F in the research unit) we have developed methods to study the dynamic organization of the genome and other nuclear components. In close collaboration with the central project A we have developed and implemented

- a 2D/3D image restoration method based on anisotropic, non-linear diffusion filtering
- an edge based segmentation approach for highly sensitive two-dimensional object segmentation
- a fuzzy-logic based method for tracking of dynamic structures in two- and three- dimensional image sequences
- a multi-dimensional scene viewer for visualization of 3D/4D processes
- and an object classification method based on spectral image information

The impact of these methods is reflected by a variety of applications both within the research unit and external collaborations:

- fully automated segmentation and tracking of cellular components
- study of gene expression events in live cells
- 3D- tracking and visualization of muscle filaments (project E)
- 4D- tracking and visualization of gas bubbles in fluids (project A)
- and automated classification of chromosomes and genomic regions based on multi-colour information

The results of the methodological developments and applications are well documented in more than 7 publications in peer-reviewed journals [9, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 41, 43]. In the following sections we will give a detailed report on the methods developed for multi-dimensional image sequence analysis (section 8). We will further briefly describe some of the major applications (8.4.1 – 8.4.2). For application of the methods within the present research unit please refer to the section in project E.

8 Time-resolved analysis and visualization of dynamic processes in living cells

The development of in vivo microscopy techniques and fluorescent reagents has stimulated interest in studying the dynamics of cellular processes (for review see [26, 29]). These types of experiments generate large and complex data sets and require tools for visual and quantitative analysis of the observed dynamic processes in space and time. Imaging fast moving vesicles in living cells at high speed and high spatial resolution generally implies a low signal-to-noise ratio, hampering accurate object detection. As a consequence of the optical aperture problem, tracking of small objects based on visual similarity criteria is difficult since many objects appear very similar [7]. Highly sensitive object detection and tracking has been recognized as crucial for an accurate evaluation of such data. However, a quantitative interpretation of trafficking vesicles has been generally based on manual evaluation of a user biased selection of objects with apparently highest motility. Such an evaluation is very time consuming and also limited by the perception of the manual inspector. In contrast, processes in the cell nucleus are much slower and need to be observed over a longer period of time. To avoid disruptions of nuclear processes the total light exposure during in vivo observation must be minimized. Thus, the signal-to-noise ratio and more importantly the number of time series taken in a particular experiment is considerably reduced leading to a loss in spatio-temporal resolution. Displaying time series as movies is a widely used method for visual interpretation. However, this approach does not improve temporal resolution, i.e. additional information about the continuous development of the observed processes between the imaged time steps (subpixel resolution in time) is not obtained. Furthermore, quantitative information is not revealed by such a visual approach. In a first approach to quantitatively describe nuclear

dynamics in vivo single particle tracking [35] has been used to estimate the diffusion of chromatin in living cells of different species [31].

We developed a versatile and fully automated approach consisting of four techniques, namely highly sensitive object detection, fuzzy logic based dynamic object tracking, computer graphical visualization, and measurement in time-space. Tests based on systematic model simulations show the reliability of the automated object detection and tracking method. Examples for potential applications of the method are the analysis of secretory membrane traffic and the study of functional dynamics of nuclear compartments enriched in pre-mRNA splicing factors.

8.1 Highly sensitive object detection

Imaging structures in living cells at high speed and high spatial resolution generally implies a low signal-to-noise ratio (Fig. F.7 (A)), hampering accurate object detection. We developed a two-step procedure for

Figure F.7: (Color image on CD) Detection of vesicles in hCgB-GFP transfected Vero cells. After release of secretion 40 images were recorded with a time lapse of 0.5 sec. (A) Enlarged region of interest of an unprocessed image at initial time step (B) Row profile of green line in image A with marked vesicle position. (C) After diffusion filtering the noise level is considerably reduced without losing significant object information. (D) Gray value profile of green line in image C after diffusion. (E) Following edge detection within the filtered image edges are connected to build regions. (F) Based on the induced region neighborhood graph vesicles are detected as regions with locally maximal intensity. For comparison, the unprocessed image A is overlaid with the detected vesicles false colored in red. Notably even weak and noisy vesicle signals (denoted by arrow head) are readily detected.

object detection. First, a constrained image smoothing by anisotropic diffusion is performed which removes noise without disturbing essential edge information (Fig. F.7 (C)). Anisotropic diffusion selectively diffuses an image I in regions where the signal is of constant mean in contrast to those regions where a rapid signal change occurs. The smoothing process within the Perona-Malik model is monitored by an abstract time-scale t , i.e. higher values imply stronger filtering [34]. The diffusion process depends solely on local

$$\frac{\partial u(\mathbf{x}, t)}{\partial t} = \text{div}(g(\lambda, |\nabla u|)\nabla u). \tag{F.1}$$

image properties and is governed by the shape of the so-called "edge-stopping" function g . Here an object scale dependent edge-stopping function based on Tukey's biweight robust estimator was applied, since

diffusion with the Tukey norm produces sharper boundaries than the Lorentzian (Perona-Malik) norm [3].

$$\begin{aligned}
g(\lambda, |\nabla u|) &= \frac{\rho'(\lambda, |\nabla u|)}{|\nabla u|} \\
\rho(\lambda, |\nabla u|) &= \begin{cases} \frac{|\nabla u|^2}{\lambda^2} - \frac{|\nabla u|^4}{\lambda^4} + \frac{|\nabla u|^6}{3\lambda^6} & |\nabla u| \leq \lambda \\ \frac{1}{3} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \\
g(\lambda, |\nabla u|) &= \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \left(\frac{|\nabla u|}{\lambda}\right)^2\right)^2 & |\nabla u| \leq \lambda \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad (\text{F.2})
\end{aligned}$$

For segmentation an edge oriented technique using a concept of local orientation was applied. Based on the smoothed representation candidate edge pixels are determined by a modified form of the standard non-maximum-suppression algorithm [33] including a weak hysteresis formulation. A pixel is classified as an edge pixel if it has a potential predecessor and successor (hysteresis) and if the magnitude of the gradient is maximal compared to the two neighbors in direction of the gradient (nonmaxima suppression). The first condition assists in the formation of unbroken contours while the second inhibits multiple responses to a single edge present in the data (Fig. F.7 (E)). To obtain closed borderlines edges were assumed to separate two neighboring homogeneous regions. A region was considered homogenous if its intensity values could be modeled by a Gaussian distribution. Edges were traced based on two parameters, namely local orientation and equal probability of belonging to adjacent regions. For small scale structures local orientation can be approximated by the direction of gradient. This induces a local coordinate system such that the orthogonal axis aligns with the isophote (line of constant intensity) parallel to the borderline. Since borderlines induce a partition of the image, the second condition implies that edge pixels need to belong to adjacent partitions with equal probability. As a result closed borderlines enclosing homogeneous regions are obtained. Based on the image partition a region neighborhood graph is built. Each node of the graph is associated with one region and is assigned morphological parameters such as mean intensity, shape and size of the respective region. Regions of interest are finally detected as regions with locally maximal intensity (Fig. F.7 (F)).

8.2 Dynamic object tracking

For dynamic analysis cellular objects need to be tracked in time-space. Based on object features such as size, shape, total intensity or texture, tracking an object amounts to finding its best match in consecutive images. According to the continuity equation of optical flow corresponding objects in consecutive images should be similar. However, distortions in the imaging process such as noise, bleaching, illumination differences as well as changes in focal position might considerably distort the time-space continuity assumption. Standard region-based matching techniques [1] do not give satisfying results in general. Our methods use a fuzzy logic based system for image sequence analysis [20] based on the assumption that object features are conserved in an indistinct (fuzzy) sense.

Fuzzy theory assumes that all things are matter of degree. Fuzzy systems behave as associative memories mapping close inputs to close outputs without requiring a mathematical description of how the output functionally depends on the input. A fuzzy system relies on a linguistic "rule" encoded in a numerical fuzzy associative memory (FAM) mapping, the FAM rule. According to a dynamic particle model the velocity of an object is assumed to remain relatively constant. To compare two objects in consecutive images differences in velocity and deviation of expected extrapolated position from the potential new position are measured. In addition differences in total intensity and area are computed and translated into fuzzy rules.

Each of these four parameters activates each FAM rule to different degree m_{ANT} . The scalar activation value act_j of the FAM rules' consequent equals the minimum of the four antesequent conjuncts' values. With correlation-product encoding the value of the consequent is multiplied by the activation value. By computing the fuzzy centroid the output is defuzzified to a single numerical value, the composite similarity measure c_{sim} . Objects in one image correspond to the object with the highest "defuzzified" similarity measure in the consecutive image.

$$\begin{aligned}
m_{ANT_{j_i}}(par_i), 1 \leq j_i \leq 3, 1 \leq i \leq 4 \\
act_{(j_1, \dots, j_l)} &= \min_{1 \leq i \leq l} m_{ANT_{j_i}}(par_i) \\
m_{OFAM_{(j_1, \dots, j_l)}}(y) &= act_{(j_1, \dots, j_l)} m_{CONS_{(j_1, \dots, j_l)}}(y) \\
c_{sim} &= \sum_{(j_1, \dots, j_l)} \frac{\int m_{OFAM_{(j_1, \dots, j_l)}}(y) y dy}{\int m_{OFAM_{(j_1, \dots, j_l)}}(y) dy} \quad (\text{F.3})
\end{aligned}$$

Figure F.8: (Color image on CD) Time-space tracking of vesicles for the cell shown in Fig. F.7. (A) Tracking and interpolation between consecutive time steps is demonstrated for 4 out of 40 sections at indicated time steps. The sequence of original images is embedded into the continuous time-space where time evolves along the vertical axis. The highlighted rings on trajectories correspond to intersections of the image sequence with interpolated trajectories. (B) After time-space interpolation trajectories were categorized into three classes: stationary (top), unidirectional (middle) and bi-directional (bottom). (C) Visualization of selected trajectories within the Open Inventor Scene Viewer. Fast moving trajectories are color encoded, while stationary trajectories are visualized in gray. For display reason only 20 of the stationary trajectories are shown. (D) Within the scene viewer the user may view the time-space from different directions, zoom and assign different colors and textures (not shown) to selected trajectories.

In case no corresponding object with a similarity value below a certain threshold has been found this object remains unmatched and the respective object track ends. A correspondence map together with the binarized images are the output of the image sequence analysis module and used for continuous visualization and quantification in time-space.

8.3 Continuous time-space reconstruction

We developed two different approaches for continuous time-space reconstruction. The dynamics of objects with constant shape over time is well described by the dynamic repositioning of their gravity centers. According to the correspondence map provided by the particle tracking module discrete trajectories are formed in time-space. By cubic b-spline interpolation between corresponding gravity centers they are subsequently transformed into continuous trajectories (Fig. F.8 (A)). Cubic b-splines were chosen for interpolation between corresponding points since they are stable in a geometric sense, i.e. they do not tend to oscillations even for a large number of sample points. Furthermore continuous derivatives exist up to the order of two. Note that the first and second derivative correspond to velocity and acceleration, respectively, which are crucial for quantification of dynamics (see below). The reconstruction procedure was embedded in a powerful multidimensional viewer (Open Inventor scene viewer, Silicon Graphics Inc., CA; available for almost all hardware platforms) providing a differentiated visualization of a large number of trajectories in time-space (Fig. F.8 (B)).

Figure F.9: (Color image on CD) (A-C) A series of three images after induction of transcription of BK-virus was taken at the indicated time steps. Detected speckles are outlined in green. Following *in vivo* imaging, the induced RNA was visualized by fluorescence *in situ* hybridization. The outline of detected RNA (red) is visualized within the time series for comparison. Scale bar in A denotes 1 μm . (D) Time-space visualization of the dynamic evolution of speckles (green) in relation to the induced RNA signal (red). The highlighted rings along the reconstructed shapes correspond to intersections of the image sequence with interpolated trajectories. (E) A close up of the speckle intersecting the induced RNA signal. (F) Time-space reconstruction of 20 images (time lapse: 1 min) from a speckle visualized after inhibition of RNA polymerase II.

The second approach was designed for visualization of objects dynamically changing their shape over time. This problem accounts to a continuous shape reconstruction from series of two-dimensional images in time-space [11, 14]. In a first step the binarized object representation is transformed into a parameterized contour representation (Fig. F.9 (A)-(C)). Thereafter corresponding boundary points in adjacent time sections are found by a global optimization scheme. Under the assumption that the transformation of one contour $\mathbf{k}_{v_1}(u)$ in its adjacent contour $\mathbf{k}_{v_{i+1}}(u')$ is sufficiently smooth and leaves the order of contour points

$$\begin{aligned}
 u &\rightarrow u' = \text{trans}(u) \\
 \text{trans}(u) &\quad \text{strictly monotonous increasing} \\
 \text{trans}(u) &\in \mathcal{C}^1 \\
 \frac{\partial \text{trans}(u)}{\partial u} &< \kappa, \quad \kappa > 1 \\
 \int_0^{u_{\max}} du &|\mathbf{k}_{v_{i+1}}(\text{trans}(u)) - \mathbf{k}_{v_1}(u)| \rightarrow \min.
 \end{aligned} \tag{F.4}$$

unchanged the optimal transformation is found by minimizing the integral over all Euclidean distances between corresponding contour points.

For minimization of this energy term a recursive contour splitting approach was chosen. A continuous surface reconstruction in time-space is obtained by b-spline interpolation of corresponding boundary points (Fig. F.9 (D)) and visualized within the graphical scene viewer. Triangles are essential primitives for computer graphical display. Hence, continuous surfaces need to be approximated by triangular meshes. To reduce the complexity of the triangle mesh while maintaining a close approximation to the original b-spline interpolation a multi-resolution strategy for visualization was developed. At each level of resolution triangles are formed according to the correspondence map in time-space. To obtain a homogeneous triangulation in time-space a triangle is further subdivided only if its maximal displacement from the b-spline interpolated surface exceeds a preset threshold [22].

8.4 Quantitative measurements

While multidimensional visualization is crucial for a qualitative evaluation of dynamic processes, morphological and dynamic parameters are required for quantitative measurements. Based on object outlines and the

time-space correspondence map a quantification module was developed. Within this module morphological parameters such as size and shape as well as dynamic parameters such as path length, velocity, acceleration, mean squared distances and diffusion coefficients are computed in a fully automated way. An interface to standard statistic software facilitates further evaluation and display of parameters (see below).

8.4.1 Application I: Dynamics of Secretory Membrane Traffic.

In a first study, we examined the motility of secretory vesicles mediating biosynthetic transport from the trans-Golgi network to the plasma membrane [45]. GFP was tagged to the secretory protein human chromogranin B (hCgB-GFP) in Vero cells followed by in vivo time-lapse microscopy. Following adaptive smoothing and segmentation (Fig. F.7) the object information was passed to the image sequence analysis tool for object tracking. Image analysis, graphical preprocessing and computation of dynamic parameters involving more than 500 vesicles in 40 time sections was performed in a fully automated way within 60 minutes on a standard Pentium PC or Silicon Graphics workstation. In comparison manual evaluation consumed more than four hours of user interaction for a small subset of 40 user selected vesicles with highest motility.

Within the time-space reconstruction module the resulting 391 trajectories were categorized as stationary, unidirectional or bi-directional according to their degree of motility (Fig. F.8 (B)). A trajectory was

Figure F.10: (Color image on CD) Quantification and visualization of surface dynamics for speckles in transcriptionally active cells. (A) A single frame from the video sequence shows highly variable morphology of nuclear speckles. (B) Quantification of surface velocities. For display reason velocities for eight representative out of a total of 45 speckles for this cell are shown. For each speckle surface velocities are calculated from the average velocity of corresponding boundary points in adjacent time sections. Note that b-spline interpolation, which does not tend to oscillations even for a large number of sample points, was chosen for time-space reconstruction of speckles. (C) Spatio-temporal reconstruction of speckles. (D) Detail from C.

considered as stationary if its mean velocity was below the average velocity of all trajectories. The group of remaining vesicles was subdivided into two classes: vesicles performing unidirectional motion and vesicles

reversing their direction of motion. A vesicle was considered as reversing its direction at a particular time step if the velocity vector averaged over three time steps before differed at least 130° in direction as compared to three time steps afterwards.

Trajectories were color encoded for easy interpretation of motility (Fig. F.8 (C)). Dynamic parameters such as mean squared distances, diffusion coefficients and velocities were computed. The vast majority (64 %) of vesicles were found to be stationary, while 31 % showed periods of fast directed movements interspersed by periods of slow random motion. The average velocity of non-stationary vesicles was 0.587 mm/sec as compared to 0.252 mm/sec for stationary vesicles. The maximum velocity measured for this cell was 1.23 mm/sec (i.e. 6 pixels/time frame; see Tab. 1). A smaller fraction (5%) showed a reverse in direction where half of these vesicles reverted their direction by 176° - 180° .

The plots of mean squared distances and diffusion constants show that stationary vesicles in normal cells as well as vesicles in cells with disrupted microtubules after addition of nocodazole undergo Brownian motion. These findings support a trial-and-error model for transport of secretory vesicles. According to this model vesicles are transported fast but on random tracks simply trying any direction to find a target membrane. It further suggests that vesicles perform fast directed movements if associated with microtubules and slow random search movements towards the next microtubule after dissociation. Interestingly, we also observed small clusters of vesicles apparently performing the same kind of random and directed movement bringing up the question whether those vesicles are associated with larger transport intermediates. The described techniques provide a fast and powerful tool to investigate how secretory traffic is regulated, e.g. to study the effect of cell motility or cell-cell contact formation on the transport of secretory vesicles.

8.4.2 Application II: Dynamics of transcription and pre-mRNA splicing.

In a second study, the described technique was applied to study gene expression events in vivo, in particular the tempo-spatial and functional relationship between transcription and pre-mRNA splicing. In the mammalian cell nucleus most splicing factors are concentrated in 20-40 distinct domains called speckles. GFP was fused in-frame to the amino terminus of the essential splicing factor SF2/ASF and visualized by time lapse microscopy. Time lapse microscopy shows that those speckles are highly dynamic structures [32]. BKT-1B cells, transfected with GFP-SF2/ASF cAMP-inducible early genes of BK virus, were triggered in vivo followed by time lapse microscopy.

After automated image analysis outlines of speckles and BK induced RNA were computed (Fig. F.9 (A)-(C)) followed by a continuous time-space reconstruction and computation of surface dynamics for these speckles (Fig. F.9 (D)). The continuous reconstruction shows that one of the speckles extends towards the BK virus gene and intersects the gene signal (Fig. F.9 (E)). Notably, the surface dynamics of all neighboring speckles measured by the average acceleration of surface points (data not shown) at each interpolated time step increases after transcriptional activation and reaches its peak when the first speckle hits the gene. Thereafter, the speckles show a rapid slow down in surface dynamics and a slight reduction in surface area.

In a different cell, speckles were imaged after addition of α -amanitin, a specific inhibitor of RNA polymerase II. After minimization of translational and rotational movement of the whole cell nucleus, speckles were detected as described above followed by continuous time-space reconstruction. Visualization of time-space reconstructed speckles shows that the morphology of speckles is much more uniform and rounded up (Fig. F.10 (C), (D)) than for speckles in transcriptionally active cells. Quantification of dynamics revealed a much lower surface velocity of 100 nm/min compared to untreated cells (Fig. F.10 (B)). A quantitative comparison of 269 speckles in transcriptionally active and 10 speckles in transcriptionally inactive cells showed a more than twofold difference in surface dynamics as reflected by acceleration of corresponding surface points. These findings represent quantitative evidence consistent with the view that nuclear speckles serve as transient storage/assembly sites for pre-mRNA splicing factors that are delivered to sites of active transcription.

8.5 Summary of dynamic image analysis method

The dynamic image analysis software has been shown to be a reliable tool for a quantitative analysis of complex data obtained from in vivo studies with GFP labeled nuclear marker proteins. The method can easily be applied to biological analysis of completely different dynamic cellular events. We have successfully applied this system to a wide variety of applications including the analysis of membrane traffic [43], the dynamics of pre-mRNA splicing factors in the nucleus of mammalian cells [12], GFP tagged centromeres (K. Sullivan and R. Eils, unpublished data) as well as dynamics of muscle filaments (see project E). With this method at hand it is now possible to study the functional dynamics of biological systems at high resolution in time and space.

9 Multicolor image analysis

Both multi-color fluorescence in situ hybridisation (M-FISH) and spectral karyotyping (SKY) are combinatorial staining techniques for the simultaneous detection and discrimination of the 24 human chromosomes [40] [37] [39] [17]. A unique combinatorial labeling of each chromosome or subchromosomal region (probe) allows the identification of every probe by its color composition. M-FISH has been shown to readily identify both structural and numerical aberrations [39] [17] [16]. The resolution limit of both M-FISH and SKY has not been well established yet, however the minimum resolvable size of an aberration is estimated to be in the range of 2-3 Mbp [44] [2] [18]. The molecular cytogenetic resolution of any of the established multi-color systems does not suffice to detect many small structural abnormalities for example in association with mental retardation [2] [21]. For the detection of subtle chromosomal rearrangements new concepts for probe design and image analysis need to be developed. To this end, we have recently described a 12-color M-FISH assay for subtelomeric rearrangements (M-TEL) to identify hidden chromosome rearrangements in apparently normal karyotypes (J. Brown et al., manuscript submitted). A further technique, the multi-color bar code approach [27], aims at a high-resolution breakpoint mapping for example in pre- and postnatal diagnostics [44] [36] or complexly rearranged tumor karyotypes [41]. The automated analysis and color classification of combinatorially labeled small probes is difficult since the image data is dominated by background rather than object information. We showed that classification based on distance in color space alone [17] fails for such data. We developed a new approach termed goldfish which combines direction in color space with spatial information for classification. This method can be applied for improving classification accuracy of the traditional M-FISH approach as well as for an accurate and fully automated analysis of differentially labeled small probes. The potential of this technique was demonstrated by application for fully automated detection of cryptic translocations in metaphases from mental retardation patients with an apparently normal karyotype and for multi-color bar coding of chromosome 12 in non-small cell lung cancer cells [41].

9.1 General approach to chromosome classification based on multi-color information

In this subsection we will describe a general approach for classification of chromosomes or subchromosomal regions based on color information. This approach will be then adapted for classification of differentially labeled small probes, where true color information is rare. For classification of M-FISH images a multi-color image analysis strategy was followed. Assuming that n fluorochromes are used for unique combinatorial labeling of chromosomes, each pixel can be regarded as a point in an n -dimensional space where each axis corresponds to one of the fluorochromes (Figure F.11 d). Together with the Euclidean distance measure the fluorochrome space spans an n -dimensional Euclidean color space. The classification strategy in color space is based on the idea that pixels belonging to the same chromosome and thus to the same color class (the unique fluorochrome combination used for labeling of this chromosome) correspond to a conical cluster of points with a characteristic direction in color space (Figure F.11 e). The direction of this cone is defined by the unique fluorochrome combination used for a particular chromosome. Distortions within images such as relative intensity variations, noise or background may have a significant impact on shape and direction of this conical cluster. To perform classification based on direction in color space a new representation of the data is introduced. Let $v=(v_1, \dots, v_n)$ be a vector representation of a data point in color space, where each entrance in this vector is given by the fluorochrome intensity v_i in the i -th fluorochrome channel (e.g. for 8-bit images in the range of 0 to 255). According to this notation each color class is represented by a unique color class vector, which is e.g. (255,0,0,255,0,0,0) for chromosome 13 in the seven color experiment (Figure F.12 d) since chromosome 13 is labeled by DEAC (channel no. 1) and cy3.5 (channel no. 4). The classification itself is performed in a three-step process. In a first step the image is tessellated (i.e. subdivided) into regions with similar color information (tessellation step). Based on the "average" color information of the regions a clustering is performed where the region color vectors are grouped together to form a known number of clusters (clustering step). Finally, each cluster is assigned to one of the color class vectors (classification step).

9.1.1 Region growing based on color information.

Image tessellation into regions with similar color information is performed by a region growing approach. Initially a region consists of an arbitrary chosen start pixel a . Each neighboring pixel b is fused with this region if the color angle difference $\cos(f)$ defined as the normalized projection length

$$\cos(f) = \frac{\langle a, b \rangle}{\|a\| \|b\|} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n a_i b_i}{\sqrt{\sum_i a_i^2} \sqrt{\sum_i b_i^2}} \quad (\text{F.5})$$

Figure F.11: (Color image on CD) Classification of a normal metaphase in a 24-color experiment. (a) A composite image is created by overlaying the individual five fluor channels (not shown) as described in Eils et al. (1998). (b) Classification on a pixel-by-pixel basis does not provide an accurate classification result. In particular, the color class of chromosome 21 blends into the color cluster associated with chromosome 2 (see set of pixels marked by an arrow in (d)). The classification based on the region oriented approach converges after three steps of iterations (c). Notably, the classification is much more accurate than the pixelwise classification. This is reflected by the fact that the two color clusters for chromosome 2 and 21 are well separated with the region oriented approach, since the angle between neighboring conical clusters is increased (e). False colors and fluors assigned to each chromosome class are shown in (f).

is below a preset threshold. The threshold, which depends on the labeling scheme and the number of fluorochromes, can be set manually or calculated automatically. For a five color experiment an angle criteria of 5 - 10 degrees proved to be appropriate. This process is iterated for all new pixels of the region. The region growing process for a region terminates if there are no more neighboring pixels with a sufficiently small color angle difference. Additional rounds of region growing processes are seeded by other pixels that have not yet been assigned to a previously computed region. The tessellation procedure stops when all pixels are assigned to a particular region. For each region an “average” unified color direction \hat{e} is computed by minimizing the following energy term:

$$\min \sum (\vec{M}_{xy} - \hat{e}I_{xy})^2 \quad (\text{F.6})$$

where \vec{M}_{xy} is the measured color vector in pixel (x, y) and I_{xy} the “intensity”, i.e. the projection of the color vector \vec{M}_{xy} onto \hat{e} .

9.1.2 Clustering and classification of color regions.

Having computed n regions in the tessellation step each of these regions is represented by its unified average region color vector \vec{e}_n . For each of the 23 color combinations one start vector (centroid) \vec{c}_m is selected from

the set of the n region color vectors as the vector which has the smallest angle with the theoretically optimal color vector. Then all region color vectors are clustered with respect to the set of 23 centroids cm as follows: a region color vector belongs to the cluster m represented by centroid cm which it has the smallest angle difference with. This clustering step is iterated where the next round of clustering is performed with respect to a new set of centroids where for each cluster a new mean centroid is computed as described above (formula F.6). The iteration stops when the Euclidean distance between the centroids of the previous iteration and the present centroids is below a preset threshold (typically $\ll 1$).

In a final classification step each centroid is assigned to the color class vector it has the smallest angle difference with. All region color vectors are then assigned to the color class its centroid has been assigned to.

9.2 Application I: Accurate analysis of highly rearranged metaphases

The above described classification strategy aims at iteratively adapting the color class vectors with respect to changes in intensities and noise within the fluorochrome images as well as hybridization heterogeneities within particular chromosomes. Classification by direction in color space is based on the normalized scalar product, which is not defined for zero length (zero intensity in all color channels). For low intensity levels the color difference is noise sensitive and thus not a robust classifier. Therefore, before chromosome classification noise reduction and background correction had to be performed. Here we applied a median filtering of the maximum projection of all fluorochrome images followed by thresholding for background elimination. Local noise and variation in color information were reduced by subdividing the image into regions of homogeneous color information thus providing a robust approach to color classification. The classification method is shown on a normal (Figure F.11) and aberrant metaphase from non-small cell lung cancer (Figure F.12). Notably due to hybridization heterogeneities, noise and/or cross talk between the different fluorochromes the classification is very much distorted without iteratively adapting the color class vectors (Figure F.11 b). After several rounds of iterations the clustering procedure converged leading to a more homogeneous and accurate classification (Figure F.11 c; Figure F.12 b) allowing a fully automated karyotyping of both normal metaphases and of metaphases with complex aberrations (Figure F.12 c).

9.3 Application II: Improving classification accuracy and sensitivity

F.13 1a shows the worst-case angle difference between the directions of two neighboring color classes for different fluorochrome combinations. For the original probe design5 employing five fluorochromes and a maximal number of three fluorochromes for one chromosome the worst-case angle difference is between two color classes which both have a triple color combination and share two fluorochromes. If the number of fluorochromes labels for a chromosome is increased to four the worst-case angle difference, i.e. the angle between two color classes sharing three fluorochromes, is decreased. Obviously this is an unfavorable probe design in terms of classification efficiency. In contrast to a ratio labeling approach [42], where the number of fluorochromes is decreased at the cost of classification efficiency, we decided to rather increase the number of fluorochromes to seven to reduce the maximal number of fluorochromes for a chromosome to two. In this case the worst-case angle difference is between two chromosomes sharing a single fluorochrome only. Note that the classification accuracy is thus increased by 27% compared to our original five-color assay5 and by 42% compared to the SKY-probe design as suggested in [37] [30]. This theoretical finding is in accordance with the experimental observation of increased classification accuracy by increasing the number of fluorochromes [2].

9.4 Application III: Cryptic translocations and intrachromosomal rearrangements

The M-FISH technology using chromosome specific painting probes is limited in cytogenetic resolution regardless of the imaging technology and probe design. One way to improve the molecular cytogenetic resolution limit of the M-FISH technology is to employ differentially labeled locus specific probes. In this case the resolution is solely limited by the size of the probe and thus improves molecular cytogenetic resolution by two orders of magnitude. To provide a sensitive approach to the identification of hidden chromosome rearrangements in apparently normal karyotypes, we have developed a 12-color M-FISH assay for subtelomeric rearrangements, termed the multiplex telomere (M-TEL) assay (J. Brown et al., manuscript submitted). This uses a set of 41 chromosome-specific cosmid, PAC and P1 clones, the majority of which are confirmed as within 500 kb of their respective chromosome end. Again an appropriate probe kit design proved to be crucial for the M-TEL assay. Here, we used two pools of 12 and 11 telomeres, respectively, which allows a full

Figure F.12: (Color image on CD) Classification of a highly rearranged metaphase from non-small cell lung cancer. (a) DAPI image. (b) Accurate classification with minimal flaring of fluorochromes at breakpoints is achieved by the region oriented approach. (c) Color karyogram computed fully automatically based on the color classification image. False color assignment and fluor mix for each chromosome are given in (d).

survey of all telomeric regions in two hybridizations. With this assay we only need to image two metaphases to obtain an accurate classification for all telomeres (F.13 1b). In typical applications only less than 0.1% of the entire image pixels originate from true signals whereas the overwhelming remainder is contributed by background noise. Figure F.14 shows a metaphase spread with a set of differentially labeled subtelomeric probes for 12 pairs of human chromosomes. Applying the above-described method for color classification of whole chromosomes does not provide a proper classification of differentially labeled small probes. Due to the low signal-to-noise ratio and because of the few pixels contributing to the 12 color classes there are no clear conical color class clusters in the multi-dimensional color space (Figure F.14 c). Accordingly, any classification method based on color information alone fails (Figure F.14 d).

Here we suggest adding a segmentation step to the color classification step to remove background regions before color classification. Application of median filtering to the maximum projected fluorescence images followed by anisotropic diffusion filtering for edge enhancement [43] yielded sufficient contrast for accurate segmentation of the telomeric signals. The maximum projection image is then tessellated into regions. Regions below or beyond a user defined size threshold are removed before classification. Figure F.14 f shows the classification of a subset of telomeres. Notably, the classification accuracy is high even though the respective distribution of pixels does not form any clear clusters in color space (Figure F.14 e). In Figure F.15 the potential of this method is presented for an individual with mental retardation, who had an apparently normal karyotype by G-banding. However, applying the M-TEL assay we could detect an unbalanced translocation involving chromosome 7 and chromosome 2, which was confirmed by conventional FISH with 2q and 7q probes (for clinical details see [24]).

A further limitation of the M-FISH technology is that the delineation of a chromosomal subregion participating in a rearrangement is often not possible based on the M-FISH results and a comparison of the

Tables

No. of fluorochromes	max. no. of combinations	Worst-case angle difference in color space	color discrimination efficiency
5	3	35.3°	1
5	4	30°	0.85
5	5	26.6°	0.75
7	2	45°	1.27
8	exactly 2	60°	1.7

Table 1a.

no. of subtelomeric probes	hybridization efficiency (%)	no. of fluors	no. of labels	probability for complete detection (%)	probability for accurate classification (%)
41	95	6	96	0.7	26.6
24	95	5	49	8.1	42.2
12 (M-TEL-pool A)	95	4	22	32.4	72.1
11 (M-TEL-pool B)	95	4	19	37.7	72.5
M-TEL (12+11)	95	4	41	12	52.3

Table 1b.

Figure F.13: (Table 1a) Classification efficiency of different probe designs for M-FISH. The worst-case angle difference denotes the angle in color space between the direction of two color classes, which share the maximum number of fluorochromes for a given probe design. The color discrimination efficiency is normalized to 1 for the original 5-fluor mix (Eils et al. 1998). (Table 1b) Classification accuracy of different probe designs for the M-TEL assay. The probability for "complete" detection denotes the chance to find one metaphase with all telomeric signals correctly hybridized. The probability for "accurate" detection denotes the chance to find one metaphase where at least one of the two telomeric signals of the two sister chromatids for a given chromosome arm is correctly hybridized.

banding pattern alone. Furthermore, intrachromosomal rearrangements cannot be detected since they do not result in a color change along the chromosome. Here we suggest the application of a set of well defined chromosomal bar codes [41]. To demonstrate the multicolor bar coding technique we analyzed breakpoints in cell lines derived from non-small cell lung cancers. To focus the analysis on chromosomes most frequently involved in structural aberrations in non-small cell lung cancers chromosome 12 specific bar codes selected from the CEPH-library based on previously published data [8] were applied [41]. The YACs and their band assignment are shown in Figure F.16 a. The fully automated color classification of a metaphase is shown in Figure F.16 b. Although some of the bands touch each other the classification allows an unequivocal separation and accurate classification of all bands (Figure F.16 a, Figure F.16 c). Interestingly, the multi-color bar codes for chromosomes are easily discerned even in the interphase nucleus (upper part of Figure F.16 b). These results indicate that chromosomal bar coding is an important addition to the chromosomal M-FISH technique since it allows for a fully automated breakpoint analysis with high resolution and accuracy. In conclusion, we have presented new concepts for probe design and image analysis to overcome most of the present limitations of the M-FISH technology. The combination of optimal probe design and highly sensitive automated image analysis results in a virtual 100% reliability to detect both inter- and intrachromosomal rearrangements. The new techniques combined with disease specific sets of differentially labeled small probes bear the potential to push M-FISH into routine molecular cytogenetic diagnostics.

Figure F.14: (Color image on CD) 12-color M-TEL assay. (a) shows the composite image calculated from the individual four fluorochrome images. Note that the significant background information, in particular for Cy3.5 (b), hampers accurate classification even by eye. (c) The distribution of all pixels in color space does not show any clusters. Accordingly, classification based on color information fails. (d) While single labeled signals can be still accurately classified (yellow telomeric signal on chromosome 6 in center), the classification of double labeled signals (red telomeric signal on chromosome 18 marked by arrow) is not unique. Furthermore, triple labeled signals would have been entirely misclassified (chromosome 22 in upper right corner marked by arrowhead). Since misclassification is mostly created by signal size differences in the four fluor channels, an accurate classification can only be achieved by combining neighborhood information with color information (f). With the region oriented approach we obtain one unique classification color for each telomeric signal although the color information for a given color class is well spread in color space (see red dots in the upper right quadrant in (e)).

9.5 Summary of multi-color image analysis method

The detection and correct classification of small interchromosomal aberrations, which cannot be deciphered by banding techniques alone, has been celebrated as the most important improvement of 24-color karyotyping by M-FISH and SKY as compared to GTG banding. The detection of chromosomal rearrangements with high sensitivity, specificity and classification accuracy, however, has still remained a challenge even with 24 color karyotyping techniques. Furthermore, subtle telomeric translocations and intrachromosomal rearrangements are undecipherable with any of the 24-color karyotyping techniques. In this paper we have described new concepts for probe design accompanied by newly developed image analysis software to overcome many of the present limitations of the 24-color karyotyping techniques. For fully automated image analysis we have developed a general approach for highly accurate classification of chromosomes or subchromosomal regions. This has been proven to be suitable for both 24-color karyotyping and classification of differentially labeled small probes. In the latter case our approach has been particularly successful where the image information is dominated by noise and true color information is rare. We showed that previously described classification approaches, which are solely based on color composition of pixels, fail for such data. However,

Figure F.15: (Color image on CD) Detection of subtle chromosomal rearrangements by the M-TEL assay. (a) Color karyogram for an individual with mental retardation, for whom conventional G-banded analysis reported a normal karyotype. Applying the M-TEL assay together with the region oriented approach for classification of small probes we could detect an unbalanced translocation on chromosome 7 (for clinical details see [24]). Note that the two telomeric signals for one of the two triple labeled chromosome 22 are classified differently. Since one of the signals is correctly identified, the green signal can be determined unequivocally as misclassified since it is classified as chromosome 4 which differs by one label when compared with chromosome 22 (see also concept of minimal requirement for accurate classification in Result section). For chromosome 8 and chromosome 12, where the telomeric signals misses at all, classification cannot be performed unequivocally. For distinguishing false positive and true results further metaphase were screened. For this karyotype, chromosome 8 and 12 proved to be normal. (b) Fluor composition and false color for the different telomeric signals.

accurate classification can be achieved by adding region neighborhood information to color classification. The discriminatory power and imaging efficiency of different M-FISH analysis systems are key factors in obtaining accurate and reproducible classification results. In contrast to theoretical considerations based on the Beer-Lambert law implying that signal-to-noise ratio is the limiting factor for sensitivity and classification accuracy of M-FISH or SKY, we showed that the most decisive factor for molecular cytogenetic resolution is the number and combination of fluors used for probe labeling. Some previously published probe designs proved to be unfavorable in terms of classification efficiency. In contrast to the concept of ratio labeling, where the number of required fluorochromes is decreased at the cost of classification efficiency, we found that increasing the number of fluorochromes further enhanced the sensitivity of the M-FISH assay. Importantly, by appropriate design of the labeling scheme the classification efficiency can be increased by 70%. Standard combinatorial probe designs fail to be specific and accurate at breakpoints due to blending of colors through fluorescence flaring. Consequently, the precise determination of a translocation breakpoint is very difficult if not impossible. This limitation can only be overcome by a conceptually new design of both probe design and image analysis. We suggest using 8 different fluorochromes, where each of the chromosomes is labeled by exactly two different fluorochromes. With this assay, fluorescence flaring causes the blending of colors

Figure F.16: (Color image on CD) Multi-color bar coding for high resolution breakpoint mapping in non-small cell lung cancer. (a) A set of 7 chromosome 12 specific YACs were applied for bar coding of chromosome 12. The YACs and their band assignment are shown on the right. The chromosome shown in composite colors (left) and classification colors (middle), respectively, shows a deletion of the most distal band (orange). (b) This metaphase has four chromosome 12 with two different bar codes. Within the three enlarged chromosomes (c) one is normal (lower left), the other two show the deletion described above.

which have not been present in the original labeling scheme. Accordingly, these new color compositions are unique and can be identified unequivocally. Although the 8-fluor assay bears the potential to achieve 24-color karyotyping with virtually 100% sensitivity, the molecular cytogenetic resolution remains limited. Experimental observation by us and others suggest that this limit is in the range of 2-3 Mb eluding hidden structural abnormalities which may result in clinically significant features such as mental retardation. This limitation can be overcome by employing sets of differentially labeled telomeric probes. In this case resolution is solely limited by the size of the probe, thus improving molecular cytogenetic resolution by two orders of magnitude. For highly sensitive identification of hidden chromosome rearrangements in apparently normal karyotypes, we developed the M-TEL assay for detection of subtelomeric rearrangements. The optimal design of this assay has again proved to be crucial for the applicability of this assay. Based on probabilistic considerations we designed a 12-color M-TEL assay which allows us to screen all telomeres in only two hybridizations. This assay was shown to be sufficient for the unequivocal classification of all telomeric signals within every second metaphase allowing its application in routine diagnostics. The identification of a chromosomal subregion participating in a rearrangement is often not possible even by combining M-FISH and GTG banding. Furthermore, intrachromosomal rearrangements cannot be detected since they would not result in a color change along the chromosome. For a fully automated breakpoint analysis with high resolution and accuracy we propose the use of a set of well defined chromosomal bar codes. For tumor cytogenetics this technique was shown to be an important addition to the chromosomal M-FISH technique. In conclusion, we have presented new concepts for molecular cytogenetic diagnostics by M-FISH with significantly increased sensitivity and classification accuracy. The combination of optimal probe design

and highly sensitive automated image analysis results in a virtual 100% reliability to detect both inter- and intrachromosomal rearrangements. The new techniques combined with the design of disease specific sets of differentially labeled small probes bear the potential to push M-FISH into routine molecular cytogenetic diagnostics.

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I Awards

- DAGM Award 1997
H. Haussecker, B. Jähne
A Tensor Approach for Precise Computation of Dense Displacement Vector Fields
19. Symposium für Mustererkennung, DAGM 1997
Braunschweig, Germany, September 1997
- DAGM Award 1999
John.L. Barron, H. Haussecker, B. Jähne, H. Spies
Differential Range Flow Estimation
21. Symposium für Mustererkennung, DAGM 1999
Bonn, Germany, September 1999
- DAGM Award 1999
Christoph Garbe, H. Haussecker, B. Jähne, H. Spies
A total Least Squares Framework for Low-Level Analysis of Dynamic Scenes and Processes
21. Symposium für Mustererkennung, DAGM 1999
Bonn, Germany, September 1999
- BioFuture 1999
Roland Eils
BioFuture-Preis des BMBF des Jahres 1999
- Anerkennungspreis der Deutschen Botanischen Gesellschaft
Dominik Schmundt
Jahrestagung der deutschen Botanischen Gesellschaft
Bremen, Germany, 1998

II Diploma, Dissertation, and Habilitation Theses

Diploma Theses

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- [50] Richard Fitzenberger, Lokale Transformationsmethoden zur Auswertung von Wellenneigungsbildern der Wasseroberfläche im Bereich kleinskaliger Oberflächenwellen, 1997.
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In Preparation

- [71] Klimm, Oliver; Cloud detection in multispectral remote sensing
- [72] Kuesters, Ralf; Raumzeitliche Untersuchung von Pflanzenwurzeln
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- [74] Reinmuth, Jutta; Tiefenrekonstruktion vertikaler Konzentrationsprofile in Wasser gelöster Gase mittels LIF

Dissertation Theses

- [75] Horst Haußecker, Messung und Simulation von kleinskaligen Austauschvorgängen an der Ozeanoberfläche mittels Thermographie, 1996.
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- [80] Balschbach, Günther; Untersuchungen statistischer und geometrischer Eigenschaften von Windwellen u. ihrer Wechselwirkung.... 2000.
- [81] Scharf, Hanno; Optimale Operatoren in der Digitalen Bildverarbeitung. 2000.
- [82] Schimpf, Uwe; Untersuchung des Gasaustausches und der Mikroturbulenz an der Meeresoberfläche mittels Thermographie. 2000.
- [83] Tvaruskó, Wolfgang; Zeit aufgelöste Analyse und Visualisierung in lebenden Zellen. 2000.
- [84] Wolfgang Kirsch; Biophysikalische Analyse der räumlichen und zeitlichen Verteilung von Ca²⁺-Ionen (Ca²⁺-Sparks) in Muskelzellen. 2000.

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- [85] Cavallo, Antonio; 3D-Bildfolgenanalyse
- [86] Fuß, Daniel; Bildfolgenanalyse von winderzeugten Wasser-Wellen
- [87] Garbe, Christoph; Net heat flux measurements using infrared image sequences
- [88] Gröning, Hermann; Geometrische, radiometrische und spektroskopische Kalibrierung von Videokameras
- [89] Kalkenings, Reinhard; IR-Spektroskopie
- [90] Kirchgessner, Norbert; Extraktion physiologisch-sinnvoller Koordinatensystem aus Bildsequenzen
- [91] Kraus, Stefan; Optimierung des DOAS-Algorithmus (GOME-Projekt)

- [92] Popp, Christopher; IR-Spektroskopie
- [93] Smoljar, Nadija; Bildgebende Spektroskopie an Pflanzen
- [94] Spies, Hagen; Range flow estimation : the movement of deformable surfaces
- [95] Wenig, Mark; Analysis of global gas emissions for multispectral image sequences
- [96] Wilms, Stefan; Mikroskopische Analyse der raum-zeitlichen Dynamik von Zellteilung und -Zellstreckung
- [97] Walter, Achim; Quantitative Analyse der raum-zeitlichen Dynamik von Blatt- und Wurzelwachstum

Habilitation Theses

- [98] Uli Schurr, Interaktion von Physiologie, Biochemie und Cytologie in wachsenden Pflanzen, 1999.

In Preparation

- [99] Dietmar Uttenweiler, Modelbasierte Fluoreszenzmikroskopie zur Untersuchung Biophysikalischer und Physiologischer Fragestellung. Seit 1997.

III Invited Lectures and Research Stays

1 External Research Stays of Members of the Research Unit

- Dr. Roland Eils
25.-28.04.1999
Bildverarbeitungsgruppe am Institut Albert Bonniot, Université Grenoble
25.-30.10.1999
Zellbiologiegruppe und BV-Gruppe am Scripps Research Institute, La Jolla, CA
- Christoph Garbe
01.1999-12.1999
Scripps
- Matthia Gebhard
25.-28.04.1999
Bildverarbeitungsgruppe am Institut Albert Bonniot, Université Grenoble
- Dr. Peter Geißler
28.-31.1.1999
Center for Machine Perception, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University, Prague, Czech Republic
- Dr. Horst Haussecker
07.1999-02.2000
Xerox Palo Alto Research Center (PARC), Palo Alto
since 03.2000 permanent employee at PARC, Palo Alto
- Volker Hilsenstein
10.1999-03.2000
Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California, San Diego, USA
- Wolfgang Kirsch
Okt. 1997 - Sept. 1999
Rush University Chicago
Labor Prof. Eduardo Rios
- Kaan Saracoglu
25.-28.04.1999
Bildverarbeitungsgruppe am Institut Albert Bonniot, Université Grenoble
- Dr. Uwe Schimpf
several stays of approx. one month
Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of California, San Diego, USA
- Dr. Hanno Scharr
28.-31.1.1999
Center for Machine Perception, Faculty of Electrical Engineering, Czech Technical University, Prague, Czech Republic
- Dr. Uli Schurr
April-Juni 1998
Research School for Biological Sciences, Australian National U, Canberra, Australia

- Hagen Spies
Sept. 1998 - August 1999
Department of Computer Science, University of Western Ontario, London (host: Prof. John Barron)
- Prof. Dr. M.N. Stitt
März-August 2000
Carnegie Institution, Dept. of Plant Biology, Stanford, USA
- Wolfgang Tvaruskó
25.-28.04.1999
Bildverarbeitungsgruppe am Institut Albert Bonniot, Université Grenoble
Dezember 1998
zwei Wochen am Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, Cold Spring Harbor, NY
- Mark Wenig
01.05.-03.06.1999
KNMI, The Netherlands
Gruppe von Prof. Dr. Hennie Kelder, Atmospheric Composition Group

2 Invited Lectures

1996

- [100] Jähne B., *Physics Colloquium*. U of Frankfurt, 24.04.96.
- [101] Jähne B., *Industrial Vision Days*. Vision '96, Stuttgart, 10.10.96.
- [102] Jähne B., *Informatik Colloquium*. U of Bremen, 13.11.96.

1997

- [103] Jähne B., *ABW-Workshop*. Technische Akademie Esslingen, 23.01.97.
- [104] Hering F., *24. Physikalischer Gesprächskreis Rhein-Neckar*. Heidelberger Druckmaschinen, 30.01.97.
- [105] Jähne B., *Colloquium of the Computer Vision Research Group (Prof. Perona)*. California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, 27.03.97.
- [106] Jähne B., *Colloquium of the Physical Oceanography Research Division*. Scripps Institute of Oceanography, 02.04.97.
- [107] Jähne B., *VDMA*. Hannover Messe, 16.04.97.
- [108] Jähne B., *KI 2 Seminar*. Bundeskriminalamt, Wiesbaden, 02.06.97.
- [109] Jähne B., *. Naval Research Laboratory*, Washington DC, 18.06.97.
- [110] Scharr H., *25. Physikalischer Gesprächskreis Rhein-Neckar*. Physikalisches Institut, Heidelberg, 19.06.97.

1998

- [111] Schurr U., *Kolloquium Scottish Crop Research Institute*. Dundee, Schottland, Januar 1998.
- [112] Schurr U., *Kolloquium des Albrecht von Haller Instituts für Pflanzenwissenschaften*. Göttingen, Februar 1998.
- [113] Stitt, M.N., *Keystone Conference on Regulation of Metabolism*. Copper Mountain, Colorado, April 1998.
- [114] Eils R., *Conference Focus on Multidimensional Microscopy*. Sydney, 17.04.98.

- [115] Schurr U., *Kolloquium Research School of Biological Sciences*. Australian National U Canberra, Australien, Mai 1998.
- [116] Schurr U., *Kolloquium Carnegie Institution*. Stanford, USA, Juni 1998.
- [117] Schurr U., *Kolloquium University of California Davis*. USA, Juni 1998.
- [118] Stitt, M.N., *Annual Meeting of EPS Graduate School*. Wageningen, September 1998.
- [119] Eils R., *Institutseminar*. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, Cold Spring NY, 15.10.98.
- [120] Schurr U., *Kolloquium Organismic and Evolutionary Biology*. Harvard University, USA, November 1998.
- 1999**
- [121] Scharr H., *Kolloquium Center for Machine Perception* Czech Technical University, Prague, Czech Republic, 28.01.99.
- [122] Schurr U., *Internationaler Workshop Xylemtransport*. Jülich, Februar 1999.
- [123] Geißler P., *Forschergruppe Bildverstehen v. Prof. Dr. Bernd Radig, Informatik IX*. München, 26.02.99.
- [124] Scharr H., *Forschergruppe Bildverstehen v. Prof. Dr. Bernd Radig, Informatik IX*. München, 26.02.99.
- [125] Engelmann D., *Forschergruppe Bildverstehen v. Prof. Dr. Bernd Radig, Informatik IX*. München, 26.02.99.
- [126] Wenig M., *Forschergruppe Bildverstehen v. Prof. Dr. Bernd Radig, Informatik IX*. München, 26.02.99.
- [127] Eils R., *European Meeting of Automated Molecular Cytogenetic Analysis (CA-AMCA)*. Budapest, 12.03.99.
- [128] Stitt, M.N., *Metabolic Networking in Plants*. U of Iowa, April 1999.
- [129] Eils R., *Annual Conference of the European Society of Analytic Cellular Pathology*. Heidelberg, 09.04.99.
- [130] Eils R., *Conference Focus on Multidimensional Microscopy*. Heidelberg, 13.04.99.
- [131] Eils R., *Institutseminar*. BV-Gruppe am Institut Albert Bonniot, U Grenoble, 27.04.99.
- [132] Jähne B., *Kolloq FORSCHUNG UND PRAXIS IN WASSERBAU UND WASSERWIRTSCHAFT*, U Karlsruhe, Neue optische Methoden und digitale Bildverarbeitung mit Anwendungen in der Strömungsmechanik, 20.05.1999.
- [133] Wenig M., *Koninklijk Nederlands Meteorologisch Instituut*. De Bilt, Niederlande, 27.05.99.
- [134] Schurr U., *Kolloquium Botanisches Institut der Universität Würzburg*. Würzburg, Juni 1999.
- [135] Jähne B., *Workshop Bildsensoren und Bilderfassungssysteme, 10 Jahre ZESS*, Zentrum für Sensorsysteme (ZESS), U Siegen, Zukunftsperspektiven der digitalen Bildverarbeitung in Relation zur Sensorik, 10.06.1999.
- [136] Eils R., *Annual Conference European Society of Molecular Cytogenetics*. Wien, 05.07.99.
- [137] Stitt, M.N., *International Symposium on Phloem transport and Assimilate Allocation*. Newcastle, Australien, August 1999.
- [138] Eils R., *Jahrestagung der Deutschen Mathematiker Vereinigung*. Mainz, 06.08.99.
- [139] Schurr U., *International Botanical Congress (IBC)*. St. Louis, September 1999.
- [140] Stitt, M.N., *Perspectives in Plant Biology*. Köln, September 1999.
- [141] Stitt, M.N., *Gordon Conference on CO₂ Fixation in Green Plants*. Oxford, September 1999.
- [142] Eils R., *Institutseminar*. National Cancer Institute, Bethesda, MD, 20.10.99.

- [143] Eils R., *Institutssseminar*. Scripps Research Institute, La Jolla, CA, 25.10.99.
- [144] Schurr U., *Kolloquium Gesellschaft für Strahlenforschung (GSF)*. , November 1999.
- [145] Eils R., *Jahrestagung des Dt. Humangenomprojekts*. München, 30.11.99.
- [146] Eils R., *Annual Conference American Society of Cell Biology*. Washington DC, 12.12.99.
- [147] Jähne B., *Informatik Kolloq*, U Freiburg, Bildfolgenanalyse zum Studium dynamischer Prozesse, 14.12.1999.

2000

- [148] Jähne B., *Annual Business Meeting Automated Imaging Association*, Orlando, Florida, European Machine Vision Market Trends, 11.02.2000
- [149] Jähne B., *Rank Xerox Palo Alto Research Center (PARC)*, Kalifornien, Computer Vision for Basic Scientific Research, 22.02.2000.
- [150] Uttenweiler D., *Actin filament sliding velocity in the motility assay analysed with the structure tensor method* Research Seminar MPI für Medizinische Forschung Heidelberg, 28.02.2000.
- [151] Stitt, M.N., *Molecular Biology of Plants*. Wernigerode, März 2000.
- [152] Spies H., *Workshop Filter- u. Interstitialforschung-Strömung u. Turbulenz*. Institut f. Hydromechanik, U Karlsruhe, 05.04.00.
- [153] Eils R., *Conference Focus on Multidimensional Microscopy*. Tokyo, 15.04.00.
- [154] Spies H., *Colloquium*. Dept. of Computer Science, U of Western Ontario, 19.05.00.
- [155] Schurr U., *Kolloquium Institut für Pflanzengenetik und Kulturpflanzenforschung (IPK)*. Gatersleben, Juni 2000 .
- [156] Stitt, M.N., *International Symposium on the Molecular Biology of plants*. Quebec, Juni 2000.
- [157] Gerlich D., *Tagung Computer Graphics and Visualization in Biological Science*. Heidelberg, 06.06.00.
- [158] Uttenweiler D., *Model based fluorescence imaging of elementary Ca²⁺-release events: from single ion channels to molecular assemblies*, Utopia 2000, Understanding the output of protein-protein interaction, DFG-Graduiertenkolleg Biotechnologie 388, 04.-05.Juli 2000

IV Guests

This appendix summarizes the guests of the research unit that either gave a talk in the colloquium or where guests of the research unit.

1 Research Stays of External Guests

Datum/Date	Gast/Guest	Thema/Topic
05.1998	Prof. Dr. W. Silk, U of California, Davies	
since 07.1998	Dr. E. Bock, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	Air-Sea-Gas-Transfer, Surface Chemistry at air-water-interfaces
03.1999	Kevin F. Sullivan, PH.D., Associate Professor, Scripps Department of Cell Biology	Dynamische Analyse von Bildfolgen in der Zellbiologie
04.1999	Matt Thompson, Harvard University	Leaf and root growth
11.1999	Prof. Dr. M. Holbrook, Harvard University	Leaf and root analysis.
11.1999 – 07.2000	Dr. Brad Launikonis, La Trobe University, Melbourne, Australien	
05.2000	Dr. Jochen Klinke, Scripps Institution of Oceanography	Wave spectra
05.2000	Dr. Vladimir Kudryavtsev, Ukraine	Wave spectra
05.2000	Dr. Vladimir Makin, KNMI, de Bilt, The Netherlands	Wave spectra
06.2000	Dr. Bruno Moulia, INRA Pontiers	Biomechanics of growing leaves
06.2000	Dr. Adom Gonzales, Rush University Chicago, USA	
07.2000	Prof. B. Osmond, Australian National U, Canberra	Leaf growth in varying environments
07.2000	Prof. Dr. David J. Adams, University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australien	
07.2000	Dr. C. Knight, Stanford University	Thermography of leaves

2 Talks Interdisciplinary Colloquium Image Processing

Winter Semester 1995/96

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
23.10.95	J. Hesser, Informatik V, U Mannheim	Echtzeit Volumenvisualisierung in der Medizin
06.11.95	C. Herwig, Zentrum für Kognitionswissenschaften, U Bremen	Bildfolgenverarbeitung für Aktive Beobachter
13.11.95	R. Eils, IWR, U Heidelberg	3D - Voronoi Diagramme zur quantitativen Bildanalyse in der Zellbiologie
20.11.95	J. Weickert, Zentrum für Technik- und Wirtschaftsmathematik, U Kaiserslautern	Kopplung lokaler Strukturanalyse und anisotroper Diffusionsfilterung
27.11.95	T. Scheuermann, Fraunhofer-Institut für chemische Technologie, Pfinztal	Tiefenscharfe Auflichtmikroskopie und Mikrostrukturvermessung
04.12.95	J. Bigün, EPFL Signal Processing École Polytechnique Fédérale, Lausanne	Image sequence analysis by motion segmentation
11.12.95	P. Maaß, Institut für Mathematik, U Potsdam	Wavelet-Methoden zur Bildkompression
18.12.95	T. Wolf, Institut für Mechanische Verfahrenstechnik und Mechanik, U Karlsruhe	Optische Meßtechnik und Fuzzy Logik zur 3-D-Deformationsanalyse
15.01.96	H. Mallot, MPI für biologische Kybernetik, Tübingen	Einfache Mechanismen des menschlichen Stereosehens
22.01.96	H.-G. Maas, Institut für Geodäsie und Photogrammetrie, ETH Zürich	Digitale Photogrammetrie in der Kalibrierung von Industrierobotern
29.01.96	U. Jäger, Fachbereich Elektronik STZ Bildverarbeitung, FH Heilbronn	Bildverarbeitung in der industriellen Qualitätssicherung
05.02.96	B. Lang, MAZ Hamburg GmbH	GIPSI - Ein SIMD-Prozessorchip zur linearen und nichtlinearen lokalen Bildfilterung
12.02.96	H. Herrmann, Fernuniversität Hagen	Die Imagine HISC Rechnerarchitektur für Computer Graphik und Bildverarbeitung

Summer Semester 1996

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
29.04.96	H.-P. Meinzer, DKFZ Heidelberg	Diagnose- und Therapieunterstützung durch medizinische Bildverarbeitung
06.05.96	M. Dohmeyer, Dr. Engler, DLR Göttingen	Anwendungen von Bildverarbeitungstechniken zur Untersuchung von Strömungsphänomenen an Modellen im Windkanal
13.05.96	R. Beranek, IWR Heidelberg und Institut für Ergonomie, TU München	Bestimmung des Blickpunkts durch Verfolgung der Augenbewegung
20.05.96	T. Waschek, DKFZ Heidelberg	Ein neuer Ansatz für Zielvolumendefinition in der 3D Strahlentherapieplanung mit Hilfe von Fuzzy-Logik
03.06.96	A. Spörl, ABB Forschungszentrum Heidelberg und IWR, U Heidelberg	Verarbeitung und Beurteilung von Sensorsignalen mittels Fuzzy-Logik
10.06.96	T. Wagner, Fraunhofer Institut für Integrierte Schaltungen, Erlangen	Texturanalyse für industrielle Oberflächenprüfaufgaben
17.06.96	B. Jähne, IWR, U Heidelberg	Optimale Filteroperationen zur Bewegungsbestimmung im Orts-Zeit-Raum
24.06.96	J. Bigün, EPF Lausanne	Segmentation by Means of Motion
01.07.96	Martin Lell, IWR und Botanisches Institut, U Heidelberg	Erste Ansätze zur Vermessung des Blattwachstums mittels Bildfolgenanalyse
08.07.96	J. Hesser, Informatik V, U Mannheim	3D Echtzeitvisualisierung

Winter Semester 1996/97

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
23.09.96	R. Grigat, Technische Informatik I, TU Hamburg	Vision Chips: Intelligente CMOS-Einchipkameras für die Messtechnik und Qualitätskontrolle
04.11.96	P. Soille, École des Mines, D'Ales, LGI2P	Morphologische Bildverarbeitung in Mehrkanal- und höherdimensionalen Bildern: Grundlagen und Anwendungen
18.11.96	E. Dickmanns, Universität der Bundeswehr, München	Maschinelles Sehen in Echtzeit
02.12.96	E. Weiß, Botanisches Institut, U Münster	Bildgebende Darstellung photosynthetischer Flüsse in Blättern höherer Pflanzen durch Chlorophyll-a-Fluoreszenz Imaging
09.12.96	S. Teiwes und H. Schwarzer, Berliner Institut für Optik (BIFO)	Optische Wavelet-Filter und Matched Filter zur Detektion von Defekten in Textilgewebebildern
16.12.96	U. Köthe, Fraunhofer Institut für Graphische Datenverarbeitung, Rostock	Parameterfreie Merkmalsextraktion mittels automatischer Skalenselektion
20.01.97	B. Höfflinger, Institut für Mikroelektronik, U Stuttgart	Digitale Silizium-Kameras für höchste Dynamik und Geschwindigkeit
03.02.97	C. Schnörr, Informatik, U Hamburg	Variationsansätze zur Segmentation und Merkmalsgewinnung aus Bildern und Bildfolgen
10.02.97	R. Mester, Institut für Angewandte Physik, U Frankfurt	Die Nutzung stochastischer Modelle in der Bildsequenzanalyse

Summer Semester 1997

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
29.04.97	W. von Seelen, Institut für Neuroinformatik, U Bochum	Analyse visueller Szenen
06.05.97	J. Burrows, Institut für Fernerkundung, Fachbereich Physik, U Bremen	GOME und Sciamachy: Fernerkundung der Erdatmosphäre
13.05.97	V.K. Makin, Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute, De Bilt, Niederlande	Coupling of wind waves with the atmosphere
20.05.97	O. Borchers, BASF AG, Ludwigshafen und IWR, U Heidelberg	Bestimmung der Größe und Geschwindigkeit der dispersiven Phase in Gas-Flüssigkeits-Strömungen mittels Digitaler Bildverarbeitung
27.05.97	J. Ruiz-del-Solar, Fraunhofer Institut für Produktionsanlagen und Konstruktionstechnik, Berlin	Biologisch basierte Verfahren zur Objekterkennung und Texturanalyse
03.06.97	J. Hornegger, Lehrstuhl für Mustererkennung, U Erlangen	Statistische Klassifikatoren in der 3D-Bildverarbeitung
17.06.97	J. Beyerer, Institut für Mess- und Regelungstechnik, U Karlsruhe	Datenfusion zur Gewinnung hochwertiger Bilder am Beispiel der Kriminaltechnik
20.06.97	D.Dabiri, Aeronautics, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena	Sources of vorticity within a spilling breaking wave
08.07.97	R. Wuertz, Institut für Neuroinformatik, U Bochum	Objektrepräsentation und flexible Matching Methoden

Winter Semester 1997/98

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
23.10.97	Dr. Wiebe Oost, Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute (KNMI) zusammen mit dem Seminar des Instituts für Umweltphysik	A project to find out more about gas transport, especially of CO ₂ , between ocean and atmosphere
28.10.97	Rafael Wiemker, U Hamburg	Robuste unbeaufsichtigte Änderungsdetektion auf multispektralen Luftbildern anhand von spektralen und räumlichen Merkmalen
11.11.97 MA	Prof. Dr. B. Jähne, IWR, U Heidelberg	SIMD-Bildverarbeitungsalgorithmen auf modernen Multimedia-Rechnerarchitekturen
18.11.97	Dr. Noffz, Informatik V, U Mannheim	Das Konzept eines FPGA-Prozessors
25.11.97	Dr. R. Lay, Informatik V, U Mannheim	Konzepte zur Programmierung von FPGA-Prozessoren
	Prof. Dr. Peter Schlüssel, Meteorologisches Institut, U München	Die kühle Haut des Ozeans - Messung, Parametrisierung und Fernerkundung
09.12.97	Weichuan Yu, Institut für Informatik, U Kiel	Rotated Wedge Averaging Method for Junction Classification
16.12.97	Stefan Dauwe, Botanisches Institut und IWR, U Heidelberg	Thermographie zur Bestimmung des Wasser- und Wärmehaushaltes von Pflanzenblättern
13.01.98 MA	Prof. G. Häussler, Angewandte Physik, U Erlangen	Möglichkeiten und Grenzen von 3-D Sensoren
20.01.98	Gerald Sommer, Institut für Informatik, U Kiel	Die algebraische Einbettung des Entwurfes verhaltensbasierter Systeme
27.01.98	Georg Wiora, Daimler Benz AG Forschungszentrum, Ulm	Kalibration von Streifenprojektionssensoren
27.01.98	Marc Knight, Dept. of Plant Sciences, U of Oxford	Imaging of Calcium in Plants - Effects of environmental Impact

Summer Semester 1998

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
12.03.98	Dr. Andres Kriete, Bildverarbeitungs-labor, Institut f. Anatomie und Zellbiologie, U-Klinikum Giessen	Methoden zur Modellierung und funktionellen Simulation biologischer Strukturen
23.03.98	John Barron, Computer Science Department, U of Western Ontario	Measuring 2D and 3D Corn Seedling Growth using Optical Flow
21.04.98	Marc Heiland, DKFZ Heidelberg	Der zyklische Zylinder - ein Modell zur Segmentierung und Bewegungsanalyse von Bilddaten des Herzens
28.04.98	Rolf Watzel, Institut für Datentechnik, TU Darmstadt	Detektion dendritischer Spine-Synapsen mit Hilfe der konfokalen Laserscan-Mikroskopie
19.05.98	H. R. Tizhoosh, U Magdeburg	Fuzzy Bildverarbeitung
26.05.98	Thomas Wittenberg, U Erlangen-Nürnberg	Bewegungsanalyse von Stimmlippenschwingungen anhand digitaler Hochgeschwindigkeitskameraufnahmen: Visualisierung und Quantitative Analyse von Heiserkeit
12.06.98	Michael Black, Rank Xerox Parc, Palo Alto, Kalifornien	Modeling of motion fields
16.06.98	Dr. Martin Gade, Institut für Meereskunde, U Hamburg	Untersuchungen zur Abbildung biogener und anthropogener Oberflächenfilme auf dem Meer mit Hilfe von Radarsensoren
14.07.98	Christian Senet, Institut für Gewässerphysik, GKSS Forschungszentrum GmbH, Geesthacht	Analyse von optischen Bildsequenzen der Meeresoberfläche

Winter Semester 1998/99

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
20.10.98	Jörg Seemann, GKSS Forschungszentrum, Geestacht	Analyse von Radar-Bildsequenzen der Meeresoberfläche
10.11.98	Tomas Werner, Technical University of Prague	Towards Visualizing Real 3D Scenes from Uncalibrated Views
17.11.98 MA	Horst Hahn, MeVis, U Bremen	Morphometrie und Modellierung der Lebergefäß
24.11.98	Christian Wolf, MPI für Astronomie, Heidelberg	(Thema wird noch bekannt gegeben)
01.12.98	Dr. Reinhard Koch, Katholieke Universiteit Leuven, Belgien	Kamerakalibrierung und 3D-Oberflächenrekonstruktion aus Bildern einer frei bewegten Kamera
08.12.98	Dr. Joachim Weickert, Dept. of Computer Science, U of Copenhagen	AOS Schemata: Effiziente und zuverlässige Skalenraummethoden zur Regularisierung N-dimensionaler Datensets
12.01.99 MA	Dr. Ryszard Kozera, Dept. Comp. Science, U of Western Australia	Shape Reconstruction from Photometric Stereo
19.01.99	Thomas Bülow, U Kiel	Fouriertransformationen und Gabor-Filter in hyperkomplexen Algebren. Theorie und Anwendungen in der Bildverarbeitung.
02.02.99	Dr. Dietrich Paulus	Verfolgung farbiger Punkte mit Anwendungen zur Szenenexploration

Summer Semester 1999

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
13.04.99	Christian Küblbeck, Fraunhofer-Institut für Integrierte Schaltungen, Erlangen	Automatische Konfiguration von Texturanalysesystemen
20.04.99	Josef Heers, Arbeitsbereich Kognitive Systeme, Fachbereich Informatik, U Hamburg	Parallele und global konvergente numerische Verfahren zur adaptiven Bildglättung
27.04.99	PD Dr. Herbert Urban, LS für Geometrie I, Zentrum Mathematik, TU München	Zur Kinematik der Bildfolgenauswertung
04.05.99	Dr. Bernhard Schoelkopf, GMD FIRST, Berlin	Pattern Recognition using Support Vector Machines
HD 11.05.99	Prof. Dr. Heiko Neumann, Neuroinformatik, U Ulm	Auswertung des Optischen Flusses zur Navigation und Hindernisvermeidung
MA 18.05.99	Dr. Karl Rohr, Arbeitsbereich Kognitive Systeme, Fachbereich Informatik, U Hamburg	Elastische Registrierung von multimodalen medizinischen Bildern
HD 25.05.99	Dr. Claus Orlemann, Institut für Physikalische Chemie, U Heidelberg	2D-Visualisierung von turbulenten Strömungen und Verbrennungsprozessen mit Laserspektroskopischen Methoden
MA 01.06.99	Prof. K. Daniilidis, GRASP-Laboratory, U of Pennsylvania	Explorative Reconstruction for Augmented Reality and Telepresence
HD 08.06.99	Catalin Dantu, IWR, U Heidelberg	Visualisation and analysis of dynamic volume data
MA 15.06.99	Prof. Dr. Thomas Sonar, AG Differentialgleichungen und Dynamische Systeme, Fachbereich Mathematik, U Hamburg	Bildverarbeitungsalgorithmen in der numerischen Lösung hyperbolischer Erhaltungsgleichungen
HD 22.06.99	Prof. Dr. Heinrich Niemann, Lehrstuhl für Mustererkennung (Informatik 5), U Erlangen	Analyse, Kodierung und Verarbeitung von Lichtfeldern Kurzfassung (40kB pdf)
MA 29.06.99	Dr. Joachim Weikert, LS Bildverarbeitung, U Mannheim	Optische Flußbestimmung mit raum-zeitlichen Glattheitstermen

Winter Semester 1999/2000

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
20.03.00	J. L. Barron, Department of Computer Science, U of Western Ontario, Kanada	Fuzzy Points: Algebra and Application (Kurzfassung)
MA 12.10.99	Prof. Karol Mikula, Dept. of Mathematics and Descriptive Geometry, Slovak U of Technology, Bratislava	Models and computational methods for processing of 3D image sequences
HD 19.10.99	Rainer Heintzmann, Institut für Angewandte Physik, U Heidelberg	Axialtomographie
HD 02.11.99	Matthias Muhlisch, Institut für Angewandte Physik, Arbeitsgruppe Digitale Bildverarbeitung, U Frankfurt	Subspace-Methoden, Total Least Squares (TLS) und Equilibrierung in Theorie und Anwendung
MA 09.11.99	Dr. Jan Modersitzki, Mathematisches Institut, Medizinische U Lübeck	Verrücktes Gehirn - Mathematische Methoden zur Bildregistrierung am Beispiel histologischer Schnittfolgen
HD 16.11.99	Tilmann Otto, Heidelberg Engineering GmbH, Heidelberg	Modellierung des retinalen Blutflusses durch Auswertung bewegungskorrigierter Angiographie-Bildfolgen
MA 23.11.99	Prof. Bart ter Haar Romeny, Image Sciences Institute, Utrecht U	Recent Developments in Scale-Space Computer Vision Research at the Image Sciences Institute, Utrecht University
HD 30.11.99	Markus Loose, Institut fuer Hochenergiephysik U Heidelberg	Ein CMOS-Bildsensor mit logarithmischem Antwortverhalten und eingebauter Kalibration
MA 07.12.99	Dr. Gerald Glombitza, Medizinische und Biologische Informatik, Deutsches Krebsforschungszentrum, Heidelberg	Medizinische Bildverarbeitung: Von der Bilddatenkommunikation bis zum klinischen Projekt
HD 14.12.99	Bernd Gutmann, U Karlsruhe	Phasentfaltung bei streifengebenden optischen Meßverfahren mit Hilfe naturanaloger Methoden
MA 21.12.99	Dr. Matthias Wulf, U Hamburg, FB Informatik und Studienstiftung des Deutschen Volkes	Modellierung zeitabhängiger rezeptiver Felder in der Retina mit einem einfachen diffusionsbasierten Ansatz
HD 11.01.00	Prof. Dr.-Ing. O. Löffeld, Zentrum für Sensorsysteme (ZESS), U-GH Siegen	Synthetic Aperture Radar - kohärente Fotografie mit Mikrowelle
MA 18.01.99	Dr. Laurenz Wiskott, Innovationkolleg für theoretische Biologie, Humboldt-U zu Berlin	Unüberwachtes Lernen von Invarianzen in einem einfachen Modell des visuellen Systems
HD 25.01.99	Prof. Dr.-Ing. H. Burkhardt, Lehrstuhl für Mustererkennung und Bildverarbeitung, U Freiburg	Invarianten in der Mustererkennung (Kurzfassung, 60kB pdf)
MA 01.02.00	Prof. Dr. J. Buhmann, Fakultät für Informatik, AG Computer Vision und Mustererkennung, U Bonn	Explorative Bildanalyse: Können wir glauben, was unsere Algorithmen sehen?
MA 15.02.00	Dr. Ralf Lay, Silicon Software GmbH, Mannheim	FPGAs in der Bildverarbeitung

Summer Semester 2000

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
MA 09.05.00	Dr. Stephen Keeling, Institut fuer Mathematik, U Graz	Nonlinear anisotropic diffusion filters for wide range edge sharpening (Kurzfassung)
HD 16.05.00	Jens Teichert, European Media Lab, Heidelberg	Monokulare Rekonstruktion zur 3-dimensionalen Modellierung und Verarbeitung (MoRe3D)(Kurzfassung)
MA 23.05.00	Dr. Vladimir Peckar, Philips Research Hamburg, Medical Image Analysis	Fast Object Selection by Front Propagation for Medical Visualization (Kurzfassung)
HD 30.05.00	Karsten Mühlmann, LS für Informatik V, U Mannheim	Echtzeit-Tiefenkarten aus Stereobildern
MA 06.06.00	Hagen Spies, Forschungsgruppe Bildverarbeitung, IWR Heidelberg	Bewegungsanalyse in Tiefenbildern mit botanischer Anwendung
HD 13.06.00	Peter Dillinger, LS für Informatik V, U Mannheim	FPGA-Bildverarbeitungsalgorithmen
MA 20.06.00	Dr. Hanno Scharr, Forschungsgruppe Bildverarbeitung, IWR Heidelberg	Anisotrope Diffusion und steuerbare Filter
HD 04.07.00	Gerhard Lienhart, LS für Informatik V, U Mannheim	Videokompression auf FPGA-Prozessoren
MA 18.07.00	Prof. Dr. Bernd Jähne, Forschungsgruppe Bildverarbeitung, IWR Heidelberg	Analyse dynamischer Prozesse in Orts-Zeit-Bildern
HD 25.07.00	Prof. Dr. Daniel Cremers, LS für Bildverarbeitung, Mustererkennung und Computergrafik U Mannheim	Formenlernen für die Bildsegmentation

V Addresses of the Current Members of the Research Unit

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